

NFDI-MatWerk Renewal Proposal – B1

National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

This is a public version of the NFDI-MatWerk Renewal Proposal – Part B1 (Sections 1-6 of the full proposal). Some information has been anonymized to comply with German privacy regulations.

List of Contents

1	General Information	1
2	Scope and Objectives.....	8
2.1	Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, specific aim(s) ..	8
2.1.1	Research domain and methods addressed by NFDI-MatWerk	8
2.1.2	Impact of NFDI-MatWerk on the relevant research landscape.....	10
2.1.3	Specific aims of NFDI-MatWerk over the next five years (for MSE and oneNFDI)	12
2.2	Objectives and measuring success.....	12
3	Consortium	14
3.1	Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest.....	15
3.1.1	Composition of and changes to the consortium	15
3.1.2	Involvement of Community through Participant Projects and FlexFunds	17
3.1.3	Training programs and related activities	19
3.1.4	Generated benefits for the community.....	19
3.1.5	Overview of the associated Participant Projects	20
3.2	The consortium within the NFDI and the national academic research system	27
3.2.1	Our connections to other NFDI consortia.....	27
3.2.2	Our connection to NFDI sections and Base4NFDI with its basic services	29
3.2.3	Our connection to other national stakeholder in RDM infrastructure	32
3.3	International networking	33
3.4	Organisational structure and viability	35
3.4.1	Organisational and governance structure of the consortium	35
3.4.2	Funding and consolidation strategy	37
3.4.3	Demand-oriented development	38
3.4.4	Sustainable use of Human Resources.....	38
3.5	Operating model	39
3.5.1	Data storage and computing power	40
4	Research Data Management Strategy	41
4.1	Scientific relevance and quality of the measures.....	41
4.1.1	Quality of implemented measures	41
4.1.2	Community-driven Infrastructure Use Case Selection	47
4.1.3	Overview of Infrastructure Use Cases	48
4.2	Metadata standards	53
4.3	Implementation of FAIR principles and data quality assurance	56
4.4	Services provided by the consortium	58
4.4.1	NFDI-MatWerk Service Architecture with technical components	59
4.5	Impact of changes of external conditions / constraints	61
5	Work Programme	62

5.1	Task Area Community Interaction (TA-CI)	64
5.1.1	Status of TA-CI's Field in MSE	64
5.1.2	General Objectives of the TA-CI	64
5.1.3	Measures and Work Packages	65
5.1.4	Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives	73
5.1.5	Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases	73
5.2	Task Area Workflows and Lab Environments (TA-WLE)	74
5.2.1	Status of TA-WLE's field in MSE	74
5.2.2	General objectives of TA-WLE	75
5.2.3	Measures and Work Packages	75
5.2.4	Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives	82
5.2.5	Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases	83
5.3	Task Area (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI)	85
5.3.1	Status of this Task Area's Field in MSE	85
5.3.2	General Objectives of the Task Area	86
5.3.3	Measures and Work Packages	87
5.3.4	Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives	91
5.3.5	Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases	92
5.4	Task Area Semantics and Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI)	93
5.4.1	Status of this Task Area's Field in MSE	93
5.4.2	General Objectives of the Task Area	93
5.4.3	Measures and Work Packages	95
5.4.4	Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives	103
5.4.5	Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases	104
5.5	Task Area Strategy Development (TA-SD)	105
5.5.1	Status of this Task Area's Field in MSE	105
5.5.2	General Objectives of the Task Area	105
5.5.3	Measures and Work Packages	106
5.5.4	Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives	111
5.5.5	Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases	111
6	Additional Aspects	112
6.1	Equity and diversity	112
6.2	Further comments	112
Appendix		1
1	Bibliography and list of references	1

List of Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration project
ADIS	Ab-initio Description of Iron and Steel
AFLOW	Automatic FLOW for Materials Discovery
AHoD	All-Hands-on-Deck meeting
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIFB	Applied Informatics and Formal Description Methods
AIMS	Applying Interoperable Metadata Standards project
API	Application Programming Interface
APT	Atom Probe Tomography
ASMO	Atomistic Simulation Method Ontology
BAM	Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung
Base4NFDI	NFDI Basic Services consortium
BFO	Basic Formal Ontology
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, since Mai 2025: BMFTR
BMFTR	Bundesministerium für Forschung, Technologie und Raumfahrt
BoD	Board of Directors
BVMatWerk	Federal Association for Materials Science and Engineering
bwFDM	Federal State Initiative for Research Data Management in Baden-Württemberg
CC-BY-US	Cultural change in sharing research data with and through the NFDI (NFDI working group/event series)
CECAM	Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire
CESAER	Conference of European Schools of Advanced Engineering Education and Research
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (data portal)

CMSO	Computational Materials Sample Ontology
CoE	Cluster of Excellence
CoMiTo	Correlative Microscopy and Tomography
CoRDI	Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)
CPSP	Composition-Process-Structure-Property
CRC	Collective Research Centre (German: SFB – Sonderforschungsbereich)
CT	Computed Tomography
CWL	Common Workflow Language
DALIA	Data Literacy Alliance
DaMic	Data-driven alloy and microstructure design of sustainable structural metals
DAPHNE	Data from Photon and Neutron Experiments (NFDI consortium)
DARIAH-DE	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities – in Germany
DFG	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Science Foundation)
DFKI	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz
DGM	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Materialkunde e.V.
DH.NRW	Digitale Hochschule Nordrhein-Westfalen
DINI	Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformationen
DIWAN	Digitaler Wandel in der Werkstoffprüfung project
DKZ	Datenkompetenzzentrum (English: Data Literacy Centre)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoD	Definitions of Done
DSaaS	Data-Stewardship-as-a-Service
DVM	Deutscher Verband für Materialforschung und Bauteilprüfung e.V.
EBSD	Electronic Backscatter Diffraction
eLabFTW	Electronic Lab notebook by Deltablot

ELM	Engineered Living Materials
ELN	Electronic Lab Notebook
ELSA	NFDI Section Ethical, Legal & Social Aspects
EM	Electron Microscopy
EMMC	European Materials Modelling Council
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology
EMPA	Eidgenössische Materialprüfungs- und Forschungsanstalt (Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERC	European Research Council
EU COST	European Cooperation in Science and Technology
EUDAT-CDI	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure
EuroMat	European Congress and Exhibition on Advanced Materials and Processes
EUSMAT	European School of Materials
EVOKS	Editor for Vocabularies to Know Semantics
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FAIR-DO	FAIR Digital Object
FAIR-GB	FAIR Grain Boundaries
FAIRmat	FAIR Data Infrastructure for Condensed-Matter Physics and the Chemical Physics of Solids (NFDI consortium)
FAU	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
FDOF	FAIR Digital Object Forum
Fdm.nrw	Landesinitiative für Forschungsdatenmanagement in Nordrhein-Westfalen
FEMS	Federation of European Materials Societies
FIB	Focused Ion Beam
FIB-EBSD	Focused Ion Beam Electronic Backscatter Diffraction

FID	Fachinformationsdienst (Specialised Information Service)
FIZ	FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur GmbH
FOR	Forschungsgruppe (English: Research Unit) - DFG funding programme
FTE	Full-time equivalent
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich
GAMM	Gesellschaft für Angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik
GEPRIS	Geförderte Projekte Informationssystem
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GRF	German Research Foundation
GridKa	Grid Computing Centre Karlsruhe
GRK	Graduiertenkolleg (English: RTG – Research Training Group)
GWDG	Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung
GWK	Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskommission (Joint Science Conference)
HeFDI	Hessische Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (Hessian Research Data Infrastructures)
HIDA	Helmholtz Information & Data Science Academy
HIFIS	Helmholtz Federated IT Services
HMC	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration
HoreKa	Hochleistungsrechner Karlsruhe (high-performance computer Karlsruhe)
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPI	Hasso Plattner Institute for IT Systems Engineering
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IAM4NFDI	Identity and Access Management for NFDI project
IAS	Institute for Advanced Simulation
ICAMS	Interdisciplinary Centre for Advanced Materials Simulation
ICME	Integrated Computational Materials Engineering

IDE	Integrated Development Environment
INM	Leibniz-Institut für Neue Materialien gGmbH
IRTG	International Research Training Group
ISC	Fraunhofer-Institut für Silicatforschung
ISWC	International Semantic Web Conference
IUC	Infrastructure Use Case
IWM	Fraunhofer-Institut für Werkstoffmechanik
IWS	Fraunhofer-Institut für Werkstoff- und Strahltechnik
IWT	Leibniz-Institut für Werkstofforientierte Technologien
JARA-CSD	Jülich Aachen Research Alliance Center for Simulation and Data Science
JL-MDMC-NEP	Joint Lab “Integrated Model and Data Driven Materials Characterization” NFFA-Europe Pilot
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD/ YAML-LD	JSON for Linked Data / YAML for Linked Data
KG	Knowledge Graph
KGI	Knowledge Graph Infrastructure
KGI4NFDI	Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for NFDI project
KIT	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie
KonsortSWD	Konsortium für die Sozial-, Verhaltens-, Bildungs- und Wirtschaftswissenschaften
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
livMatS	Living, Adaptive and Energy-autonomous Materials Systems (Cluster of Excellence)
LLM	Large Language Model
LOD	Linked Open Data

LPBF	Laser Powder Bed Fusion
LSDF	Large Scale Data Facility
MADICES	Machine-Actionable Data Interoperability for the Chemical Sciences
MAMBA	“Materials irradiation: from basics to applications” project
MAP	Materials Acceleration Platform
MaRDA	Materials Research Data Alliance
MaRDI	Mathematical Research Data Initiative (NFDI consortium)
Mat-o-Lab	Materials open laboratory
Meso-AID	Multiscale analysis and inverse design of uncertain meso-structures
ML	Machine Learning
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MPCDF	Max Planck Computing and Data Facility
MPG	Max-Planck-Gesellschaft
MPI-SusMat	Max-Planck-Institut für Nachhaltige Materialien
MSE	Materials Science and Engineering
MWO	MatWerk Ontology
NEP	NFFA-Europe PILOT
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (National Research Data Infrastructure)
NFDI4BIO IMAGE	National research data infrastructure for microscopy and bioimage analysis
NFDI4Cat	NFDI for Catalysis-Related Sciences
NFDI4Chem	Chemistry Consortium ion the NFDI
NFDI4Culture	Consortium for research data on material and immaterial cultural heritage
NFDI4DataSci ence	NFDI for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence
NFDI4Earth	NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences

NFDI4Energy	National Research Data Infrastructure for Interdisciplinary Energy System Research
NFDI4Ing	National Research Data Infrastructure for Engineering Services (Mechanical and Industrial Engineering)
NFDI4Memory	National Research Data Infrastructure for History
NFDI-MatWerk	National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science & Engineering
NFDIxCS	National Research Data Infrastructure for and with Computer Science
NFFA	Nanoscience Foundries and Fine Analysis project
NHR	Nationales Hochleistungsrechnen-Verbund (National High Performance Computing Alliance)
NHR4CES	National High Performance Computing Center for Computational Engineering Science
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NOMAD	Novel Materials Discovery project
OCDO	Open Crystallographic Defects Ontologies
OMERO	Open Microscopy Environment (OME) Remote Objects
OO-LD	Object Oriented Linked Data Schemas
OpenBIS	Open Biology Information System
OPTIMADE	Open Databases for Integration for Materials Design
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
ORKG	Open Research KG
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society
OSL	OpenSemanticLab
OVITO	Open Visualization Tool
PASTA-ELN	adaPtive mAterials Science meTadatA - Electronic Lab Notebook
PI	Participant Individual
PID	Persistent Identifier
PID4NFDI	Persistent Identifier Services for the German National Research Data Infrastructure

PMD	Platform MaterialDigital
PMDco	Plattform MaterialDigital Core Ontology
PMD-S	Plattform MaterialDigital Server
PP	Participant Project
PRIMA	PRovenance Information in MAterials science ontology
PSP	Process-Structure-Property
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt Braunschweig und Berlin
PUNCH4NFDI	PUNCH4NFDI - Particles, Universe, NuClei and Hadrons for the NFDI
QUDT	Quantities, Units, Dimension and Types ontology
RADAR	Research Data Repository
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA IG	Research Data Alliance Interest Group
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDM	Research Data Management
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
RPTU	Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität
RPTU-AME	RPTU Advanced Materials Engineering profile area
RSpace	Research Data Management Platform / ELN
RTG	Research Training Group (German: GRK – Graduiertenkolleg)
RUB	Ruhr-Universität Bochum
RWTH Aachen	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
SCC	Scientific Computing Center
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SeMatS	International Workshop on Semantic Materials Science
SFB	Sonderforschungsbereich (English: CRC – Collaborative Research Centre)

SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SLUB	Sächsische Landesbibliothek – Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden
SOL-AI	Symbiotic modular foundation model for accelerating solar energy materials development
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SPP	Schwerpunktprogramm (English: Priority Programme)
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
SWSA	Semantic Web Science Association
TA	Task Area
TAB	Technical Advisory Board
TA-CI	Task Area Community Interaction
TA-MDI	Task Area (Meta)Data Interoperability
TA-SAI	Task Area Semantics and Artificial Intelligence
TA-SD	Task Area Strategy Development
TA-WLE	Task Area Workflows and Lab Environments
TEC	Technical Evaluation Committee
TEC	Technical Expert Committee Base4NFDI
TIB	Technische Informationsbibliothek
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRR	Transregio (SFB/CRC variant)
TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology
TS4NFDI	Terminology Services 4 NFDI
TU9	Alliance of leading Universities of Technology
TUD	Technische Universität Dresden
UFR	Universität Freiburg
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

W3ID	W3C Permanent Identifier
WG	Working Group
WLCG	Worldwide LHC Computing Grid
WP	Work Package
XRD	X-ray Diffraction
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

B-1 Proposal Template Part 1

1 General Information

▪ Name of the consortium in English and German

DE: Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für Materialwissenschaft & Werkstofftechnik

EN: National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science & Engineering

▪ Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium

According to the DFG review board classification system [1].

4. Engineering Sciences

- 4.31 – Materials Engineering
- 4.32 – Materials Science
- 4.12-02 – Mechanics
- 4.12-03 – Lightweight Constructions
- 4.51-03 – Construction Material Sciences, Chemistry, Building Physics

▪ URL of the consortium website and repositories used for publishing output

Website of the consortium: <https://nfdi-matwerk.de/>

NFDI-MatWerk Zenodo Community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/nfdi-matwerk/>

Further output is published on various institutional repositories, available via the individual tools and services on the solutions area of the consortium website.

Please Note: Although the German Science and Humanities Council, as well as the German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures recommended changes to the NFDI structure in their evaluation reports [2,3] we are writing this proposal under the assumption that the NFDI funding and governance structure remains largely the same.

▪ Summary National Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science & Engineering

NFDI-MatWerk supports the still young discipline of Materials Science and Engineering (MSE) in its effort to theoretically and experimentally study, characterize and control engineering materials and their performance, as well as their processing and manufacturing. The ultimate goal of MSE is to design optimized materials for resource efficient usage. A major challenge particular to MSE data is their inherent interdisciplinary and multiscale character. Materials performance is determined by its heterogeneous microstructure, depending on chemical configuration, defects at atomistic levels, microscale deformations as well as macroscopic structures which all change with processes applied to materials. Therefore, in NFDI-MatWerk we develop a federated digital infrastructure for MSE and closely collaborate with physics (FAIRmat [4], DAPHNE4NFDI [5]), chemistry (NFDI4Chem [6]), NFDI4Cat [7]), mathematics (MaRDI [8]) and mechanical engineering (NFDI4Ing [9]). Therefore, NFDI-MatWerk is actively working on implementing 'oneNFDI' [10].

Due to a vast number of experimental, computational and analytical methods to reveal these dependencies, labs developed their own data tools. Missing standards and uncoordinated development hampered the digital transformation and implementation of FAIR principles [11]. NFDI-MatWerk steered the development into a community-driven process. Based on data usage profiles from different sub-disciplines we identified relevant scientific scenarios represented in Infrastructure Use Cases (IUCs), which challenge our infrastructure solutions.

NFDI-MatWerk will strategically advance the five most important objectives through five Task Areas (TA): to (i) include all stakeholders with Community Interaction (TA-CI); (ii) provide infrastructure solutions for (Meta) Data Interoperability (TA-MDI); (iii) easily develop, execute and share Workflows and Lab Environments (TA-WLE); (iv) provide and integrate semantic descriptions and AI (TA-SAI) for interoperability, and (v) establish a Strategy Development (TA-SD) towards a digital transformation of MSE.

Leverage advantages of AI and ML within the MSE community is strongly correlated to the development materials ontologies and workflows as well as establishing a central MSE knowledge graph (KG) aligned to NFDIcore. Furthermore, we will continue establishing quality criteria and processes for the curation of MSE data. Since acceptance and dissemination in the community has grown markedly, FlexFunds will be introduced in the next funding period to simplify a broad participation. We also shift our focus from solution generation to implementation by devoting more personnel to collaborate with participant projects. We will furthermore extend the roll-out strategy, while ensuring scalability and meeting the heterogeneous needs in a federated FAIR MSE research data infrastructure.

▪ **Zusammenfassung Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für Materialwissenschaft & Werkstofftechnik**

NFDI-MatWerk unterstützt die junge Disziplin der Materialwissenschaft und Werkstofftechnik (MatWerk) in ihrem Bestreben, hochtechnologische Werkstoffe und deren Eigenschaften sowie deren Verarbeitung und Herstellung theoretisch und experimentell zu untersuchen, zu charakterisieren und zu kontrollieren. Ziel der MatWerk ist es, leistungsfähige Werkstoffe für eine ressourceneffiziente Nutzung zu entwickeln. Die Leistungsfähigkeit wird durch ihre heterogene Mikrostruktur bestimmt, die durch chemische Konfiguration, atomaren Defekten, Verformungen im Mikromaßstab sowie makroskopischen Strukturen definiert und wird geprägt durch die Verarbeitung. Die Herausforderung für MatWerk-Daten ist ein inhärenter multiskaliger und interdisziplinärer Charakter, weshalb wir eng mit der Physik (FAIRmat [2], DAPHNE [3]), der Chemie (NFDI4Chem [4]), NFDI4Cat [5]), der Mathematik (MaRDI [6]) und dem Maschinenbau (NFDI4Ing [7]) zusammenarbeiten. Daher arbeitet MatWerk aktiv daran, „oneNFDI“ umzusetzen.

Aufgrund vieler experimenteller, rechnerischer und analytischer Methoden zur Untersuchung der Abhängigkeiten existieren viele verschiedenen Datenwerkzeuge. Fehlende Standards und

unkoordinierte Entwicklung verhinderten die durchgehende digitale Transformation und Umsetzung der FAIR-Prinzipien [8]. NFDI-MatWerk lenkt die Entwicklung hin zu einem gemeinschaftlichen Prozess. Auf Grundlage von Datennutzungsprofilen haben wir repräsentative wissenschaftliche Szenarien identifiziert, die wir in Form von Infrastruktur-Anwendungsfällen (IUCs) zur Prüfung von Infrastrukturlösungen nutzen.

NFDI-MatWerk wird in der nächsten Periode die fünf wichtigsten Ziele durch fünf Task Areas (TA) strategisch vorantreiben: (i) Einbeziehung aller Interessengruppen durch Community Interaction (TA-CI); (ii) Bereitstellung von Infrastrukturlösungen für Metadateninteroperabilität (TA-MDI); (iii) Entwicklung, Ausführung und gemeinsame Nutzung von Workflows und Lösungen für Laborumgebungen (TA-WLE); (iv) semantische Beschreibungen und KI (TA-SAI) bereitzustellen und zu integrieren und (v) eine Strategieentwicklung (TA-SD) für die digitale Transformation von MatWerk zu etablieren.

Die Nutzung von KI/ML in der MatWerk-Community ist eng verknüpft mit der Entwicklung von Materialontologien/-workflows und der Bereitstellung eines zentralen MatWerk-Wissensgraphen (KG), der auf der NFDIcore basiert. Darüber hinaus werden wir weiterhin Qualitätskriterien und Prozesse für die Kuratierung von MSE-Daten festlegen. Da die Akzeptanz und Verbreitung in der Community sehr deutlich zugenommen hat, sollen FlexFunds eine einfache und breite Beteiligung ermöglichen. Der Fokus verschiebt sich noch stärker von der Entwicklung auf die Implementierung in der Community, indem wir mehr Personalressourcen für die Zusammenarbeit mit den teilnehmenden Projekten einsetzen. Dazu wird in der Rollout-Strategie auf die Skalierbarkeit und die heterogenen Anforderungen einer föderierten FAIRen MatWerk-Dateninfrastruktur fokussiert.

- **Applicant institution**

Applicant institution	Location
Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V. (Fraunhofer)	München

- **Spokesperson**

Spokesperson	Institution, location
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- **Co-applicant institutions**

Co-applicant institutions	Location
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Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz (DFKI)	Saarbrücken
FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz-Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur GmbH (FIZ)	Karlsruhe
Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)	Jülich
Fraunhofer, Fraunhofer-Institut für Werkstoff- und Strahltechnik (IWS)	Dresden

Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU)	Erlangen
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT)	Karlsruhe
Max-Planck-Institut für Nachhaltige Materialien (MPI-SusMat)	Düsseldorf
Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH)	Aachen
Ruhr-Universität Bochum (RUB)	Bochum
Technische Universität Dresden (TUD)	Dresden

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Gesellschaft für Angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik (GAMM)	Dresden
Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon GmbH	Geesthacht
Hochschule Aalen	Aalen
Leibniz-Institut für Neue Materialien gGmbH (INM)	Saarbrücken
Leibniz-Institut für Werkstofforientierte Technologien (IWT)	Bremen
Max-Planck Gesellschaft e.V., Max Planck Computing and Data Facility (MPCDF)	München
Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg	Magdeburg
Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität Kaiserslautern-Landau	Kaiserslautern
Sächsische Landesbibliothek Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden	Dresden
Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB)	Hannover
Technische Universität Berlin	Berlin
Technische Universität Clausthal	Clausthal
Technische Universität Darmstadt	Darmstadt
Universität des Saarlandes	Saarbrücken
Universität Freiburg	Freiburg
Universität Kassel	Kassel
Universität Paderborn	Paderborn
Universität Stuttgart	Stuttgart

Contributions of participating institutions:

Please note: The contributions of our participating institutions match the resulting contributions of the participating individuals that are affiliated to these institutions. Therefore, contributions of

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Participating individuals

Participating Individual	Institutional affiliation
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Birgit Skrotzki	Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung
Dr. Stefan Klein	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Materialkunde e.V.
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Tilmann Beck	Deutscher Verband für Materialforschung und -prüfung e.V. & RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau
Dr. Simon Stier	Fraunhofer-Institut für Silicatforschung (ISC)
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Florian Pyczak	Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon GmbH
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Tim Dahmen	Hochschule Aalen
Prof. Dr. Peter Gumbsch	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie
Dr. Christian Müller Prof. Dr. Aránzazu del Campo Bécares	Leibniz-Institut für Neue Materialien gGmbH (INM)
Dr.-Ing. Matthias Steinbacher	Leibniz-Institut für Werkstofforientierte Technologien
Prof. Dr. Erwin Laure	Max Planck Computing and Data Facility
Prof. Dr. Manja Krüger	Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg

Prof. Dr. Heike Leitte	Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität Kaiserslautern-Landau
Prof. Dr. Sandra Korte-Kerzel Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Ulrich Kerzel	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
PD Dr. Thomas Hammerschmidt Dr.-Ing. Sarath Menon Prof. Dr.-Ing. Markus Stricker Prof. Dr.-Ing. Alfred Ludwig PD Dr. Rebecca Janisch	Ruhr-Universität Bochum
Katrin Stump	Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Claudia Fleck	Technische Universität Berlin
Prof. Dr. Nina Merkert	Technische Universität Clausthal
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Karsten Durst	Technische Universität Darmstadt
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Markus Kästner	Technische Universität Dresden
Prof. Dr. Hans-Georg Herrmann Prof. Dr. Christian Motz Prof. Dr. Frank Mücklich Dr.-Ing. Flavio Soldera Dr.-Ing. Florian Schäfer	Universität des Saarlandes
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Felix Fritzen	Universität Stuttgart & GAMM e.V.
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Gerson Meschut	Universität Paderborn
Prof. Dr.-Ing. Wenwen Song Prof. Dr. Benoit Merle	Universität Kassel
Dr. Irina Sens	Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB)

Contributions of Participating Individuals

Please note: The contributions of our participating institutions match the resulting contributions of the participating individuals that are affiliated to these institutions. Therefore, we refrain from listing these contributions here again. Details can be found in the participants' Letters of Commitment in the Appendix. In the following, we list the contributions of participating individuals that are affiliated to one of our (co-)applicant institutions.

Prof. Dr. Birgit Skrotzki (BAM): [Redacted]

Dr. Simon Stier (Fraunhofer Institut für Silicatforschung ISC): [Redacted]

Prof. Dr. Peter Gumbsch (KIT): [Redacted]

Prof. Dr. Sandra Korte-Kerzel, Prof. Dr. Ulrich Kerzel (RWTH): [Redacted]

PD Dr. Thomas Hammerschmidt (RUB): [Redacted]

PD Dr. Rebecca Janisch (RUB): [REDACTED]

Prof. Dr. Alfred Ludwig (RUB): [REDACTED]

Prof. Dr. Markus Stricker (RUB): [REDACTED]

Dr. Sarath Menon (RUB): [REDACTED]

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Markus Kästner (TU Dresden): [REDACTED]

- **Names and numbers of the DFG review boards (DFG-Fachkollegien) that reflect the subject orientation of the proposed consortium**

4.31 (Engineering)	Materials Engineering
4.32 (Engineering)	Materials Science
4.12-02 (Engineering)	Mechanics
4.12-03 (Engineering)	Lightweight Constructions
4.51-03 (Engineering)	Construction Material Sciences, Chemistry, Building Physics
4.51-05 (Engineering)	Applied Mechanics, Statics and Dynamics
4.43 (Engineering)	Computer Science
3.22 (Physics)	Statistical Physics, Nonlinear Dynamics, Complex Systems, Soft and Fluid Matter, Biological Physics

2 Scope and Objectives

2.1 Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, specific aim(s)

2.1.1 Research domain and methods addressed by NFDI-MatWerk

Research domain of NFDI-MatWerk: Engineering materials are at the core of almost all high-tech innovations that have shaped human history and that are needed to address present concerns. Human ages were named after materials humankind was able to master, e.g., the Stone, Copper, Bronze or Iron Age. Today many technological challenges are tightly coupled to limitations materials present, and for industrial production more than 50% of the total costs are caused by materials [19]. The still young research discipline MSE focusses on the fundamental and applied questions related to the complete lifecycle of such engineering materials (Figure 1a). The MSE community addresses today’s global societal challenges, e.g., climate change, resource scarcity, the transformation towards renewable energy, the necessity of a true (green) circular economy, reuse and renewal of infrastructure, safety and defence. They require MSE to follow

Figure 1: Materials microstructure is hierarchical by nature and determines their performance. This microstructure develops during manufacturing and can deteriorate during usage. Therefore, a digital materials representation requires the same hierarchical logic as well as the whole history of the material. a) materials play a crucial role in the circular economy, b) their microstructure is determined by defects on different size scales (from atoms to macroscopic size), c) which we can access and design by experiments and simulations and d) determine the properties and performance of materials.

a holistic approach: discovery and development of new materials, efficiency in materials production, enhancing materials' lifetime and improving the end-of-life usage or recycling possibilities (Figure 1a). Since any interaction with a material (e.g. mechanical, chemical) changes its hierarchical microstructure (inner structure of materials, Figure 1b and 1c) and therefore its performance, the data and information space of MSE is exceptional high-dimensional and needs to contain the full materials history and full hierarchical information. Isolated measurements of individual samples and classical data structures are by no means sufficient to determine and predict performance of modern materials. Hence, MSE requires community-driven materials information and knowledge management to master the societal challenges. Further, as an intrinsically interdisciplinary field, MSE depends on participation of neighbouring disciplines, e.g., condensed matter physics, chemistry, mechanics and process engineering and the related NFDI consortia.

The MSE community is part of engineering science (DFG Subject Areas [1] in Sec. 1) and covers the development and characterization of all properties (e.g., physical, chemical, mechanical) of different classes of materials, metals, ceramics, glasses, coatings and surface technology, polymer and biomaterials, functional materials as well as composites. Furthermore, MSE researches the fundamental mechanisms in processing engineering materials in metallurgy, sintering, synthesis, generative manufacturing and is responsible to transfer this knowledge into applicable manufacturing steps while achieving a performance relevant in applications.

Research methods addressed: The research methods in MSE are based on observations and hypothesis formulation as well as quantitative (virtual) experiments in the lab and in-silico, followed by an analysis of the data. Due to the hierarchical nature of the microstructure of materials an immense number of experimental techniques as well as simulation methods/codes exists to cover the different classes of materials, the different size scales and manufacturing

processes. Therefore, MSE teams have different lab and computational setups to be able to cover a certain subject area along the lifetime of a material (class). It is part of the MSE culture to combine and develop techniques into innovative scientific workflows (often across different groups) to discover and derive new materials' knowledge.

2.1.2 Impact of NFDI-MatWerk on the relevant research landscape

The MSE community is set on its path to face the digital transformation. External pressure from AI development, federal funding agencies requiring FAIR data as well as the strong global competition in MSE research societal challenges have nurtured the acceptance a great deal. In this setting, NFDI-MatWerk played a crucial role by:

Establishing the confidence that complex MSE data and workflows can be made fully reusable without losing information has hence been the biggest success of MatWerk. We firmly believe that this confidence had a huge impact on the MSE community. The second biggest impact was to provide a path through the irritating jungle of software, semantics, infrastructure and standards. **We have paved the way to consolidate the variety of services used in the MSE community** (cf. Sec. 3.4.2). The seamless integration of the FAIR Digital Object (FAIR-DO) concept, the development of a consortia-overarching ontology, the establishment of an integrated development environment (IDE) for workflows combined with the Python Workflow Definition, as well as the improvement of data exchange and interoperability between ELNs (ELN Consortium) have greatly reduced development costs in MSE research and have substantially improved FAIRness along the full data life cycle in MSE.

We developed a first iteration of a digital MSE architecture: NFDI-MatWerk provides a software, service, and tool architecture that enables a seamless FAIR research data infrastructure for MSE. It allows MSE teams and research institutions to understand how the path to their own RDM can become FAIR, to strategically plan a local implementation (e.g. institutional) and to connect it into the federated MSE FAIR research data infrastructure as well as the oneNFDI.

MSE demonstrators in IUCs: Together with our Participant Projects (PPs, see 3.1) and Individuals (PIs), NFDI-MatWerk has identified infrastructure use cases (IUCs) and has implemented workflow and semantics demonstrators in these IUCs to show how different elements of the MSE architecture can be connected to achieve FAIR digital dataflows. Several demonstrators have already been presented to the community (cf. Sec. 3.1), others have been added recently. All of them have earned very positive responses as they show the feasibility of a FAIR MSE infrastructure. Now demonstrators are being generalized together with more PPs and the usage simplified so that more MSE researchers can make research more efficiently. Based on demonstrators, interactive teaching material and blended learning approaches are developed further to enable researchers implement their own solutions. Furthermore, we will intensify the conduction of User Journeys and Data Journeys at the site of the PPs and PIs to help identify

needs related to the individual scientific workflows (e.g., ELN, workflows, semantics, storage, computation) to implement a federated FAIR MSE research data infrastructure.

Findability and Accessibility: NFDI-MatWerk has implemented a prototype MSE Knowledge Graph, compatible to the NFDI core ontology for oneNFDI, which will be further developed as a service to register e.g. MSE data sets, workflows, tools, research equipment, authors, institutions. With the second phase, this MSE-KG becomes the central backbone of the federated MSE information infrastructure and will be continuously enhanced by the community. Several projects already have committed themselves to further develop the necessary ontologies (application and domain level) and will register their materials data sets, published in local or public repositories, so that they are findable and accessible. Similarly, workflows and software packages, being developed e.g. in GitLab or GitHub, can be registered and linked to the data sets through the KG.

Interoperability requires standards on many different levels, from basic data formats, via domain specific information, to the way how data are processed. While all levels of interoperability are being integrated, the focus of NFDI-MatWerk lies on the domain specific standardization of materials data, information and knowledge, as well as workflows. Due to the high dimensional parameter-space defining materials and their performance, NFDI-MatWerk relies on semantic technologies. With their recent developments (as part of AI technology) and their improved usability, a FAIR materials information infrastructure solution becomes feasible, able to cover the depth and breadth of MSE. To improve interoperability, metadata schemas and materials (application and domain) ontologies have been introduced to the MSE and the larger science community (oneNFDI), in the latter case by actively supporting the development of the NFDI core ontology. For example, application ontologies were developed with PPs for microstructure description, compatible with the PMD core ontology for processing and materials properties as well as the NFDI-MatWerk ontology for institutions, experts and devices. Meta data schemas for ELNs are derived or mapped to the developing MSE ontology. The interoperability of data generation, processing and analysis workflows together with the employed software solutions is ensured by using IDEs, general workflow engines and common workflow languages. They further integrate semantic interfaces and a semantic description of data workflows.

Reusability: General reusability of MSE research data is a complex undertaking. In simple settings (e.g. specific atomistic code and simple crystal structure) this can be done by providing the boundary condition and certain files which were used. In more complex cases, where several simulation tools and data processing need to be orchestrated, the documentation for reusability becomes much more difficult. Our efforts on workflow environments provide the answer to these challenges. Experimental data is even more difficult to handle, since instrumentation, lab conditions, sample handling and processing cannot be simply saved into a document and copied between different labs. This is addressed by the NFDI-MatWerk generator for experimental

workflows. Further, as materials properties change in a non-linear fashion depending on sample manufacturing and preparation, Round-Robin testing has shown many times that even nominally similar settings do not guarantee the same results. The solutions presented by NFDI-MatWerk are therefore based on ontologies which allow to standardize data, information and knowledge and easily link them with information about sequential processes.

For example, IUC02 on creep data has attracted attention from several PPs which are now implementing the concepts and tools to make the output of their own scientific workflows FAIR. Within PP16, this development made it possible to replace the traditional paper-based lab book with the ELN eLabFTW. In TA-WSD the case study of nanoindentation in aluminum exemplifies the seamless integration of diverse technical solutions for data handling and analysis, enabling both the pursuit of specific scientific inquiries and the adherence to the FAIR principles. These demonstrators also show that the usability is still very much depending on learning new skills, e.g. structuring data and maybe even (co)develop application ontologies.

2.1.3 Specific aims of NFDI-MatWerk over the next five years (for MSE and oneNFDI)

In the next funding period, the standards, confidence and consolidation efforts mentioned above need to be established in the full MSE community. It can only be achieved, if we - as a community - master the challenges of the digital transformation together. Nevertheless, the added value of structured, reusable MSE data have already convinced a strongly growing number of colleagues and NFDI-MatWerk is providing services to enable more research groups to participate.

To make MSE data reusable we in the NFDI-MatWerk want to increase our efforts in (1) teaching metadata schema integration in ELNs/LIMS, developing workflows as well as ML techniques, (2) provide the possibility to participate in NFDI-MatWerk on creating new solutions for more research groups, (3) support more groups to exchange know-how (e.g. openBIS, Semantics, ...), (4) provide them a better technological support and advice decision makers, (5) give more interactive talks, enable more discussions as well as support the cultural change (e.g. special issues on digital transformation of MSE), (6) improve usability and expand the adaptation of our technological fundament for data driven MSE science to more groups by acquiring more external funding and help creating a novel community as well as (7) nucleate more novel research ideas.

2.2 Objectives and measuring success

Making our materials' data FAIR will create unprecedented added value by linking disconnected datasets to find new correlations and dependencies, using machine learning (ML) and accelerating knowledge creation. To design better and more resource-efficient materials for future generations, we seek to drastically increase the quality and value of research data in MSE.

Defining Success: Therefore, we define our success in how much we can reduce the *transformational costs* for the domain and our colleagues. We want to help reducing financial, personal, organizational, epistemological, legal and ethical costs for our community. While this is

difficult to quantitatively measure, we propose our more practical overarching objectives in the following. These objectives are detailed out in our work program, connected to measurable KPIs.

1. Inclusion, integration and enablement of all stakeholders for a user-driven, collaborative MSE research data infrastructure development

The overarching objective is to support the MSE community in the digital transformation process by disseminating practical, need-based solutions for RDM and promoting their effective integration into everyday research practice. This involves targeted communication through public relations, direct dialogue and cooperation with individuals, projects and working committees, as well as online platforms such as the project website. Teaching formats foster self-empowerment by offering tailored learning opportunities, such as workshops, blended learning, events (symposia, conferences) and live demonstrations. A structured roll-out of tools, workflows, and services – accompanied by counseling through a professional helpdesk, participation in community events, and an open community-membership – ensures practical relevance and ongoing adaptation based on user demand and feedback. The project aims to highlight relevant publications from NFDI-MatWerk and beyond, as well as strengthen networking with Base4NFDI [20] and other NFDI consortia to establish interoperability through oneNFDI.

2. Reliable, scalable, federated digital infrastructure for registration and publication of materials data and information according to the FAIR principles

The digital infrastructure forms the basis for handling interoperable and decentralized materials research data repositories. We envision a virtual ecosystem with an interoperable multitude of tools, services, and service providers. A central knowledge graph provides a common catalog while the larger part of the infrastructure, actual services and repositories, is decentralized – within participating organizations or public infrastructure. Scalability and interoperability of local and centralized infrastructures is a key factor. Within the ecosystem, we promote tools and services that use technology independent standards and interfaces according to the FAIR principles like the FDO (FAIR Digital Object) concept. To bring structure to the ecosystem, we continuously enhance our architecture. It covers the entire path from devices and workflows for data and metadata generation in the scientist's environment via validation and contribution to the MSE KG to storage and sharing across institutional and also industrial boundaries.

3. Framework for development FAIR workflows for data sharing and reuse

In NFDI-MatWerk, the FAIR principles apply in addition to research data also to the workflows that are used to generate, transform, (post)process or use these data. Workflows for computer simulations, experimental processes, AI applications and data transformation become reproduceable and reusable, if they are version-controlled, together with the environment in which they are or have been executed (e.g. similar to Conda). They become interoperable, if they are developed, formulated, and executed in established workflow languages. An additional requirement is the separation of workflows into individual steps (nodes) that can be newly

combined for a different application. The findability and accessibility are ensured if these nodes are (semantically) annotated and stored in repositories. The vision is a global dynamic space of FAIR nodes that capture all aspects of materials research such that all published routines can be redone by all colleagues, provided they have access to the corresponding equipment.

4. Interoperability by collaborative MSE ontology development, accelerated by AI

An ongoing objective of NFDI-MatWerk is to expand the semantic coverage and interoperability of MSE data by developing and harmonizing ontological components that capture the multiscale complexity of materials. NFDI-MatWerk will facilitate data sharing across platforms and disciplines by promoting consistent, extensible vocabularies and ensuring compatibility with community standards. As part of this effort, the aim is to curate a semantic map of MSE information that, on one hand, enables the identification of overlaps, alignment of terminologies, and harmonization of concepts, thereby supporting semantic interoperability across the community; and on the other hand, helps users discover ontologies and schemas to describe their data and workflows.

5. Developing processes to establish and implement data quality criteria

In NFDI-MatWerk the quality of data sets is high, if their generation is documented in a fully reproducible way and if all relevant meta-data (informatic, methodologic, materials specific) are added in a semantic manner. The objective of our work is to develop these criteria and corresponding tools for individual classes of MSE research data based on the underlying research questions. This work will be performed in our IUCs (see 4.1.3).

6. Collaborative strategic development of the digital transformation of MSE

The digital transformation of MSE is fast paced and activities constantly need to be adapted. We seek to continue to agilely respond to current developments in the domain as well as near-future technological developments (e.g. integration of agentic AI or semantic standards by oneNFDI). Therefore, NFDI-MatWerk continuously develops organizational processes as well as strategically identifies or changes our IUCs (see 4.1.3) and the corresponding PPs (see 3.1.5).

3 Consortium

The following chapter responds to “Readiness and Relevance of the Consortium” and “Consortium Structure and Viability”. We therefore will describe the consortia from an institutional as well as individual perspective and comment on changes relative to the first phase. Due to the monumental workload to create a transdisciplinary FAIR research data infrastructure aka oneNFDI, we aim to integrate as many solutions developed within NFDI consortia as possible. One way is to have co-spokespersons and Participants working within different consortia:

Harald Sack (FIZ) is member in NFDI4Memory and Base4NFDI, co-spokesperson in the consortia NFDI4Culture and NFDI4DataScience; Achim Streit (KIT) is co-spokesperson in NFDI4Ing; Matthias Müller (RWTH) is co-spokesperson in NFDI4Ing, NFDIxCs, participant in NFDI4Chem.

NFDI-MatWerk participants are also members of other consortia: Heike Fliegl (FIZ) in NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4DataScience; Marius Politze (RWTH) in NFDI4Ing, [REDACTED] (KIT) in NFDI4Ing as measure lead “Storage and Repositories”, Isabella Bierenbaum (KIT) in NFDI4Ing as member of the “Lenkungskreis”. Nina Merkert (Clausthal, PP 06) is also a participant in NFDI4Ing; Erwin Laure (MPCDF and in TA-WLE) and Thomas Hammerschmidt (RUB, PPs 01 and 21) are also members of FAIRmat.

Beyond this personal level, many NFDI-MatWerk member institutions are also participating in other consortia. Institutional involvement across NFDI consortia is published in GEPRIS [21].

3.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

3.1.1 Composition of and changes to the consortium

The consortium is composed of (co-)applicants and their institutions as well as participating projects, individuals and institutions (see chapter 1). The NFDI-MatWerk consortium consists of participating universities that receive about 70% of DFG funding spent in the subject areas materials engineering (DFG review board 4.31) and materials science (DFG review board 4.32) [22]. Fraunhofer Verbund Materials (roughly 5000 persons) is also part of NFDI-MatWerk and mostly funded by federal funding (e.g. BMFTR, BMW, BMV, BMUKN) and industry. Materials research in the Helmholtz Society is also represented through by FZ Jülich, KIT and HEREON. Furthermore, the two biggest societies in the field of materials science and engineering (MSE) are part of the consortium which extend the reach of NFDI-MatWerk to the larger community (e.g. by the topic work groups). Additional to the universities, many institutions and associations in these subject areas are an important part of the consortium. In this way, we are fulfilling our objective to represent and bring together Germany’s most important universities and non-university research institutions in MSE. The consortium consists of stakeholders that cover different materials classes, simulation methods, as well as experimental testing and characterization methods that are relevant to the MSE domain. Our consortium was joined by more organizations (e.g. MPCDF) during the first project years and will be joined by more participants for the second funding period to support our joint vision. The structure of the consortium (see 3.4) reflects the experiences and qualifications in research data management (RDM): the technical Task Areas Semantics and Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI), Workflows and Lab Environment (TA-WLE) and (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI) consist of the applicant institutions that are all highly qualified and experienced with RDM. The participating institutions bring in their deep domain knowledge in MSE and have mixed levels of experiences and qualification with RDM: in the process of working together with the TAs on the IUCs (overview of IUCs (see 4.1.3), one major aim is to increase their knowledge and level of FAIR RDM.

Figure 2: (left) Research institutions of various types from all throughout Germany are part of NFDI-MatWerk as either (co) applicants or participants; (right) Location of NFDI-MatWerk Participant Projects at either co-applicant or participating institutions.

Overview of NFDI-MatWerk Task Areas	
TA Name	TA Central Responsibility
TA Community Interaction (TA-CI)	This TA is responsible to stimulate the acceptance and vivid participation of the overall MSE community through communication, counselling, education / training and steady increase of the outreach.
TA (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI)	This TA is responsible for developing the Digital Materials Environment (DME) and for providing services to easily store, share, search, and analyze data and metadata while ensuring data integrity, provenance, and authorship.
TA Workflows and Lab Environments (TA-WLE)	This TA is responsible for advancing the digitalization in MSE by providing solutions for workflow management and electronic laboratory notebook software foundations that will improve both productivity and quality of the data processing and simulation aspects.
TA Semantics & Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI)	This TA develops ontologies and metadata schemas in close cooperation with stakeholders, tailored to their respective needs. It provides the foundations for interoperable, reusable, and machine-actionable data, while exploring the use of AI to support knowledge extraction across MSE domains.
TA Strategy Development (TA-SD)	This TA is responsible for managing the development of a digital strategy for our consortium and the MSE community.

Changes to the consortium: The consortium composition is constantly evolving through the uptake of new PPs and thus new participating institutions. During the first funding phase, a process was set up to integrate new members with their knowledge and support to collaborate within IUC teams. For the second funding phase, the former Participating Institution Ruhr-

Universität Bochum (A. Hartmaier as co-spokesperson in TA-MDI) and BAM (Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, with N. Huber and T. Hickel as co-spokespersons in TA-WLE) become co-applicants due to their strong background in RDM and MSE, as well as their commitment to NFDI-MatWerk. TU Dresden becomes a new co-applicant with Martina Zimmermann as co-spokesperson. For the RWTH Aachen, Marius Politze will become an additional co-spokesperson due to his expertise in IT-focused strategic and operational levels as well as his involvement in the NFDI basic services development. For Universität Nürnberg-Erlangen, Erik Bitzek will leave the consortium as co-spokesperson for TA-MDI and Peter Felfer will join as co-spokesperson for TA-WLE. Furthermore, Peter Gumbsch, former TA-MDI co-spokesperson from KIT, becomes Participating Individual, as will Frank Mücklich, former TA-CI co-spokesperson from Saarland University. Jan Janssen becomes co-spokesperson for MPI-SusMat, replacing Tilmann Hickel who has changed institutions. Antonio Krüger replaces Philipp Slusallek as co-spokesperson for DFKI.

Further growth of the consortium stems from Leibniz-Institute for New Materials INM (since 2024) and Hochschule Aalen, the Technische Universität Berlin, the Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg, the Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden, Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) and Universität Kassel joining in the 2nd funding period. The Christian-Albrechts-Universität Kiel and PTB (Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt Braunschweig und Berlin) left the consortium to focus more on physics consortia.

Overall, already during the first funding phase, one strategic goal of the consortium is to further integrate participants to reflect their specific workflows, gather representative data sets for testing infrastructure solutions and to empower participants in their RDM. In the second funding phase, the outreach of the consortium is expected to strongly increase due to the growing interest to actively participate.

3.1.2 Involvement of Community through Participant Projects and FlexFunds

Embedding in the community: PPs introduce typical tasks related to the everyday scientific life (e.g. combining data from different sources, creating digital representations of workflows) and exemplify needs of the MSE community. **Together with PPs**, NFDI-MatWerk developer **identify IUCs which represent common MSE related RDM challenges**. Developers from NFDI-MatWerk together with colleagues from PPs then develop solutions based on workflows, semantics and infrastructure. To continuously identify the needs and requirements as well as collect feedback in a structured way NFDI-MatWerk has set up, e.g. dedicated scientific event and interviews. One very important instrument for the interaction and engagement with the community are **User** and **Data Journey workshops** with PPs (e.g. with Transregio 285). Here we aim to a) identify the current status in RDM within the PP, b) empower PPs to identify relevant metadata schemas and semantics and c) guide them through the process of becoming FAIR by

using NFDI solutions. These workshops will be intensified as part of the new measure “**solution management**“ (see 5.5.3) by TA-SD. This will help to **match community needs** and our solutions and enable the tracking of **technology readiness levels (TRL)** (see 5.5) of infrastructure components.

In the next funding phase NFDI-MatWerk plans to further **increase the number of participants by introducing FlexFunds** (requested extra funding from 2029 on): PPs will be able to apply for funding to generalize and integrate their RDM solutions into the larger NFDI-MatWerk infrastructure. Often, this process requires resources to assure interoperability (in terms of software), semantic alignment (e.g. data sets and databases), or generalization of a solution to serve a larger community. Many DFG funded research projects develop solutions for data driven research and therefore a flexible financial tool allows to support their alignment and reuse. This allows to scale up the number of solutions for the community but needs NFDI-MatWerk to management (e.g. standardization, alignment, maintenance). The process for dedicated calls for proposals and external reviews will be set up.

To further lower the barriers of participation, NFDI-MatWerk introduces the **community membership** starting in Fall 2025. Becoming an official Participating Project or Individual requires some administrative effort (e.g. be recognized by DFG) the community membership allows single researchers and smaller working groups to interact closely with the NFDI-MatWerk consortium. The membership is free, and grants added value like Data Stewardship as a service, access to yet to be released tools, training materials, the possibility to apply for in-house workshops and more. Members can test new NFDI-MatWerk developments, thus becoming “early adopters”, giving back valuable feedback and feature requests. Additionally, they can contribute their own use cases, learnings and developments to NFDI-MatWerk and the MSE community, e.g. by uploading own open-source software, workflows and semantics to a community store.

The involved professional associations are actively enhancing our visibility and interaction within the MSE community, e.g. through own events such as the DGM (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Materialkunde e.V.) Lunchtalk, especially dedicated to “sceptics” as well as breakout sessions during the DVM (Deutscher Verband für Materialforschung und Bauteilprüfung e.V.) conference 2023 dedicated to participants from industry. Feedback and interaction possibilities are also given with many interactive events for sharing insights regarding RDM solutions conducted by NFDI-MatWerk, e.g. NFDI-MatWerk Conference in 2023 [32], NFDI-MatWerk Research Data Forum [33] in 2025. Dedicated symposia were part of major MSE conferences, e.g. Euromat (European Congress and Exhibition on Advanced Materials and Processes) 2023 [23], the AI-MSE Congress in 2023 [24], MSE Congress 2024 [25] and Materials Week 2025 [26] as well as the coming Euromat 2025 and MSE congress 2026. In total we were able to reach out to around 7500 event participants at 78 (educational) events. Additionally, interviews and surveys with diverse users

from MSE have been conducted in the past years to identify and verify major fields of action for the consortium regarding needed developments and solutions for FAIR RDM [27].

With the combination of these instruments, NFDI-MatWerk continues to broaden its embedding and acceptance in the community. Even more, with tools for self-empowerment and the possibility for contributions by the community, the consortium has an increasing lever for the movement to become sustainable.

3.1.3 Training programs and related activities

All levels: In the scope of NFDI-MatWerk activities, 29 educational events have been held by the consortium since the beginning of the project. In addition, numerous teaching materials and technical documents have been developed and uploaded to our NFDI-MatWerk Zenodo community [28], allowing for easy adoption for university MSE education. Wider dissemination of the educational materials created by NFDI-MatWerk is realized through DALIA (Data Literacy Alliance) Platform [29]. Furthermore, the consortium is currently preparing digital trainings for self-learning, e.g. for using the ELN PASTA [30].

PhD and PostDoc: With summer schools, a platform for roll-out and feedback processes has been established. Multi-day courses, aimed at equipping researchers with the necessary skills to handle, organize, and share their data effectively, ensuring compliance with funding agency requirements and fostering collaboration. Integrating case studies and hands-on workshops specific to MSE allows participants to apply RDM principles directly to their research, promoting a culture of data stewardship within the field. Due to the international character of summer schools organized by EUSMAT a vivid exchange of different approaches for RDM could be realized.

MSE students: Based on gained experience from conducted workshops and feedback on published materials, TA-CI initiated an exchange with “Studientag Materialwissenschaft und Werkstofftechnik e.V.” to prepare recommendations the university curriculum in MSE.

3.1.4 Generated benefits for the community

Until now, 110 services according to the DFG datasheet service categories have been developed by NFDI-MatWerk, reflecting the diversity of needs from the MSE community. The users can modularly combine the services that they need to perform RDM for their respective research workflow (see 0). To maintain these services and to keep them updated and secure, it is necessary in the long term to plan with costs [31].

Consequently NFDI-MatWerk services begin in the laboratory or the working group but to achieve long term sustainability these local workflows need to be interconnected with reliable and trustworthy infrastructures. While the FAIR principles form a direct goal for handling the data, the TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology) principles [32] are aimed towards the long tail of data handling. Operating, managing and maintaining of these

long-term and trustworthy infrastructures should not be in scope of individual research groups, but should be taken up by local, regional and national service providers. While it is crucial that researchers know how to handle their research data, it is as important to enable these IT service providers to keep up with the domain specific requirements. On the other hand, central service providers often optimize infrastructures differently: in the research context the ability to react to changes is key, central service providers aim for stability. Consequently, it is necessary to define the right handover points between the community and service providers, ideally without losing the identity of the data. Representing data as FDO, as endorsed by NFDI-MatWerk proposes a solution to this problem, as FDOs can be minted in the scope of the researcher and later be passed to service providers maintaining both flexibility and trustworthiness for long-term storage. Ever increasing data volumes and long-term responsibility for acquired datasets poses a significant challenge for service providers as this does not match typical project based and short-term funding that is available in scientific projects.

Especially the close collaboration with neighboring consortia like FAIRmat, NFDI4Ing, and NFDI4Chem ensures that researchers' needs beyond the scope of NFDI-MatWerk are fulfilled. With additional services such as on-demand workshops for user and data journeys with MSE research groups as well as the NFDI-MatWerk community membership with its benefits for researchers, NFDI-MatWerk provides a highly valuable set of benefits for the MSE community which will be further developed and adapted to the evolving needs of the community.

3.1.5 Overview of the associated Participant Projects

At the start of the first funding phase, NFDI-MatWerk had 20 PPs. We gained two additional PPs during this phase, bringing the total to 22. However, several PPs, including some Clusters of Excellence and SFBs, ended or dropped out for various reasons and are now shown in grey in the list below. For the next funding phase, we attracted nine new PPs, marked with ***new*** in the following overview. While it was difficult to create an interest in 2020/21, we experienced a strong increase over the last three years, leading to a PULL from many new PPs and stakeholders.

PP01 SFB/TR103 - From atoms to turbine blades – a scientific basis for a new generation of single crystal superalloys (Transfer Projects) – adapted from 1 st phase	
Contact: PD Dr. Thomas Hammerschmidt URL: https://www.sfb-transregio103.de Topics: TA-MDI, TA-WLE, TA-SAI	DFG subjects: 4.31-01, 4.31-04, 4.32-03, 4.32-04
Material/Methodology: Ni-/Co-based single-crystal superalloys / experiments and simulations Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC09, IUC10, IUC17	

<p>Contributions: Experimental and computational data sets on as-cast, homogenized and deformed superalloys; Data on structure-property relationships, particularly line-/planar-defects and mechanical properties; Integration of requirements from closely linked industrial partners; 10% FTE of PhD from SFB/TRR103 Transfer-Project 190389738 and multiple contributions from individual researchers; Blueprint for sustainable integration in NFDI beyond funding time</p>	<p>Engagement Continued exchange within network of 24 groups from SFB/TRR103 beyond funding 6 transfer projects of 8 groups ongoing, each with industry partner, with funding until 06.2028</p>
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PP02 Structural and chemical atomic complexity (CRC 1394)

<p>Contact: Univ.-Prof. Dr. Sandra Korte Kerzel URL: https://www.sfb1394.rwth-aachen.de/ Topics: TA-MDI, TA-WLE</p>	<p>DFG subjects: 4.31-01, 4.31-04, 4.32-03, 4.32-04</p>
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Material/Methodology: Thermodynamic and Kinetics of Defects / Simulations and Experiments
Related Use Cases: IUC04, IUC9, IUC15

<p>Contributions: [REDACTED]</p>	<p>Engagement: 15 groups</p>
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PP03 Method development for mechanical joinability in versatile process chains (TRR 285)

<p>Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Gerson Meschut, Dr.-Ing. Mathias Bobbert URL: www.trr285.de Topics: TA-CI, TA-SAI, TA-SD</p>	<p>DFG subjects: 4.11-03, 4.12-01, 4.12-02, 4.12-03, 4.31-04</p>
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Material/Methodology: Joining processes and loaded joints (metals, frp) / Experiments and Simulations
Related Use Cases: IUC01, IUC02, IUC10, IUC12

<p>Contributions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [REDACTED] • [REDACTED] • [REDACTED] 	<p>Engagement: 16 groups</p>
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PP04 Magnetolectric sensors: from composite materials to biomagnetic diagnostics – project A10 (CRC 1261) – dropped out, focusses on physics consortia

PP05 Hysteresis design of magnetic materials for efficient energy conversion (CRC/TRR 270)

<p>Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing Karsten Durst URL: https://www.tu-darmstadt.de/sfb270 Topics: TA-MDI, TA-SAI, TA-WLE</p>	<p>DFG subjects: 4.32-01, 4.32-03, 4.32-04</p>
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Material/Methodology: Functional magnetic and magnetocaloric materials/Additive manufacturing, AI
Related Use Cases: IUC04, IUC08, IUC12

<p>Contributions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [REDACTED] • [REDACTED] 	<p>Engagement: 20 groups</p>
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [REDACTED] 	
PP06 Working group Modeling of oxygen-free production (CRC 1368)	
Contact: Prof. Dr. Nina Merkert, Dr.-Ing. Hoang-Thien Luu, URL: https://www.sfb1368.uni-hannover.de/ Topics: TA-WLE	DFG subjects: 4.32-04
Material/Methodology: Composites between different metals / MD simulations to study atomic interactions at interfaces, transfer to the continuum scale by multiscale simulations Related Use Cases: IUC07, IUC17	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: Working group modeling consisting of 20 projects
PP07 Processing uncertain microstructural data (EXC2075-PUMD) – funding ran out	
PP08 ExIni Cluster Living, Adaptive and Energy-autonomous Materials Systems (livMatS) – funding ran out	
PP09 DIWAN - The Digital Transformation in Materials Testing: Necessary Actions for the Paradigm Change in Enterprises – funding ran out	
PP10 Integrated engineering of continuous-discontinuous long fiber reinforced polymer structures (IRTG 2078) – funding ran out	
PP11 ERC Starting Grant MuDiLingo: Ontology Design for Dislocations – funding ran out	
PP12 Data Science in internat. MSE education, qualification and life-long learning (EUSMAT)	
Contact: Dr.-Ing. Flavio Soldera, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Mücklich URL: www.eusmat.net Topics: TA-CI	DFG subjects: 4.31, 4.32
Material/Methodology: Supports teaching on RDM in MSE. Training materials, summer schools] Related Use Cases: IUC01	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: EUSMAT Team Faculty of Natural Sciences and Technology Saarland University
PP13 Correlative Microscopy and Tomography (CoMiTo) – adapted from 1st phase	
Contact: Prof. Dr. Christian Motz, Saarland University URL: https://www.uni-saarland.de/fakultaet-nt/comito.html Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI, TA- MDI	DFG subjects: 4.32-03

Material/Methodology: Tomography, in situ mechanical testing Related Use Cases: IUC07, IUC15, IUC20	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: Core Facility at Saarland University with staff / users.
PP14 Materials modeling across the scales (MatScale) – adapted from 1st phase	
Contact: Dr.-Ing. Sarath Menon, apl. Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Franz Roters Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI, TA-MDI	DFG subjects: 4.32-03, 4.32-04
Material/Methodology: computational MSE, material informatics, data-driven approaches Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC07, IUC10, IUC17	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 8 research units and 14 research groups
PP15 Working Group “Metadata in Nanoindentation and Micromechanics” (NanoData)	
Contact: Prof. Dr. Ruth Schwaiger, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Karsten Durst, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Wenwen Song, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Benoit Merle Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI	DFG subjects: 4.31-03, 4.31-04, 4.31-05
Material/Methodology: Nanoindentation raw data and analysis / Experiments Related Use Cases: IUC08, IUC10, IUC14, IUC15	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 4 scientific research groups contribute data, analysis input, implement/test
PP16 Profile Area Advanced Materials Engineering (AME) at RPTU (RPTU-AME)	
Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Tilmann Beck, Prof. Dr. Heike Leitte, Dr.-Ing. Marek Smaga URL: https://rptu.de/en/ame Topics: TA-WLE	DFG subjects: 4.11, 4.12, 4.21, 4.22, 4.31, 4.41, 4.32, 4.43
Material/Methodology: metals, polymers, composites / analysis of mechanical and physical properties as well as microstructure / interactive data exploration analysis Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC08, IUC10, IUC12, IUC14	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 20 Professors with their working groups involved in AME
PP17 Leibniz-Institut für Werkstofforientierte Technologien (IWT)	
Contact: Dr.-Ing. Matthias Steinbacher URL: https://www.iwt-bremen.de/	DFG subjects: 4.21-01, 4.31-01, 4.32-03

Topics: TA-SAI; TA-WLE	
Material/Methodology: highly stressed metallic structural materials/ material, process and production engineering Related Use Cases: IUC07, IUC10, IUC11	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 4 departments, 6 groups in Dept. MSE

PP18 Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)

Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Birgit Skrotzki URL: https://www.bam.de/ Topics: TA-CI, TA-MDI, TA-WLE, TA-SAI	DFG subjects: 4.31-01, 4.31-04, 4.32-03
Material/Methodology: Metal alloys / Mechanical testing Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC14, IUC15	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 6 Divisions

PP19 Physikalisch-Technische-Bundesanstalt (PTB) – dropped out, contact stays active for metadata schemas and physics related ontologies

PP20 Mat-o-Lab – Materials open laboratory

Contact: Dr. Philipp von Hartrott, Dr. Simon Stier URL: https://mat-o-lab.github.io/OrgSite/ Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI, TA-MDI	DFG subjects: 4.31, 4.32
Material/Methodology: Use Cases for different materials classes Related Use Cases: IUC10, IUC11, IUC12, IUC13, IUC14	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: Fraunhofer Materials & BAM Team

PP21 FAIR Grain Boundaries (FAIR-GB)

Contact: PD Dr. Thomas Hammerschmidt, PD Dr. Rebecca Janisch Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI, TA-MDI	DFG subjects: 4.31-04, 4.32-03
Material/Methodology: grain boundaries data, high-resolution exp. and atomistic simulations Related Use Cases: IUC04, IUC07, IUC09, IUC10, IUC12, IUC17	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 7 research groups, DFG project 535248809

PP22 Coord. project SPP-2451 (Engineered Living Materials with Adaptive Functions)

Contact: Dr. Christian Müller, Prof. Dr. Aránzazu del Campo Bécares URL: https://spp2451.de Topics: TA-SAI, TA-WLE	DFG subjects: 21, 23, 31, 43
Material/Methodology: Engineered Living Materials with Adaptive Functions Related Use Cases: IUC08, IUC12, IUC14	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 33 groups 16 individual projects
PP23 *new* Multiscale analysis and inverse design of uncertain meso-structures (Meso-AID)	
Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Felix Fritzen URL: https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/530808823 Topics: TA-WLE	DFG subjects: 4.12-02
Material/Methodology: elastoviscoplastic composites; microstructure design Related Use Cases: IUC18	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 3 FTE scientists (3 institutions; 3 PIs) + surrounding groups Meso-AID
PP24 *new* Hereon – AI-based data collection and optimisation of additive manufacturing process parameters for titanium-based materials	
Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Florian Pyczak URL: https://www.helmholtz.de/ Topics: TA-MDI, TA-SAI	DFG subjects: 4.31-02, 4.31-04
Material/Methodology: Titanium alloys / Data Mining, Additive Manufacturing Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC18	
Contributions: [REDACTED]	Engagement: >2 groups
PP25 *new* DaMic – Data-driven alloy and microstructure design of sustainable structural metals (SPP 2489)	
Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Markus Kästner URL: https://tu-dresden.de/ing/forschung/dfg-schwerpunktprogramme/spp-2489/ Topics: TA-MDI, TA-SAI, TA-WLE	DFG subjects: 4.31, 4.32, 4.12
Material/Methodology: recyclability and sustainability of aluminum and steel alloys; data-driven methods for inverse materials design enabled digital Process-Structure-Property linkages; high-throughput methods capturing microstructure evolution for property prediction. Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC10, IUC15, IUC17, IUC18	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 9 subprojects à 2 doctoral students

PP26 *new* CRC1625 Atomic-scale understanding and design of multifunctional compositionally complex solid solution surfaces	
Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Markus Stricker, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Alfred Ludwig URL: https://www.ruhr-uni-bochum.de/crc1625/ Topics: TA-MDI, TA-SAI, TA-WLE	DFG subjects: 4.32, 3.12-01, 3.12-02, 4.43-04
Material/Methodology: Compositionally complex solid solutions for electrocatalysis Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC04, IUC08, IUC12, IUC14, IUC17, IUC20	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 19 projects in 5 institutions
PP27 *new* O(A)pportunities for your Publications (FID (Fachinformationsdienst (Specialised Information Service)) Materials Science)	
Contact: Katrin Stump (SLUB); Dr. Irina Sens (TIB) URL: https://www.materials-science.info ; https://www.slub-dresden.de/ ; https://www.tib.eu Topics: TA-CI	DFG subjects: 4.31, 4.32
Material/Methodology: Teaching material, publication information Related Use Cases: IUC01	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 2 partners (SLUB/TIB), other partners
PP28 *new* FOR 5657 BioAntiFatigue	
Contact: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Claudia Fleck URL: website in preparation Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI, TA-MDI	DFG subjects: 4.31-04, 4.32-02
Material/Methodology: fatigue testing and structural characterization of hierarchical nanocomposites Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC15, IUC08	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: Groups from 7 different institutes (national and international)
PP29 *new* Applying Interoperable Metadata Standards – Phase II (AIMS-2)	
Contact: Dr.-Ing. Patrick Ziemke URL: https://aims.pages.rwth-aachen.de Topics: TA-SAI, TA-MDI	DFG subjects: 4.43-07, 4.12-02, 4.32-04, 4.31-04
Material/Methodology: Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Large Scale Computations, Architected Materials, Materials for Extreme Environment Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC04, IUC08, IUC18	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 6 groups

PP30 DGM Expert Committee on hydrogen effects in engineering materials	
Contact person: Dr.-Ing. Florian Schäfer URL: https://dgm.de/ Topics: TA-WLE, TA-SAI	DFG subjects: 4.12-02, 4.31-04, 3.14-01
Material/Methodology: Round Robin test hydrogen effects on metallic materials, experimental data on hydrogen charging, thermal desorption analysis and hollow specimen testing Related Use Cases: IU05, IUC10, IUC19	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: > 3 scientific research groups data and analysis input, and implement / test
PP31 Plattform MaterialDigital (PMD)	
Contact person: Prof. Peter Gumbsch, Dr. Tilmann Hickel URL: http://material-digital.de https://dgm.de/en/network/expert-joint-committees/hydrogen-effects-in-engineering-materials Topics: TA-CI, TA-SAI, TA-WLE, TA-MDI	DFG subjects: 4.11, 4.12, 4.21, 4.22, 4.31, 4.41, 4.32, 4.43
Material/Methodology: PMD: community interaction, workflows, semantic interoperability, and industrial use cases; several subgroups (e.g., Ontology Playground), open to community; large number of associated projects, spectrum of MSE problems and digital solutions. Related Use Cases: IUC02, IUC10, IUC11, IUC12, IUC13, IUC17	
Contributions: [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED]	Engagement: 6 institutions PMD, 25 associated projects with industry contribution

3.2 The consortium within the NFDI and the national academic research system

3.2.1 Our connections to other NFDI consortia

NFDI-MatWerk continues to play a vital role in the overall development of the NFDI by contributing to the governance of the NFDI association, actively participating in various sections and task forces and by the integration with Base4NFDI with the aim to establish oneNFDI. The goal of our activities is to ensure interoperability with other disciplines and benefiting from already existing or jointly developed solutions within the NFDI and other national projects and stakeholders, fostering close contact and exchange. Therefore, NFDI-MatWerk contributes to the building of the NFDI as a whole and is collaborating closely with other (related) NFDI-consortia (see NFDI collaborative work table [33]). In the following, we list examples of our collaborations, which continuously increase in number and intensity:

(1) **IUCs devoted to the interaction with other NFDI consortia.** In **IUC09**, we brought two different perspectives on the same class of experiments into the same software environment (CONDA-Forge [34], Jupyter notebooks), fostering materials-scientific synergies between solid state physics (**FAIRmat**) and engineering science (NFDI-MatWerk). In **IUC07**, FAIRmat and MatWerk are working together on a standardized representation of microstructures. The **IUC10**,

a joint use case with **NFDI4Ing** focuses on the exchange of workflows developed in the respective other consortium, by use of KadiStudio, enabling the chance for a multiscale connection from materials properties to device performance. The workflows are described by the Python Workflow Definition [35,36] and generalized to experimental workflows by Steffen Brinckmann (FZ Jülich). **IUC15** (formerly **IUC05**) is working with **NFDI4Energy** (National Research Data Infrastructure for Interdisciplinary Energy System Research) [37]) on joining workflows in creating synthetic datasets based on protected datasets. We deploy the tools for collection of experimental data from **NFDI4Chem** in the same IUC and support the development of improvements for a wider range of experimental instruments. Additionally, **joint IUCs are planned**, including one together with **NFDI4Cat**, which focuses on catalysis.

(2) **Transdisciplinary workshops and seminar series.** NFDI-MatWerk is part of the collaboration “Physical Sciences in NFDI”[38], which includes **NFDI4Chem**, **FAIRmat**, **DAPHNE4NFDI**, **MaRDI**, NFDI-MatWerk, **NFDI4Cat**, and **PUNCH4NFDI**. Within this group, a series of (web-)seminars on FAIR data have been jointly organized. Furthermore, there are monthly strategic discussions between co-spokespersons of FAIRmat and NFDI-MatWerk. Together with **KonsortSWD** [39], **NFDI4Chem**, **NFDI4Earth** [40], we are organizing a workshop series with scientists and scientific publishers, focusing on tools, common solutions and requirements for the foreseeable increasing use of LLMs for publishing.

(3) **Collaborative Use Cases.** The emerging FAIR research data infrastructure enables interdisciplinary research in a completely new quality. For now, these Use Cases help to identify novel interdisciplinary research cases. E.g. NFDI-MatWerk, **NFDI4Ing**, **NFDI4Chem**, **MaRDI** developed collaborative use cases (presented at CoRDI 2025 [41]), with NFDI-MatWerk being strongly involved in discussions on 'Circular Economy in the Automotive Industry.' With **MaRDI** and **NFDI4Culture**, NFDI-MatWerk is developing a Use Case where materials data are used to classify cultural heritage in an unprecedented depth. With **DAPHNE4NFDI** we will implement workflows and semantic interfaces for photon and neutron based material analytics via CRC1261.

(4) **Collaboration within institutions.** Through the MPI SusMat, the consortium NFDI-MatWerk is involved in a network MPG-NFDI, connecting activities in a large number of NFDI consortia. In this context, for example, an interaction with NFDI4Biolmaging on the usage of OMERO (Open Microscopy Environment (OME) [42]) and OpenBIS has been agreed upon. Meta data and semantics developed in NFDI-MatWerk are used in Helmholtz data initiatives, which connect to other NFDI consortia. The same is true for Fraunhofer. Many universities have established internal NFDI meetings to connect the solutions provided by the consortia.

(5) Beyond that, there are interactions with other NFDI consortia, ranging from **joint services** with **NFDI4Ing** (e.g. the Data Collections Explorer [43]), or the reuse of the NFDIcore Ontology [44] by **NFDI4Culture** and **NFDI4DataScience**, through mutual conference participations and local consortia networking events, to common interest groups like the Helmholtz Electron

Microscopy Glossary Initiative (collaboration with **FAIRmat**), and the JL-MDMC-NEP (Joint Lab “Integrated Model and Data Driven Materials Characterization” NFFA (Nanoscience Foundries and Fine Analysis project)-Europe Pilot) Metadata Working Group (together with **NFDI4Ing** and **NFDI4Chem**). Another overlap with **FAIRmat** is that pyiron is available in NOMAD (Novel Materials Discovery project) [45] North (remote tools hub), and NOMAD can simultaneously be addressed as one of the databases of materials science within pyiron.

(6) Last but not least, another level of collaboration is personal connection through our spokesperson, Chris Eberl, who is a member of the official advisory board of **MaRDI**.

Next phase plans for collaboration and their benefit. As described, many connections have already been established and continuously lead to a more effective use of resources as infrastructure services can be reused by other disciplines, workflow and software developments can be accelerated together and semantic development can be matched early on (e.g. NFDI core ontology) so that interoperability is enabled in the infrastructure foundation of oneNFDI. Therefore, we will continue to collaborate within NFDI to reduce the transformational costs.

3.2.2 Our connection to NFDI sections and Base4NFDI with its basic services

Some of the cross-cutting topics we have foreseen in Sec. 5.2.6 of our proposal [46] have been transferred to the NFDI sections or Base4NFDI. One example is the Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI), taken up by the project IAM4NFDI (Identity and Access Management for the NFDI) of Base4NFDI, where Marius Politze (RWTH) is co-speaker [47]. Furthermore, Metadata services and (standardized) formats are actively pursued by many consortia: e.g. in the NFDI-Section Metadata, Terminology and Provenance to which NFDI-MatWerk prominently contributes (see below). The storage of research data in a scalable manner and in a data transfer federation is addressed in close collaboration with NFDI4Ing, where mutual infrastructure partners are participating. On the other hand, some topics have particularly moved into our focus since the start of NFDI-MatWerk, e.g.: (i) the development of an NFDI-MatWerk and a global NFDI architecture (see 2.4). (ii) the seamless integration of the FAIR-DO concept. This will also support the findability, sharing and reusability of data and computing resources. (iii) a consortia-overarching ontology, including relevant tools and services. (iv) “The ELN Consortium” [48] together with NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Chem and other international research data experts. It aims at improving the data exchange and interoperability between the different ELNs, where we, for example, actively contribute to the standardization of a common ELN File Format. NFDI-MatWerk is represented in NFDI sections and task forces and is contributing to Base4NFDI at different levels: the consortium was instrumental in founding the Section Industry Engagement, where Christoph Eberl (IWM) served as deputy speaker until May 2025 and was involved in the Industrial Advisory Board (Industriebeirat). Marius Politze (RWTH) is chair of the WG (Working Group) IAM (Identity and Access Management) and the WG Overall Architecture in the Section Common Infrastructure. The Concept Document of the Section Metadata, Terminology and

Provenance was co-authored by former member of NFDI-MatWerk [REDACTED] (KIT). Members of NFDI-MatWerk are contributing to various section-WGs (e.g. Multi Cloud, Research Software, Ontology Harmonization) and NFDI Task Forces (e.g. Evaluation and Reporting, User Research, Governance & Sustainability, Metadata). In Base4NFDI, Achim Streit (KIT) and Erwin Laure (MPCDF) are part of the TEC (Technical Expert Committee). Furthermore, we are participating in four (IAM4NFDI, TS4NFDI (Terminology Services 4 NFDI) [49], KGI4NFDI (Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for NFDI project) [50], PID4NFDI (Persistent Identifier Services for the German National Research Data Infrastructure) [51]) of the currently running Base4NFDI projects: For example, the RWTH Aachen is providing a co-speaker and is hosting institution for a Service Steward for IAM4NFDI; Volker Hofmann (FZJ) is representing NFDI-MatWerk as affiliated participant of KGI4NFDI. In the following, we will detail out our commitment to Base4NFDI.

Base4NFDI – a path to OneNFDI

We, as NFDI-MatWerk, recognize the importance of collaboration with Base4NFDI as an essential building block on the path to OneNFDI. We support and where relevant for our consortium engage with and use the emerging Base4NFDI services. The focus here is particularly on the Base4NFDI objective of harnessing the potential of existing networks to create common services that support RDM in the research field of MSE and on universal access to common services as a complementary activity to the development of our own discipline-relevant tools and services (see 4.4 Services provided by the consortium). The established basic services assure interoperability with existing solutions both within other NFDI consortia as well as with European Open Science frameworks, such as the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud). Base4NFDI ensures that services are openly available, openly governed, and avoid lock-in with commercial vendors.

NFDI-MatWerk has actively participated in the Base4NFDI workshops held in April 2024 and March 2025 to identify and agree on viable contributions of the consortia for a successful integration of Base4NFDI services. During the Initialisation Phase, NFDI-MatWerk actively contributed to IAM4NFDI in form of attending meetings and helping with requirements collection. NFDI-MatWerk member M. Politze (RWTH) is now a Principal Investigator at IAM. We contributed to DMP4NFDI as well, in the form of a Letter of Support. Furthermore, we support the proposals for the new Base4NFDI services DALIA4NFDI (Teaching Materials) and Support4RDM (Helpdesks).

During the Base4NFDI service integration, **NFDI-MatWerk focusses allocated efforts to align with and integrate services**. NFDI-MatWerk actively engaged with and/or has plans regarding e.g the following services:

1. IAM4NFDI: We have already integrated the NFDI AAI as an identity provider for Coscine [52]. It allows users to login with their existing NFDI identities. The same is planned for our workflow

node store. Chaldene, a visual programming language of the DFKI, will be part of the next incubator phase (August 2025).

2. PID4NFDI: PID4NFDI will be examined in depth and adapted. The PID Coordination Hub serves as a centralized infrastructure for managing PIDs (persistent identifiers) of NFDI. NFDI-MatWerk has already joined a focus group on DMPs (Data Management Plans), Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs), and developing use-cases for emerging PIDs.

3. TS4NFDI: Terminology Services 4 NFDI (TS4NFDI) is a service for provision, curation, development, harmonization, and mapping of terminologies. The team behind the MatWerk service Coscine is in contact with Roman Baum from TS4NFDI and planning an integration soon.

4. KGI4NFDI: KGI4NFDI advocates for a central KGI (Knowledge Graph Infrastructure) to enhance interoperability. We are monitoring technology readiness and plan to align with KGI and plan e.g to establish a connection to Cosine. A joint screening of the KGs across NFDI resulted in a joint paper for CoRDI in which TA-SAI participated with Heike Fliegel (FIZ).

5. Jupyter4NFDI: The Jupyter4NFDI [53] service aggregates Jupyter based data analysis and post-processing platforms currently employed by NFDI consortia. T. Hickel and J. Janssen are in contact with Klaus Reuter from Jupyter4NFDI to integrate the pyiron workflow environment.

The topic of the integration of basic services was also addressed in our core working group "Architecture": By strategically integrating suitable services into our architecture, we are addressing the implementation in a targeted and sustainable manner. In concrete terms, we dedicate person months to actively integrate Base4NFDI services during their Integration Phase. we will earmark effort in the NFDI-MatWerk architecture group to do the following: (1) In close cooperation with the service team, carry out a technical analysis to switch from existing solutions to Base4NFDI services. This will be decided on a case-by-case basis and the criteria will include: identifying which consortia members are involved in Base4NFDI services, sustainability of the current service vs. the Base4NFDI service, and alignment with existing consortia technical workflows. (2) Participation in future Base4NFDI service incubator calls and pilots to demonstrate feasibility of adoption during the Integration Phase. (3) Specific efforts will be focused on engagement in the NFDI Sections: regular meetings in our TAs to identify cross-cutting needs of consortia for its data sharing requirements.

We, as NFDI-MatWerk, reserve time resources to support structured ongoing communication with Base4NFDI. We will closely monitor and connect to activities in Base4NFDI and will provide a dedicated communication channel to Base4NFDI technical and community updates. Reciprocal activities to assign one contact person familiar with cross-cutting topics in our consortium who will be dedicated to work closely with the Base4NFDI Service Stewards and keep the channels of communication updated. We will reserve efforts to attend community workshops, calls and training activities for each basic service.

Need for improvement regarding both cross-cutting topics and basic services: While Base4NFDI implemented major improvements in information distribution, this is still difficult concerning the sections of NFDI. Here, a more coordinated management, a common information platform and clearing out inactive work groups would help with transparency and make contributions more seamless.

Participated in and contributed to the governance structure of the NFDI: We contribute to the governance of the NFDI since C. Eberl (IWM) is representing all consortia in his role as one of the three elected chairs of the “NFDI Consortia Assembly” (2024-2026). The chairs are in continuous exchange with the DFG, the German Council of Science and Humanities (German: Wissenschaftsrat, WR) and the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (German: BMFTR (Bundesministerium für Forschung, Technologie und Raumfahrt)) [54] to improve the political support of the NFDI. They represented all NFDI consortia in the “Strukturevaluation” [3] conducted by the German Sciences and Humanities Council. Furthermore, the chairs of the Consortia Assembly are also responsible for the communication with the NFDI Senate and for the strategy development of the NFDI. Concrete examples of the work for the NFDI strategy development include the participation in the committee workshop (German: Workshop des Ausschusses), in the DFG expert discussion (German: DFG-Fachgespräch), and at the call for data storage systems, which has been approved by the DFG and is currently open for applications from institutions (keyword 'NFDI-Speicher 2025') [55].

3.2.3 Our connection to other national stakeholder in RDM infrastructure

We, as NFDI-MatWerk contribute to **knowledge transfer within and beyond NFDI with national projects and stakeholders in the field of RDM:** (1) DKZ.2R (Datenkompetenzzentrum (English: Data Literacy Centre).2R) [56]: The Rhine-Ruhr Center for Scientific Data Literacy (DKZ.2R) is one of the eleven Data Literacy Centers in Germany, that were founded in 2023. The project leads S. Sandfeld (FZ Jülich) and M. Müller (RWTH) are both Co-Spokespersons in NFDI-MatWerk, plus the DKZ.2R PI A. Hartmaier is Co-spokesperson in MatWerk, too. NFDI-MatWerk und DKZ.2R conduct shared workshops on Data Literacy, if possible, which are based on the Carpentries concept, for example, as part of the Spring School 2025 in Aachen organized by NFDI-MatWerk. Additionally, there is a mutual exchange on the application of ML and AI. (2) In the context of MaterialDigital, we emphasize the importance of aligning our efforts with their existing frameworks to enhance knowledge transfer and collaborative research efforts. Specifically, we are focusing on the alignment of MWO (MatWerk Ontology) [57], a modular extension of the NFDIcore ontology, with PMDCo 3.0, particularly in relation to BFO (Basic Formal Ontology) [58]. We aim to create a cohesive framework rather than developing competing ontological concepts. Since we already have experience with the use of ELNs in NFDI-MatWerk, an exchange of valuable insights will take place here. MaterialDigital will utilize these insights.

Our workflow solutions developed in pyiron and the Python Workflow Definition [35] are designed with versatility in mind. They are compatible with both NFDI-MatWerk and MaterialDigital initiatives. The Plattform MaterialDigital will be established as PP31 to directly contribute to NFDI-MatWerk. Additionally, MaterialDigital projects, especially those involving significant contributions from industry partners, can become PPs. (3) The FDO (FAIR Digital Object) concept and its associated tools, conceptualized by the RDA (Research Data Alliance) [59] and the FAIR Digital Objects Forum, implemented within the HMC (Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration) [60] is being adopted and customized to enable machine-actionable decisions that facilitate automation processes within NFDI-MatWerk. They provide a structured approach for gathering all necessary information required for experiments. This capability allows distributed data resources to be connected and related, regardless of their storage locations. An additional effort involves aligning efforts between the MSE KG (Knowledge Graph) and the Helmholtz KG to ensure that our approaches are interoperable. NFDI-MatWerk is committed to the implementation of discipline-specific services and applications. We actively contribute to the EM Glossary, an HMC initiative that standardizes terminology in electron microscopy. Furthermore, we recognize the importance of closely aligning training material to support researchers in navigating these complex frameworks.

3.3 International networking

NFDI-MatWerk is well embedded in the international MSE community (e.g. USA, Japan, China, Korea) and in international research data initiatives. Hence, it is ensured that our activities will not be insular but tightly integrated in these networks. To ensure harmonization, NFDI-MatWerk appointed an international scientific (see 3.4.1) [61] .

Scientists of NFDI-MatWerk are strongly involved in the Research Data Alliance (RDA) [59], a worldwide community-driven initiative with the mission of building the social and technical environment to openly share data across technologies, disciplines, and countries. As part of the governance bodies, R. Aversa (KIT) is elected member of the Technical Advisory Board. Several members of the NFDI-MatWerk consortium contribute to several working and interest groups, e.g. the IG on FAIR-DOs [62], the WG on sample type classification [63], a WG on harmonized terminologies[64] and on national data services [65]. Furthermore, members of NFDI-MatWerk are actively involved in the MaRDA (Materials Research Data Alliance) [66], a community-led network for advancing data driven materials discovery and open, accessible and interoperable materials data. MaRDA council member Catherine Brinson is a member of the International Advisory Board of NFDI-MatWerk. The International Data Space Association [67] network defined a reference architecture for creating and operating virtual data spaces. Collaborations are initiated through the Fraunhofer society.

Cooperation with the EOSC [68] is established via KIT (A. Streit). NFDI-MatWerk members (e.g., R. Aversa (KIT)) actively participate in the newly launched NFFA-Europe PILOT [69] project. that focuses on providing a platform for multidisciplinary research at the nanoscale. We will support the establishment of the National Node within NFDI by providing MSE-specific services and contributing our tools, services, and expertise to its development. NFDI-MatWerk member institutions like Fraunhofer IWM or KIT (e.g., P. Gumbsch) are also involved in the European Advanced Materials Initiative 2030 [70], which has the vision of being a multi-sectoral accelerator regarding safe and sustainable advanced materials towards a circular economy.

R. Aversa (KIT) is member of the Steering Committee of the FAIR Digital Object Forum [71] and assures that relevant results are transferred to NFDI-MatWerk. The European Materials Characterization Council [72] is an initiative on the experimental materials characterization side. Furthermore, NFDI-MatWerk institutions IWM and BAM were involved in foundation of the EMMC (European Materials Modelling Council) [73] and have ongoing collaborations through EU projects with the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology initiative [74] that is linked to EMMC. Founding members Gerhard Goldbeck and Emanuele Ghedini are in the International Advisory Board of the NFDI-MatWerk. In addition to networking with European initiatives, members of NFDI-MatWerk have ongoing collaborations and interactions with the U.S. National Institute of Standard and Technologies [75] and the Japanese National Institute for Materials Science [76]. The German Materials Society [77], e.g. represented by B. Skrotzki (BAM) and F. Mücklich (Uni Saarland) established a collaboration with the American Society of Materials [78]. NFDI-MatWerk members are also involved in Materials Research Society (MRS) and The Minerals Metals & Materials Society (TMS) [79], have contacts to the Swiss EMPA (Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology) [80] and to many other societies.

In addition, members of NFDI-MatWerk actively reach out to the international materials science communities by organizing international conferences, workshops and symposia at topic related events such as the Material Science and Engineering bi-annual conference [25], the bi-annual FEMS (Federation of European Materials Societies EuroMat) [81] conference series or the Multiscale Materials Modelling conference [82], the spring meetings of the German Physical Society and its Division of Metal and Materials Physics [83], and International Workshop on SeMatS (Semantic Materials Science) [84]. T. Hickel (MPI SusMat/BAM) and J. Neugebauer (MPI SusMat) organized the international conference on ADIS (Ab-initio Description of Iron and Steel) 2023 [85] with a focus on digitalization and workflows.

We will make efforts to keep abreast of NFDI activities and Base4NFDI in alignment with the new EOSC EU Node services and the German EOSC Candidate Node activities. Our consortium will consider being a contributor of our tools and services to the EOSC NFDI National Node. We will keep aware of updates in the OSCARS project open calls to ensure our activities are complementary and participate in RDA Working Groups or Interest groups relevant to MSE.

3.4 Organisational structure and viability

3.4.1 Organisational and governance structure of the consortium

NFDI-MatWerk's central decision body is the **Lenkungskreis** ("Executive Board"), composed of (co-) spokespersons, participating individuals plus other relevant key staff from TAs (e.g. with coordinative functions). The Lenkungskreis meets bi-weekly online for TA-specific strategies and inter-TA decisions and two to three times a year in person at the in-person meetings AHoD (All-hands-on-deck meeting) in spring, the NFDI-MatWerk Conference in summer (every second year, other year online), and the Strategy Meeting in fall. The Lenkungskreis reflects the consortium's composition in different TAs, thus providing a TA perspective.

In turn, the **Steuerungsgruppe** ("Steering Committee") is composed of (co)-spokespersons (one vote per (co-)applicant institution) and participants with funding as observers (no voting rights). The Steuerungsgruppe meets quarterly. The Steuerungsgruppe takes an institutional view, considering the contributions of the single institution. It votes upon changes in TA Work Packages and distribution of funding. The Steuerungsgruppe is responsible for overall strategy and prioritization of IUCs in the annual Strategy Meeting.

In addition, an **(International) Advisory Board** with national and international representatives from academia and industry is invited twice a year or as needed to advise the Lenkungskreis on the overall NFDI-MatWerk strategy (see 3.3). Board members provide advice, critically review progress, establish new connections, and contribute improvements from their perspectives. They provide a technical review of the NFDI-MatWerk strategy and architecture in the areas of workflows, ontology, and infrastructure (see [61]).

The **NFDI-MatWerk Office** consists of TA Strategy Development (TA-SD) as Permanent Office, in close collaboration with TA Community Interaction (TA-CI). The NFDI-MatWerk Office serves as main contact for the MSE community (e.g. new PPs), the NFDI network, and international partners (e.g. Advisory Board). Within each TA, staff with coordinative function support TA Speakers (co-spokespersons) in strategy alignment and inter-TA collaboration.

In addition to the described governance structure so far, **flexible topic-specific working groups** are set up ad-hoc for collaboration between TAs and/or IUCs as needed. So far, this includes a roll-out group (TA-CI and TA-SD with data stewards from TA-MDI) and a central architecture group (TA-MDI with TA-WLE, TA-SAI and TA-CI). Similarly, a knowledge graph implementation group (all TAs and selected IUCs) will be set up in the second funding phase.

Decision-making in NFDI-MatWerk follows a one-year strategy cycle (grey circle in Figure 3). Strategic decisions are based on input gathered via PPs, workshops and at the annual NFDI-MatWerk conference in summer as well as from NFDI and the larger scientific community. The input is structured into IUCs (see list of IUCs at the end of this section) for the annual Strategy Meeting (autumn). Decisions on the prioritization of IUCs and the formulation of new IUCs (if needed) consider both the developer perspective (development time and cost) and MSE

community (needs and priority). TAs adjust measures and work packages according to selected and prioritized IUCs. Status updates of the IUC related work packages are regularly given to the Steuerungsgruppe, presented quarterly to the PPs and at the AHoD meeting (spring).

The main **development process** in NFDI-MatWerk takes place in the IUCs. Teams for each prioritized IUC develop a solution target (product goal, long-term goals of the IUC), specific sprint-goals (short-term goal until the next in-person consortium event), user stories, backlogs, and a DoD (Definitions of Done). Interdisciplinary IUC teams operate on agile management with three-month sprint cycles between the three annual in-person meetings (blue circles in Figure 3). Each development cycle starts with a sprint planning and ends with a review and team retro. The achievement of product and sprint goal is then reviewed at the in-person meetings. Key stakeholders for IUC teams are appointed researchers representing PPs (acting in the role of Product Owners) and the central roll-out group (as described above).

Figure 3: The timelines for strategy development, decision making, and community interaction follow a yearly cycle, while technological development is on 3-month cycles.

NFDI-MatWerk aims to **increase links to MSE projects and institutions** for broader representation. For integration as PP (3.1, 3.1.5), specific criteria and a dedicated process is described on the website [86]. New members are admitted by voting in a Lenkungskreis meeting. PPs actively contribute and benefit from TA experts in our IUCs and can receive funding via FlexFunds. As a low-threshold alternative, individual MSE researchers and smaller research groups will have the possibility to become NFDI-MatWerk Community Members. The membership offers benefits for MSE researchers and NFDI-MatWerk members alike (see 3.1).

Modification of the implemented governance structure: A core characteristic of NFDI-MatWerk’s structure is its decentralized and distributed nature, even within the co-applicant

institutions. This is also reflected in the distribution of resources across various institutions with different infrastructure and MSE-specific competences (see 3.1). The network-structure easily allows for a fast adaptation of the IUC teams and integration of new PPs. The organizational structure and governance process follows mainly the way it was laid out in the original proposal. In addition, the aforementioned (International) Advisory Board was set up in the first funding period [61]. Furthermore, based on experiences with agile management of IUC teams in the first funding period, the structure of development cycles within the IUCs was specified in more detail in this proposal.

3.4.2 Funding and consolidation strategy

Deviations in spending of funds: The funds of the original proposal were cut by 30% (all second and third round proposals were affected). This made it necessary to cut all travel funding, all student helper funding, reduce the funding for PPs from 5 to 3 years and reduce the total number FTE. Consequently, several work packages were reduced, postponed or shifted into a second phase proposal. This change in work program was reported in 2021 to the DFG. Besides this initial change to our work program, we have been very successful in delivering our promised services to the MSE community.

Within the consortium we have also transferred funding as well as responsibilities for work packages, mainly due to co-spokespersons changing their institutions. [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] Due to delays in recruiting, funds of various institutions had to be transferred to the respective next year. All in all, funds were so far spent as planned in the proposal. Nevertheless, the necessary own contributions from consortium and participating institutions were heavily underestimated. Especially the strong increase in personell costs (about 20% between 2021 to 2025) reduced the funded FTEs. Altogether, the institutions contributed way more due to the high interest in the topic of NFDI.

Service Consolidation Strategy: Several measures have been implemented, but the globally most effective one is the standardization NFDI-MatWerk has started in the areas of services, workflows and semantics across the whole MSE community. This enables thousands of researchers to benefit from others' efforts but also allows them to contribute. While we are still at the beginning, the money spent in NFDI-MatWerk reduces efforts in many institutions and labs. To consolidate services and maintenance further, NFDI-MatWerk involves major infrastructure providers (FIZ, FZJ, DFKI, IT centres) for sustainable provision of services. NFDI-MatWerk also

continuously integrates existing services to limit development of new ones, e.g. by using institutional initiatives (e.g. Coscine) or other NFDI consortia (e.g. integrate NOMAD, Omero, openBIS, contribute pyiron, semantics). A cross-TA architecture group continuously consolidates the overall NFDI-MatWerk service portfolio from an infrastructural viewpoint (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**), including the integration of Base4NFDI services (see 3.2.2). On the other hand, different services are consolidated in IUC workflows from a MSE researcher view. Continuous stakeholder feedback and quantitative monitoring ensure the relevance of the developed services.

3.4.3 Demand-oriented development

IUCs are central to the demand-driven NFDI-MatWerk developments, supported by all other entities. Input for IUCs is gathered continuously at the NFDI-MatWerk Conference (summer, online and on-site alternating) and throughout the year (e.g. when admitting new PPs), such that the working focus of the consortium is up to date with community needs. The TAs analyze IUC proposals for (technical) feasibility and resource demand. Finally, the Steuerungsgruppe prioritizes IUCs in the strategy meeting and identifies a Product Owner from the involved PPs to represent the PPs. The IUC teams are continuously challenged by their Product Owners. In these IUC teams, NFDI-MatWerk developers work together with developers from the PPs to solve infrastructure challenge introduced by the PPs. Depending on community demand, PPs can apply for FlexFunds to intensify activities in a specific IUC (see 3.1). Using agile methods in IUC teams furthermore ensures user-centric development process and responsiveness to community feedback, supported by the central roll-out group. Based on the work in the IUCs, the TAs have to identify gaps in knowledge or services and strategically identify actions to close them. This can be either by integrating existing services from institutions or other consortia (or in the worst case develop a new service). The resulting services, workflows and semantics are then added into the solution portfolio (including an estimated TRL) and the Roll-Out group develops a path for the integration into the existing infrastructure. The feedback gained from the roll-out process is then used to identify missing feature and prioritize developer time and the development circle starts again.

3.4.4 Sustainable use of Human Resources

To achieve demand-driven development and consolidation of our services, attracting personnel with specific skills is crucial for NFDI-MatWerk's success. Recruiting and human resource development is handled within each institution, competence development also within NFDI-MatWerk. Regular retrospectives in the development cycle, constructive feedback and re-prioritization of IUCs ensure efficient use of staff time based on community needs. As experienced in the first funding phase, a diversity of roles and responsibilities is crucial to develop a sustainable organisation (coordinators, data stewards, developers, etc.). Furthermore, continuous training of staff maintains capacities and engagement. An open and constructive feedback routine within the

consortium promotes a positive error culture. Furthermore, a respectful and appreciative interaction with one another is important to us. Transparency (Gitlab repositories are collaboratively used across all institutions and teams) and participation of all members, e.g. in the strategy process and the different groups (architecture, roll-out, ...) help to integrate different ideas and voices.

3.5 Operating model

Rather than just creating new tools, the focus of NFDI-MatWerk is on integrating existing ones (e.g., ELNs, data management services, software, semantics...) into coherent and seamless solutions supporting the researchers' scientific workflows and teach them how to create their own ones. Indeed, the majority of the services (see datasheet and [87]) are provided by the participating institutions and adapted by the consortium to solve MSE-specific RDM challenges in the framework of IUCs. In turn, the IUCs demonstrate that RDM solutions require an interplay of local infrastructures in the labs and centrally provided services, which are curated and centrally collected in the consortium online platform and in the MSE Knowledge Graph.

NFDI-MatWerk caters to interdisciplinary communities; therefore, the infrastructure solution needs to support a heterogeneous collection of services and tools. This is ensured by a distributed funding scheme to integrate different stakeholders. While this approach requires more cross-institutional and cross-community collaboration (e.g., ELN and MSE, see 0), it helps in terms of adoption and leads to a more sustainable infrastructure.

At the organizational level, NFDI-MatWerk leverages state initiatives such as bwFDM (Federal State Initiative for RDM in Baden-Württemberg) [88], HeFDI (Hessische Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (Hessian Research Data Infrastructures)) [89], and fdm.nrw (Landesinitiative für Forschungsdatenmanagement in Nordrhein-Westfalen) [90] to expand its network, reach underconnected institutions, and involve local RDM consultants, supporting roll-out efforts at the individual institutions. It also collaborates with initiatives like the HMC platform, the AIMS (Applying Interoperable Metadata Standards) project, and the MaterialDigital network to advance semantic interoperability in materials science.

We do not plan to demand fees as most services are operated by the participating institutions. These are primarily universities and non-university research institutions which, as described above, set up and operate the services with mixed funding. However, the current situation of "mixed financing" is not a suitable long-term solution for sustainably providing the services and infrastructure. Small fees are currently only charged for conferences and workshops organized by the DGM as part of TA-CI. Members of TA-SD actively participate in a discussion group across the NFDI regarding business models.

3.5.1 Data storage and computing power

NFDI-MatWerk is continuously working on concepts and services to ensure that the produced data adheres to the FAIR principles, and that the storage solutions are seamlessly connected to data and workflow services. In line with its federated design, open-access software is developed and hosted on public GitHub and GitLab repositories, while datasets are primarily stored on local servers at the institutions where they are generated, reflecting the current funding schemes; nevertheless, some central services remain essential for registering and sharing data, as well as for hosting the KG. As a result, participating institutions typically provide the necessary resources; where this is not feasible, central instances are offered by the consortium.

For example, central registration of FDOs requires generic infrastructure for minting persistent identifiers (PIDs), such as those provided by the Handle System or W3IDs. These services are complemented by the Data Type Registry, with current implementations relying on Handle PID services and the registry operated by GWDG (Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung). These systems are promoted and used in alignment with recommendations from PID4NFDI.

For on-demand storage capacity and metadata management, the RDM service Coscine [52] and its backend storage service DataStorage.nrw [91] are provided by RWTH Aachen by base funding and funding of the state Nord Rhine-Westphalia; a quota is granted based on a science led peer review that focusses on quality criteria established in NFDI-MatWerk for RDM and workflows. As an alternative, the NFDI-MatWerk Data and Metadata Repositories [92,93] are attached to the LSDF (Large Scale Data Facility) [94] provided by KIT and supported through institutional and state-level funding in Baden-Württemberg.

Computational needs are met through institutional and national computing centers, primarily via NHR (National High Performance Computing Alliance) [95] and MPCDF. NFDI-MatWerk collaborates with NHR, notably through joint workshops in the Simulation and Data Lab for Materials Design. Computing providers support local deployment of services on institutional resources, offering accessible workflows via platforms such as Jupyter and BinderHub [96].

A key interface between centralized services and local infrastructures are ELNs, which are typically maintained by individual research groups or institutions and integrated directly into laboratory workflows. NFDI-MatWerk adopts a technology-neutral stance but supports interoperability and community standards. Some widely used ELNs within the community are OpenBIS and eLabFTW [97], both of which offer flexible deployment options and support for structured metadata. Recently, the NOMAD platform has also seen increasing adoption as a solution bridging ELN functionality with advanced data analytics and sharing.

4 Research Data Management Strategy

4.1 Scientific relevance and quality of the measures

4.1.1 Quality of implemented measures

The consortium has progressed successfully on the implementation of measures outlined in the original proposal, despite the compromises required due to the 30% budget cut. NFDI-MatWerk comprises three technical TAs (WLE, MDI, SAI) and two TAs for communication and organization (CI, SD). The strong connection of TAs in NFDI-MatWerk to the PPs and the commitment to community-defined IUCs turned out to be a big advantage. On the one hand, this ensured a prioritization of those measures and IUCs that have a high relevance for the MSE community (e.g. during the AHoD meetings). On the other hand, the direct feedback of the PPs on services and demonstrators (in meetings and conferences, see 3.1) turned out to be our most valuable quality assessment. For the group of stakeholders from the broader MSE community that is not necessarily in direct interaction with NFDI-MatWerk, it is our task to raise awareness and to ensure dissemination in a roll-out process. Here, quality is measured in terms of access numbers and participants at events. For the renewal proposal, we have started to attract more researchers to join as PPs. We also plan to measure the relevance by KPIs proposed in the NFDI-1000 datasheet. In addition, the International Advisory Board of NFDI-MatWerk provides valuable feedback to quality of the measures. In the following, we report on the individual TAs:

The main aims of **TA Strategy Development (TA-SD)** involve the establishment of project governance structures, project management processes, as well as enabling user involvement in NFDI-MatWerk's developments. TA-SD successfully set up the proposed project **governance structures** including financial processes between the different organisations and the Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft (Erstempfänger). The "Steuerungsgruppe" (see 3.4) has been established including the necessary structured processes towards decision making (e.g. financial and WP changes). Further, the "Lenkungskreis" (see 3.4) for information exchange and operational decisions was successfully implemented (biweekly).

To ensure the **user- and goal-oriented collaboration** between TAs and PPs along the IUCs, processes and organizational structures have been successfully established following the proposal. (1) A **yearly strategy** process involving the MSE community strongly represented by the PPs has been established to continuously identify MSE user requirements and derive or revise IUCs representing the typical researchers' workflow. Furthermore, (2) **Product Owners** from PPs are identified as well as (3) **agile developer teams** from the TAs to work on the respective IUCs following our proposed infrastructure development process. As a deviation from the project proposal, we established (4) the working group **Roll-out Management** which is developing roll-out strategies and processes to support the developers. The continuous development also

requires a (5) **solution management system** connecting identified user needs and existing solutions by NFDI-MatWerk or other NFDIs and developers.

Due to the **initial budget cut** at the beginning of the project, it was necessary to cut 0,5 FTE in measure SD-2 “Cultural Change and Target group feedback analytics”. However, in 2023 a cross-consortia interest group called CC-BY-US (Cultural change in sharing research data with and through the NFDI) [98] was established, where TA-SD contributes in their joint workshops and publications. Also, the measure SD-3 “Incentive Mechanisms” needed to run with reduced resources, e.g. with a special issue and an online collection of a scientific journal where especially young researchers from NFDI-MatWerk and the MSE community can publish their developments with and in RDM. The measure SD-4 Project management was initially cut, but due to the demands of the project capacities were shifted from SD-5 to SD-4. The collaboration within the NFDI section ELSA (NFDI Section Ethical, Legal & Social Aspects) [99] made it possible to still work on SD-5 “Legal”. For example, the fact sheets on data protection in RDM published by Section ELSA cover key legal questions for the consortium that were originally foreseen in Measure SD-5 Legal [100–102].

The **TA Community Interaction (TA-CI)** has promoted data literacy, FAIR principles and the concept of NFDI in multiple ways among different stakeholders from student to expert level. Therefore, several events and workshops were organized, both for consortium work and for interacting with the MSE community (see 3.1.4). 49 community events have been conducted with altogether more than 5000 participants, as well as 29 educational events with 11,500 participants. With respect to outreach and community counselling, LinkedIn is used to post news and invitations. It currently has 577 followers and has received a total of 42,470 impressions. A website [103] was set up and hosted by DGM and has been accessed 25,000 times. It serves as a point of entry for MSE researchers, featuring event announcements, a helpdesk form and a solutions area, which is a collection of tools, links and other resources of relevance for NFDI and FAIR research. It contains both own and foreign developments. In the future, the solutions area will be remodelled and fed directly from the MSE KG, developed by TA-SAI.

Furthermore, NFDI-MatWerk members have been organizing symposia and workshops in our communities' conferences (MSE conference series, Spring meetings of German Physical Society) where a strong increase in submissions from the community can be observed, see Figure 4. Different other formats have been introduced to conduct more interactive teaching, e.g. in cooperation with EUSMAT (European School of Materials) at Saarland University [13] within the activities of IUC01 [104], two schools for PhD students and one school for international Master level students were held. A further school was held at TU Dresden, mainly organized by M. Zimmermann (IWS) focusing on RDM within collaborative research programs taking the DFG

Figure 4: RDM-related submissions from the Materials Science and Engineering Community to MSE Congress (total numbers)

experts presenting their respective ELN system based on one common dataset was held in 2022. Budget cuts made it necessary to shift the development of teaching material for technical staff (WP (Work Package) CI-2.2) into the next phase and cancel Measure CI-4, Psychology of Change Management, although the latter is still dealt with by TA Strategy Development.

The TA Semantics & Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI) (previously TA-OMS) achieved substantial progress during the first funding phase for the two main objectives: (1) generating a minimal description of material properties and making it accessible; (2) implementation of a global materials ontology as a central semantic alignment target, to enable interoperability across heterogeneous materials data. A key objective of the base ontology is to ease the implementation of more specific, application-level materials ontologies.

By publishing the MatWerk Ontology (MWO) v1.0.0 [105], v2.0.0 [106] and v3.0.0 [107] we supplied the community with a top-level semantic representation of the consortium, as well as a minimal representation to describe materials. MWO v.3.0.0 is aligned and ingests classes from multiple external established ontologies and vocabularies to increase outwards interoperability and connectivity. In particular, MWO has been aligned to BFO (basic formal ontology) as well as to the NFDICore ontology v.3.0.0 [108] paving the way for a smooth connection to other NFDI consortia or material science related initiatives like MaterialDgital, which is a key objective for the next phase. Moreover, the transition to the community-driven open-source ODK (ontology development kit) [109] has led to substantial enhancements in ontological interoperability and curation. This development signifies a paradigm shift from an empirical ontology development to a more systematic and engineered approach, thereby facilitating the harmonisation of various (MSE) ontologies. In addition, we have collected and integrated data, parsed it into the ontology as a semantic backbone to create a demonstrator for a MSE KG [110] that is supposed to make digital assets in MSE findable. At the time of submission, the MSE KG consists of 11005 entities, 90584 triples, 202 registered software entries, 148 registered events, and 236 publications.

RTG 2868 as a representative of the stakeholder group “doctoral researchers”. Another school was held in Aachen, mainly organized by K. Grünwald (data steward in TA-MDI).

Different concepts were tested and evaluated to refine the course program based on participant evaluation. All TAs contributed by sending their respective experts on various topics, e.g. ELNs, workflow solutions, metadata and DMPs. On expert level, e.g. an ELN online event with 180 participants from the MSE community and six

To ensure that the ontology development is tailor to the specific needs of different application contexts, we have driven and supported the development of 16 semantic artefacts at the domain and application level across multiple IUCs, closely collaborating with the PPs involved. These artefacts cover a wide range of topics relevant to multiple communities within MSE including crystallographic defects, computational materials science, microstructure representation, mechanical testing and various characterization techniques. The development of these metadata models have contributed significantly to the semantic infrastructure of NFDI-MatWerk, the integration and semantic alignment of the different development and initiatives to ensure harmonization is discussed and worked on IUC12 [111]. Additionally, we have invested in ensuring that emerging ontologies are integrated into computational workflows, as demonstrated in IUC02 [112] and IUC17 [113] where semantic annotation and knowledge graph instantiation have been embedded directly into simulation and data analysis processes.

In addition, TA-SAI has made substantial contributions to community education and dissemination. We have supported NFDI-MatWerk internal and external educational events such as the NFDI-MatWerk Seasonal Schools as well as the massive open online lecture series “Knowledge Graphs – Foundations and Applications” of Prof. Sack that reached more than 6000 interested individuals. Furthermore, we are actively building up an international community dedicated to the interplay of semantic web technologies and Material Science as demonstrated by the *Semantic Materials Science – Harnessing the Power of Semantic Web Technologies in Materials Science (SeMatS)* workshop series [114] that are part of established Computer Science conferences like SEMANTICS and ISWC (International Semantic Web Conference).

A confluence of factors, including budget cuts, the allocation of responsibilities within the NFDI, and the limited availability of pre-processed data, contributed to the challenges in achieving progress. The transformation of unstructured data into a format compatible with the MSE-KG required a significant investment of time. It is acknowledged that further time and educational investment will be required to enable the MSE community to share data in such a manner that it can be seamlessly ingested into the MSE-KG, which is one of the key objectives of this initiative. The activities of the **TA Workflows and Lab Environments (TA-WLE)** (previously TA-WSD) have followed two directions: Firstly, the TA has successfully worked on the major objectives and tasks formulated in the proposal. Secondly, the TA has strongly interacted with the PPs to fulfil the goals of the IUCs. A main objective was to ensure full reproducibility of data generation within NFDI-MatWerk. To this end, various measures have been foreseen and implemented. This starts with frameworks to ensure version control of involved software tools (GitHub: version control, package management: Conda and PyPI), particularly relevant for computational data. More than a dozen packages that are directly related to services provided by TA-WLE are shared in this way. For IUC04, IUC09, IUC17 and others, we also offer executable Jupyter notebooks as demonstrators, hosted on Binder via Jupyter4NFDI. These can be conveniently accessed,

enabling immediate hands-on experience with our developments. In-person hands-on sessions have been offered at conference satellite events (50-100 participants eachtime).

Central to the TA's efforts was the development of frameworks for integrating diverse tools and data types, often not natively interoperable. For instance, to ensure the combination of experimental results with their associated metadata, the ELN system PASTA has been further developed. As a founding member of the ELN Consortium [48], PASTA has played a key role in defining common specifications allowing the interchange of data between different ELNs. Finally, the pyiron team lead the development of the Python Workflow Definition (695 downloads, see nfdi1000 sheet), enabling the exchange of workflows between AiiDA, jobflow and pyiron [35].

To allow the execution of complex simulation protocols, the integrated development environment (IDE) pyiron [115] has been further developed (> 3400 pull requests between 10/21-04/25), modularized to meet the needs of several communities and restructured into workflow nodes to improve interoperability of workflows. To expand its accessibility and provide an interactive experience, a graphical user interface was also developed for pyiron. Meanwhile, to enhance user friendliness, e.g., for the analysis of tomographic images, the graphical programming language Chaldene [116] was developed and now contains a large variety of features. Another highlight of TA-WLE's activities includes the development and provision of specialised software frameworks designed to efficiently support ML approaches. A major mission of the work on the IUCs is connecting with the activities in other TAs as well as other NFDI consortia. Typical examples include the joint work on defects in collaboration with TA-SAI (IUC17) [113] and the establishment of a joint framework for the analysis of experimental data from APT in collaboration with FAIRmat (IUC09) [117]. Due to budget cuts, measure WSD-6 on Data curation, numerical precision and statistical/systematic errors received reduced attention. Simulation workflows for automatized uncertainty quantification for convergence parameters [118] and continuous integration as well as unit tests for code development have been established.

TA (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI) (previously Materials Data Infrastructure) as provided reliable data and metadata services interoperating with many other RDM infrastructures worldwide. This has allowed to efficiently connect the TA measures and has motivated the contributing partners to closely collaborate. Material scientists, domain data experts, data stewards, and computer scientists have been employed to define user requirements and implement scalable infrastructure components to fulfil them. This convergence of complementary expertise resulted in concrete, high-impact outcomes.

One example is the plugin development for the automatic extraction of metadata from SEM/FIB tomography data in IUC04, which enables seamless mapping of extracted information to a metadata schema designed in collaboration with PP13. Another successful outcome is the framework concept developed by IUC02 [112] which encompasses data generation, metadata enrichment (incl. data schema definition, ontology development, and KG construction), and the

development of a digital infrastructure to effectively address the needs of the MSE community regarding the usage, storage, search, and discovery of reference datasets. The infrastructure builds on the FDO paradigm to support machine-readability and accessibility of data.

The architecture working group, established in 2023, structured all technical and related infrastructure components in a portfolio of services and tools (see **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**), which since then has been enriched by perspectives from semantic and workflow specialists, as well as data stewards. To ensure interoperability and harmonization, the recommendations from accredited international initiatives, such as the RDA [59] and the FAIR Digital Objects Forum [71] have been implemented. For the same reason, many components have been adopted from, e.g., the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration Platform[119], the FAIR Data Spaces[120], EOSC [68], other NFDI consortia [121], NFDI Sections [122], and of course Base4NFDI [20].

As a central data representation, the concept of FAIR-DOs allows a common view on all data artifacts independently of their scientific contents and metadata structures and provides machine actionability and interpretability (see also 2.3). The developments of TA-MDI show that technically different flavours of FDOs based on Kernel Information Profile or FAIR Data Point retain interoperability and thus serve the long-term strategy to form a federated data space and will be integrated into an MSE KG. Data Stewards accompany the technical adoptions and developments and connect the results provided in TA-MDI seamlessly with the partners in the PPs and IUCs. Having a technological basis and an extendable architecture, TA-MDI will focus on a gradual outreach, onboarding and roll-out process to engage with more PPs and IUCs.

Figure 5: IUCs are distributed along the scientific user journey (x-axis), from data acquisition to publication and reuse. Research questions of the PPs related to the IUCs are focussing on specific lengthscales and relations within materials (expressed by the y-axis). PPs and IUC teams define success scenarios together.

4.1.2 Community-driven Infrastructure Use Case Selection

The IUCs play a pivotal role in NFDI-MatWerk, since they facilitate the connection of PPs, which also act as co-developers, with the services and solutions that are developed in the various TAs. It is vital that the developments made within NFDI-MatWerk remain both relevant to and consistent with the demands of the MSE community. The IUCs provide actual data and ensure that the NFDI-MatWerk data infrastructure will be integrated into the daily workflows at the PPs and research institutions in general. PPs include, in particular, large collaborative research initiatives such as CoEs (Cluster of Excellence), or IRTGs (International Research Training Groups), which guarantee a wide reach of NFDI-MatWerk into the community. The IUCs are selected in conjunction with the PPs in a transparent process that permits the MSE community to participate. It is asserted that IUCs function as legitimate assessments of NFDI-MatWerk services and the infrastructure that has been developed. These issues are indicative of a significant scientific MSE research community problem, the optimal resolution of which is the implementation, adaptation, or development of new NFDI-MatWerk services and solutions. The NFDI-MatWerk initiative has been developed to address the challenges posed by "real-world problems" by ensuring the implementation and deployment of MSE solutions is carried out to the highest standards. Typically, IUCs are utilised to evaluate the implemented NFDI-MatWerk workload along the

Figure 6: The flow chart shows the process how Infrastructure Use Cases (IUCs) are derived from community input. IUCs allow validating infrastructure feature implementations as well as their deployment.

scientific workflow (Figure 5). A significant proportion of the employed services are provided to the MSE community by the PIs and adapted by NFDI-MatWerk. These systems are operated

within the infrastructure of the respective academic institutions. NFDI-MatWerk facilitates interoperability of these services in the framework of IUCs to solve MSE-specific RDM challenges and provides a curated and central collection on the consortium online platform, and, in the future, in the MSE KG.

4.1.3 Overview of Infrastructure Use Cases

Detailed description of each IUC, including status reports and demonstrators (if available), can be found on the NFDI-MatWerk website [123]. Institutions marked with an asterisk (*) indicate co-applicant institutions acting as Participant Projects (= infrastructure providers that also have materials science contributions to IUCs).

IUC01: Teaching framework for MSE research data infrastructure
PPs: PP03 CRC/TRR285, PP12 EUSMAT, PP27 FID Materials Science
Material/Data: Guidelines, Teaching materials, Workshops Main Success Scenario: Teaching materials enhancing understanding and application of RDM principles, usage of ontologies and workflows among the MSE students. Added value MSE: Teaching personnel can utilize proposed materials to adopt them to their training courses
Main requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop engaging and accessible teaching materials, including slide decks, handouts, video tutorials, and interactive exercises. • Develop stakeholder specific teaching materials (i.e. onboarding of int. students) • Organize workshops to roll out created teaching materials.
IUC02: Development and application framework for distribution of reference datasets
PPs: PP01 SFB/TRR103; PP03 TRR285; PP14 MatScale; PP16 RPTU-AME; PP18 BAM; PP24 Hereon; PP25 SPP2489; PP26 CRC1625; PP28 FOR5657; PP29 AIMS-2
Material/Data: Hardness, Creep, Tensile, Fatigue, AM process, Metals, Num. data Main Success Scenario: Users can generate, find, and access data schemas and MSE datasets with comprehensive information regarding data, material, production, and measurement process including uncertainties, and e.g. use datasets as benchmark. Added value MSE: General framework for the generation, provision, identification and usage of reference datasets, best practice example.
Main requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MSE backend (data registration, PID, authenticity of reference data) • Metadata store (search and discover of data and interrelationships) • Mechanisms for creating incentives • Legal aspects (licenses) • General agreement on domain terminology and data structure to generate metadata schemas and/or ontologies • Support from TA-WLE and TA-SAI to assess data quality • Support from TA-WLE to create workflows transforming data schema into JSON format
IUC03: Storage concepts for large hierarchical datasets – merged with IUC05 into IUC15
IUC04: Model driven data space exploration
PPs: PP02 CRC1394, PP21 FAIR-GB, PP05 CRC/TRR270, PP25 SPP2489, PP26 CRC1635, PP29 AIMS-2
Material/Data: Ni-X solid solutions/intermetallics; Mg-X alloys; Thermodynamic and structural data of defects Main Success Scenario: User can automatically generate defect phase diagrams, based on both experimental and simulation data and predict performance of materials

Added value MSE: General framework of model-driven thermodynamic databases that combine computation and experiment
Main requirements: • Multiscale simulation (of multiphysics data) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workflows combining theoretical and experimental structural data of defects • Adaptive databases for high dimensional data structures containing sparse data • Visualization thermodynamics data: microstructure, chemical or mechanical perspective • Electronic lab book / LIMS (Laboratory Information Management System) (for defect data)
IUC05: Digital infrastructure and workflows for labs – merged with IUC03 into IUC15
IUC06: Integrating materials data from experiments and computation (ICME) into Industry 4.0 manufacturing paradigms – transferred to the NFDI Section 'Industry Engagement'
IUC07: Beyond 3D: Tools for tracking spatiotemporal microstructure evolution
PPs: PP06 CRC1368, PP13 CoMiTo, PP14 MatScale, PP17 IWT, PP21 FAIR-GB
Material/Data: Spatiotemporal point/voxel data of phases and crystal orientations, further tensorial or scalar field data from experiments or computer simulations of microstructure evolution at the microscopic and atomic scale.
Main Success Scenario: The user can characterize the geometrical arrangement of phases and grains in the material and employ flexible workflows to describe the evolution of microstructures during typical materials processing routes. This is achieved by flexibly exchanging spatiotemporal data between simulation tools for materials processing and property prediction from atomistic to microstructural length scales.
Added value MSE: A semantic description of microstructural features like phases, grains, grain boundaries and precipitates in form of an FDO employing a widely accepted data schema. This enables users to identify characteristic features of microstructures and their time evolution agnostic of specific data formats or implementations in a simulation code and to predict mechanical properties along typical materials processing routes.
Main requirements: • FAIR data schema for microstructures, meta data and semantic meaning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrating existing open-source tools for workflows mimicking materials processing routes • Parsers for common commercial tools will be made available • Ready-to-use open-access demonstrators adaptable to individual user requirements
IUC08: Approaches and best-practise examples for implementing the digital transformation in the daily laboratory work
PPs: PP28 FOR5657, PP15 NanoData, PP16 RPTU-AME, PP22 SPP2451, PP05 CRC/TRR270, PP26 CRC1625, PP29 AIMS-2
Material/Data: metallic alloys, microstructure, properties, history and testing methods
Main Success Scenario: Broad implementation FAIR data handling in daily lab work using ELNs; also e.g., Python-based evaluation / visualization tools / appropriate data schemas.
Added value MSE: Fostering low-level-entry concepts for digitization of lab work
Main requirements: • Integrate data management: Use and adapt FAIR data documentation and management across multiple testing methods: e.g., tensile, creep and fatigue testing, micro- and nano-indentation, Light microscopy, SEM/FIB and XRD <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatized implementation of meta-data schemas developed in NFDI-MatWerk in ELNs • Implement visualization for interactive visual exploration and analysis of materials datasets • Develop correlation analysis techniques: Systematize and enhance correlation analysis techniques for materials data, including error control. • Establish best practices: Define, test and enhance data handling, analysis and visualization. • Develop RDM infrastructure in collaboration with the computing center. • Standardize Data Formats: Define and implement standardized (meta)data formats based on NFDI-MatWerk ontologies in collaboration with IUC02, IUC10, IUC12, IUC14
IUC09: Infrastructure interfaces with condensed-matter physics (collab. with FAIRmat)

PPs: PP01 CRC/TRR 103, PP02 CRC 1394, PP21 FAIR-GB
<p>Material/Data: Experimental characterization and simulation of material microstructures</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Through analysis workflows of the measured or simulated microstructure data, users get more precise information and a deeper understanding of their results, with regard to the formation and interplay of the different elements of the microstructure.</p> <p>Added value MSE: Workflows and software tools designed with FAIRmat for interoperability of (meta)data, ontologies, and concepts for data curation, eliminate information loss.</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIRmat: Workflows on processing EM data (e.g., Kikuchi pattern analysis) into microstructure data including metadata with contextualization (e.g., sample prep.) • MatWerk: Workflows on processing data from EM (e.g. EBSD) or simulations (e.g. phase field simulations) into elements of the microstructure including all metadata with contextualization (e.g. simulation details, defect-detection algorithms) (NFDI-MatWerk) • Integration with device software via open-source parsers and simulation software via APIs • ML/statistical analysis of measured/simulated structural features for detection and interpretation of microstructure features, e.g. planar faults, dislocations, and interfaces • Interface between formats and queries of (meta)data in FAIRmat and NFDI-MatWerk • Ontology matching between both communities
IUC10: Interoperability of workflow systems
PPs: PP03 TRR285, PP15 NanoData, BAM*, PP20 Mat-o-Lab, PP16 RPTU-AME, PP01 CRC/TR103, PP14 MatScale, PP17 IWT, PP21 FAIR-GB, PP25 SPP2489
<p>Material/Data: Workflow data from manual experiments and numerical simulations</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Agreement on common workflow description for manual experiments, data analysis and numerical simulations and implementation of this description into one software tool in NFDI4Ing and NFDI-MatWerk</p> <p>Added value MSE: Ability to store workflows and their input and output data, ability to compare workflows; Identifying differences in workflows</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extension of the Python Workflow Definition as common workflow format for simulation workflows to manual experiments and data analysis. • https://github.com/OO-LD/awl-schema Format to support semantic description of workflow steps, their inputs and outputs
IUC11: Develop coupled ontologies and workflows for thermochemical treatments
Participant Projects: PP17 IWT, PP20 Mat-o-Lab
<p>Material/Data: High strength structural materials / time-temperature-transformation relations to microstructures</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Users can utilize a KG populated by process and material data to predict microstructures evolution by thermochemical heat treatments. FAIR data storage via KG allows a new level of reproducibility of experiments from different setups and groups.</p> <p>Added value MSE: Concepts for the combined ontologies for thermochemical processing and materials transformation. This provides a general framework for heat treatment representation and the resulting experimental impacts on materials microstructure.</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for automated data assembly • Ontology for heat treatment courses and transformation in structural materials • Workflow management systems that can be adapted during use (e.g., primary data acquisition, assertion augmentation, heterogeneous post-processing) • Data augmentation and condensation for advanced data handling
IUC12: Alignment of application- and higher-level ontologies
PPs: PP16 RPTU-AME, PP21 FAIR-GB, PP22 SPP-2451, PP20 Mat-o-Lab, PP03 TRR285, PP05 CRC/TRR270, PP26 CRC1625
Material/Data: Other ontologies, e.g., BFO, EMMO, PMDco, NIST ontologies, Structured Metadata, Specification on Ontology regarding Scope and Purpose from PPs

<p>Main Success Scenario: Users easily connect application- higher-level and general ontologies.</p> <p>Added value MSE: Consistent interfaces with all neighboring communities and expertise.</p> <p>Main requirements: • Preferably existing application/domain or general ontologies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured Metadata • Basis ontology advisory and ontology development support • Software interfaces for ontology alignment
<p>IUC13: Co-creation environment for linked data resources</p> <p>PPs: PP20 Mat-o-Lab, PP29 AIMS-2</p> <p>Material/Data: Data and services developed within the context of Mat-o-Lab, including an OpenSemanticLab instance as knowledge graph interface</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: AI-supported co-creation environment for semantic assets (terminologies, schemas, FDOs and workflow orchestration). User can create MWO-compliant FDOs with a few code lines, mouse clicks or words to an LLM chatbot.</p> <p>Added value MSE: Low level but robust way to interact with linked data and knowledge graphs.</p> <p>Main requirements: • Stable MWO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schematized MSE-KG
<p>IUC14: Integrated Data Infrastructure for Accelerated Materials Development</p> <p>PPs: PP15 NanoData, PP18 BAM, PP16 RPTU-AM, PP20 Mat-o-Lab PP22 SPP2451, PP26 CRC1625, PP25 SPP 2489</p> <p>Material/Data: Metals, glasses, polymers / process parameters and experimental results</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Collection of successful implementations of materials acceleration platforms</p> <p>Added value MSE: Accelerate optimization of new materials by a FAIR, automated, and scalable infrastructure integrating fabrication, characterization, and feedback-driven workflows.</p> <p>Main requirements: • Capture detailed process data, e.g., print parameters, post-processing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized ontologies, formalized workflows and persistent IDs for materials, experiments, and data provenance (for instance through ELN) • Advanced 3D printing platforms, e.g., LPBF for metals and automated glass synthesis rigs
<p>IUC15: Multiscale Materials Tomography – merged with IUCs 03 and 05</p> <p>PPs: PP02 CRC 1394, PP13 CoMiTo, PP15 NanoData, PP18 BAM, PP25 SPP 2489, PP28 FOR5657</p> <p>Material/Data: Tomographic datasets (e.g., APT, FIB-EBSD or OM serial sectioning), mechanical test data (e.g., high-throughput nanoindentation, micropillar compression data)</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Integrated infrastructure enables analysis and fusion of multiscale, multimodal data sets (e.g., tomography + mechanical testing) from a single material sample. Researchers can navigate between both local and global microstructural data and their correlation to mechanical properties of the sample.</p> <p>Added value MSE: This integrated infrastructure bridges multiple length scales and modalities for experimental data, enabling a deeper understanding of material behavior and its dependency on microstructure. By promoting FAIR data practices and standardized workflows, it ensures long-term accessibility, reusability, and reproducibility of complex datasets. The approach also fosters lab integration and workflow automation within the MatWerk community.</p> <p>Main requirements: • Tomography and mechanical data and their respective processing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A common metadata schema to incorporate all respective data sets from different sources • Metadata store for high-volume experimental data
<p>IUC16: Unified ontology for matrix-inclusion microstructure and composites - paused</p>
<p>IUC17: Ontologies for defects in crystals</p> <p>PPs: PP01 SFB/TRR 103, PP06 CRC 1368, PP14 MatScale, PP21 FAIR-GB, PP25 SPP 2489 DAMIC, PP26 SFB/CRC 1625, BAM*</p>

<p>Materials/Data: Single- and polycrystalline materials/metals / Simulation data as well as post-processed microscopy data.</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Researchers are able to describe, annotate, and query crystalline defect data across scales using a unified ontology infrastructure, enabling cross-comparison between atomistic simulations, mesoscale models, and experimental microscopy data.</p> <p>Added value MSE: Reusable, interoperable semantic framework for crystalline structures and defects. This generalization enables consistent metadata standards, supports automated workflows, and facilitates integration into broader data infrastructures.</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ontology for consistent description of crystallographic defects • Ontologies for describing experimental and simulation methods • Metadata schemas for crystal defects datasets • Software tools that enable semantic annotation within computational workflows • Use of LLMs and AI pipelines for semantic enrichment • Knowledge graph integration pipelines
<p>IUC18: ML workflows for data-driven materials modelling and inverse design</p>
<p>PPs: PP23 DFG/FNRS Meso-AID, PP25 SPP2489 DAMIC, PP29 AIMS-2</p>
<p>Materials/Data: Integration of microstructural data into digital workflows for materials, e.g., composites, porous materials and metals</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Users can generate, access, and reuse microstructure-resolved datasets and associated metadata capturing structural features across scales. Researchers are able to derive robust CPSP (Composition-Process-Structure-Property) relations and data-driven constitutive models from simulation and experimental data with low efforts through standardized workflows and data schemes. This enables the data integration into CPSP models and inverse design strategies, the selection of suitable surrogates and their training. A crucial ingredient is the publication of reference data sets, pre-trained models, and workflows.</p> <p>Added value MSE: The IUC provides the MatWerk community with standardized, interoperable access to microstructure-resolved data and metadata across materials, processes, and characterization methods. This is done by reusable, universal workflows for material-specific model selection and calibration to derive effective material models from available data. Thereby, researchers can focus on material related topics, model refinements.</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for multi-modal, multi-scale and large-scale data integration • Benchmarking scheme and exchange platform for models and benchmark results • Ontologies and semantics describing the CPSP links and related workflows • Inverse design methods and necessary experimental and simulation data sources • Standardized microstructure descriptors, data formats
<p>IUC19: Round-robin tests for materials characterization</p>
<p>PPs: New PP FA Hydrogen, PP BAM, FAU</p>
<p>Material/Data: Metallic alloys, e.g., advanced high-strength steels, Ni-based alloys, Al alloys, used for structural applications and exposed to corrosive environment containing in particular hydrogen. Data is obtained from mechanical testing and thermal desorption spectroscopy.</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: A FAIR comparison of data obtained by different stakeholders for one and the same experimental setup is achieved, equipment, methods and analysis techniques. To this end, a digital platform is available to share methods, data, and metadata.</p> <p>Added value MSE: The IUC results into a reusable procedure and toolset to perform Round Robin test for materials characterization.</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic description of the relevant devices, measurement procedures and metadata • Semantic description of the sample history, incl. H charging and sample transportation • Database to share and store data, as well as Workflows

IUC 20: Standardized Description of Samples for Electron Microscopy
PPs: PP13 CoMiTo, PP26 CRC 1625
<p>Material/Data: Metallic alloys / Physical laboratory samples for Electron Microscopy (EM) measurements</p> <p>Main Success Scenario: Users can describe their physical samples using a common structure and semantics. This information can thus be reused at the facility to gain knowledge about materials and to improve the efficiency of the experimental and data analysis workflows.</p> <p>Added value MSE: The structured and semantic description of physical laboratory samples enables consistent documentation, improving reproducibility and supporting workflow and provenance tracking across facilities. This approach serves as a blueprint for describing other types of samples and measurements within the MSE community, establishing a best practice use case for FAIR sample documentation exemplarily for EM.</p>
<p>Main requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vocabulary service to store controlled vocabularies • Ontology for physical sample description as well as for material and sample processing • Provenance workflow linking samples, treatments and processing, and EM measurements

4.2 Metadata standards

In this section, we focus on the contribution of NFDI-MatWerk to metadata standardization and harmonization in the MSE domain. Details on established services upon these standards are provided in subsequent chapters.

The NFDI-MatWerk consortium does not comprise institutions that are able to issue de jure metadata standards to the MSE communities in Germany. However, we actively contribute to de facto standardization through a coordinated strategy that combines bottom-up and top-down approaches: (1) Metadata schemas and semantic artifacts are developed collaboratively at the application level by PPs within the IUCs. These developments are driven by concrete research and data management needs within a subdomain. These efforts result in the emergence of harmonized semantics at a “local” level, based on the requirements of similar materials, methods or workflows. (2) To enable interoperability across different applications, we have established a central NFDI-MatWerk semantic infrastructure that provides domain-level semantics across applications. It is developed in a top-down fashion and disseminated to the bottom-up developments. Therefore, it supports semantic alignment.

Thus, our strategy is based on lateral harmonization of semantics within IUCs and vertical alignment of IUC semantic artefacts with the central NFDI-MatWerk semantic infrastructure. This will result in metadata that finds broad acceptance in relevant communities and can then mature to de-facto standards in the respective fields. The hierarchy of the semantic artefacts – in terms of level of abstraction – most relevant in NFDI-MatWerk is shown in Figure 7.

(1) Bottom-Up development of metadata schemas and semantic artefacts and lateral harmonization of terminology takes place within several initiatives, primarily organized through the IUCs. One initiative is the IUC “Ontologies for Defects in Crystals” (IUC17) [113] which focuses on developing ontological descriptions of material defects across different length scales. Within the NFDI-MatWerk framework, this led to the establishment of the OCDO (Open Crystallographic

Defects Ontologies) [124], a new ontology organization that includes various semantic artifacts for describing crystal defects, covering both atomistic and mesoscale representations.

Figure 7: NFDI-MatWerk semantic artefacts categorized by level of abstraction.

Complementing this, the CMSO (Computational Materials Sample Ontology) [125] and the ASMO (Atomistic Simulation Method Ontology) [126] provide semantic layers for the digital representation of computational samples and atomistic simulation workflows, respectively. Figure 8 illustrates the landscape of ontologies developed in relation to materials microstructure and simulation methods. These ontologies are integrated with the atomRDF python toolkit [17] which enables automated ontology instantiation during the creation of atomic and defect structures. This toolkit supports ontology-driven workflows for structure generation, manipulation, and querying, thereby facilitating semantic annotation and machine-readability. Further development of metadata schemas is carried out in IUC07 [127], where a workflow-centric metadata schema for micromechanical simulations is considered [128].

Further examples are the activities in IUC02 [112], where data schemas, developed in close collaboration with domain experts, reflect the terminology of relevant standards and support consistent documentation of materials testing experiments. A current use case focuses on creep reference data [129]. Beyond vocabulary development, this work demonstrates how tools such as SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) for validation, EVOKS (Editor for Vocabularies to Know Semantics) [130] for collaborative vocabulary curation, and FAIR-DO-Lab [131] for the creation and management of FDOs can be integrated into RDM workflows to ensure high-quality, interoperable metadata. Showcases of how scientists integrate metadata and semantic artefacts into their everyday research workflows and data management are presented in the MSE demonstrators, particularly within IUC02, IUC04, and IUC17 [112,113,132].

Figure 8: Semantic representation of materials microstructure across scales and processes. The blue boxes represent semantic artifacts developed within the consortium, supporting harmonized metadata across methods: materials simulation and characterization.

(2) *NFDI-MatWerk central semantic infrastructure* consist of two parts: The MatWerk Ontology (MWO) [57] and the MSE Knowledge Graph (MSE-KG) [133]. After strongly supporting the proliferation of the NFDI4culture ontology to a basic NFDI core ontology [44], TA-SAI developed the MatWerk Ontology (MWO) as a modularized extension of NFDIcore. This setup is adopted by several other consortia of the second and third NFDI funding round, which will ensure top-level alignment and high-level data interoperability. MWO is used as the semantic backbone of the MSE-KG and provides semantics to describe the administrative and organizational structure of our consortium as well as resources and digital assets. It also contains a minimal description of materials information specifically related to materials properties, classification and methods. These semantics can be extracted as linked-data schemas (in JSON-LD/YAML-LD (JSON for Linked Data [134] / YAML for Linked Data) [135]) for “datasets”, “computational workflows” and “experimental workflows” [136], further extension will integrate object oriented linked data schemas [137] for data provision towards the MSE-KG in the context of IUC13 (see 4.1.3). The MSE-KG is a central NFDI-MatWerk development that aims to accumulate metadata across MSE. It is developed to become the central metadata index of a decentralized MSE data infrastructure enabling interoperability and findability of MSE metadata on a domain and top level.

As a central data representation, the concept of FDO is adopted. A FDO is a unit of data, represented as a sequence of bits, that collects and links all critical information about an entity in one place and creates a new kind of actionable, meaningful, and technology-agnostic object. This

allows a common view on all data artifacts independently of their scientific contents and metadata structures and provides machine actionability and interpretability.

Representatives of NFDI-MatWerk participate in initiatives towards the harmonization and standardization of metadata and file formats. Examples include the “ELN Consortium” [48], which aims to define a common specification that allows the interchange of data and metadata between different ELNs. Similarly, the Python workflow definition [35,36] specifies a workflow exchange format for Python-based workflow engines, which will also be used by the EU project “MaterialsCommons”. TA-CI and TA-SAI have contributed to the harmonization of terminology in electron microscopy [138] through development of content within a community process, as well as the technical implementation of the terminology [139]. Members of NFDI-MatWerk are actively participating in NFDI Metadata Workshops organized by the Taskforce Metadata, aimed at developing joint recommendations for metadata schemas for datasets and use of re3data [135] as a central registry for repositories. NFDI-MatWerk also collaborates closely with Platform MaterialDigital (PMD), particularly in aligning with their ontology development activities and contributing to the PMDcore ontology [15], used in multiple contexts within the consortium. Furthermore, NFDI-MatWerk contributes to the international standardization landscape through active participation in the RDA, including the Working Group “Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains.”

These coordinated efforts position NFDI-MatWerk as a key driver of semantic interoperability and metadata standardization, both within the MSE community and in collaboration with other NFDI consortia (Sec. 3.2.1) as well as national and international research data initiatives.

4.3 Implementation of FAIR principles and data quality assurance

The aim of NFDI-MatWerk is (i) to provide tools, solutions and guidelines and offer counselling that enables researchers to implement the FAIR principles and (ii) to raise general awareness for FAIR data in the broader MSE community. Eventually, the implementation of the FAIR principles (cf. Sec. 2.1.2) is to be realized by MSE researchers.

The first aim is realized in close collaboration with selected groups of researchers from PPs and IUCs where solutions for specific RDM problems are developed and rolled out to individual research groups. This approach is designed to ensure scalability, allowing for future use by external research groups beyond the original development team. The second aim is addressed by measures that promote and facilitate involvement of the MSE community. Our website serves as a point of contact, including a helpdesk system and a solutions area providing links to tools, services and guidelines developed by NFDI-MatWerk, as well as other NFDI consortia or associations/institutions. The presented information is backed by the MSE-KG, which also collects details on RDM-related events, e.g. conferences, workshops, webinars. The solutions developed in the collaborations of PPs and IUCs are also included, thus leveraging impact.

To achieve FAIRness in this distributed setting, NFDI-MatWerk has created a recommendation specifying the requirements for minimal data quality. While these minimal requirements are deliberately simple, they are formally defined to allow automated compliance checking. Most importantly, the quality criteria are applicable to both Open Data and confidential data. For the required technical implementation, NFDI-MatWerk has committed to using the FDO Concept; through the registration of FDOs, datasets can be included into the MSE-KG.

The MWO forms a minimal set of relevant domain level metadata (R1). They need to be sufficient to describe a material, the methods with which it has been treated and the materials properties. They are stored together with bibliographical information about the author and responsible organization. It is used to harmonize metadata between IUCs and ultimately the MSE community (I1, I2). While the MWO is set up to provide a minimal common ground, it can be extended by areas of application to generate in-depth descriptions with a shared kernel language (F2). This forms the basis for (meta)data interoperability and exchange on access restricted instances like Coscine (A1.2) and finally the registration in NFDI-MatWerk's KG (F4).

The TAs of NFDI-MatWerk work together to provide tools and services that work according to these specifications for the entire research life cycle, from the integration of lab equipment over data processing to storing, sharing, and archiving research data. The defined notion of data quality is then implemented in commonly used services and tools. Hence, the implementation puts great emphasis on interoperability. This is demonstrated, for example, by the definition of the ELN-Format to enhance interoperability among ELNs such as elabFTW, PASTA and OpenSemanticLab, as well as by the adoption of metadata profiles and FDO specifications in central services such as Coscine and the NFDI-MatWerk Data and Metadata Repositories. The following is a showcase of selected efforts to support researchers on the way to adopting FAIR principles, explicitly referencing individual principles that were mainly targeted in parenthesis (following [140]).

IUC02 considered the creation of reference data sets with two goals: (i) Demonstrate forming and managing of research data according to state-of-the-art techniques and mechanisms to strengthen data availability and machine actionability and (ii) Discuss scientific quality measures for highly relevant and trustworthy (“quality”) data sets especially regarding conditions of measurement and data acquisition. Vocabularies and metadata profiles were created (I1, I2, R1) and made available together with the created data as open data publications in Zenodo (F1) and as machine actionable FDOs (F1, F4, A1, I3).

IUC11 focused on enabling FAIR data generation from non-digital or non-networked scientific instruments. The goal was to establish a low-barrier, cost-effective architecture for capturing and transmitting measurement data along with metadata, and ensure this information is semantically structured and published using open, machine-readable formats. The data and metadata now have the potential to comply with the FAIR principles: with references to shared vocabularies and

structured provenance (I2, R1.2) or FDOs (F1, F4, A1, I3), illustrating how legacy equipment can be integrated into modern FAIR-compliant research workflows [141].

Additionally, technical measures for raising awareness of FAIR principles in the broader community have been implemented. For undergraduates a basic course for "Good Scientific Practice" and "ELNs" has been readily established at TU Dresden. Compact courses on RDM in the form of 3–5-day schools for undergraduate and PhD students were designed, regularly conducted, and refined based on the feedback by the participants at different universities, resulting in a template for future implementations at other sites. Graduates and technicians are addressed at conferences, through the DGM society, and relevant events are promoted on the consortium's website.

4.4 Services provided by the consortium

In NFDI-MatWerk, we not only develop services ourselves: we create, adopt, and establish a broad and complex portfolio of technical and related components, services, and tools for the MSE community. The result is displayed in the Service Architecture. Individual components can serve as interconnected building blocks to create dedicated RDM service architectures that are required within the scope of the NFDI-MatWerk IUCs and beyond. A description of those interconnected components used for IUC02 and the added value for the MSE community can be found below.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. depicts the layered NFDI-MatWerk Service Architecture that ranges from the most MSE specific components, tools, and services as specialized layers on the top, to generic components on the bottom: Typically, the MSE scientists work with the frontend consisting of "Applications and Workflows" without having to worry about the technical details in the backend processes; application programmers will use the "Knowledge Graph Representation" with its tools, standards and semantic artifacts, the "Workflow Environment", and its common "Data Representation: FAIR Digital Objects" layer; "Data and Metadata Services" build generic data services which bear on established "IT Infrastructure" components. These technical layers are accompanied by essential pillars representing "Support" and "Dissemination" that are important to empower the MSE community in the usage (e.g. Data Stewardship), along with "Harmonization & Data Governance". Harmonization is important to ensure sustainable interoperability with other methods, concepts, and technologies developed nationally and internationally.

Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. contains components that are either provided and funded by NFDI-MatWerk, by other initiatives, and funded by the institutional base funding. The architecture considers a variety of services with different operating models. It resembles the decentralized nature of MSE research. Some already existing components provided by NFDI and other national and international initiatives are re-used and adapted, for

example user interfaces are specifically designed to meet the requirements of MSE scientists and are therefore applied in NFDI-MatWerk.

4.4.1 NFDI-MatWerk Service Architecture with technical components

Figure 9: A comprehensive overview of the service and infrastructure components to build a RDM service architecture.

Use Case of the Service Architecture: We now explain the general service architecture for the example of IUC02 (see also Sec. 4.3). This usecase can be described in two ways, (1) **from the MSE perspective:** IUC02 evaluates and validates MSE datasets and their uncertainties. To this end, we define criteria for a dataset to qualify as a reference dataset and provide comprehensive material descriptions (including data schema, ontology, knowledge graph). We developed a best

practice framework for generating and distributing MSE reference datasets using creep data of Ni-based superalloys as an example. Our framework concept includes the generation of data and their metadata, considering the intended usage and integrating into an easily accessible digital infrastructure to annotate and discover/distribute the datasets using a metadata schema accordingly aligned to a domain ontology; and (2) **from the RDM perspective**: IUC02 provides a concept to shape MSE datasets into exemplary reference datasets such that they are FAIR. We utilize the concepts of data quality, along with data structuring, interoperability, findability, and reusability. Furthermore, we conceptualize and adapt components (tools and services) to develop a digital infrastructure to fulfil the needs of the MSE community for usage, storage, search, and discovery of reference datasets. Our infrastructure builds on the FDO concept to support machine readability and accessibility. With ontology development, the reference dataset can be semantically represented, enabling the reuse of shared concepts from the domain experts, the community, and beyond. Another example of service architecture integration is the implementation of a user-friendly interface for the MSE Knowledge Graph. IUC13 contributes by establishing OpenSemanticLab [142] as an interface, offering features like visualizations, filterable tables, and detailed linked data views. This integration brings together multiple NFDI-MatWerk services, including the knowledge graph backend, SPARQL EndPoint, project website, LLM solutions, and developed semantic artifacts, to create accessible tools for materials scientists.

Our strategy in NFDI-MatWerk is to **ensure the sustainable operation of the architecture and its components and services**. The integration with Base4NFDI is also a part of this strategy to create OneNFDI (see below). In this context, highly scalable “cloud” services should be mentioned first. They generally have a high maturity as they build on production RDM infrastructures. Locally deployed software solutions are as robust as local infrastructure and operating model offer. Due to the interoperability of the tools and services, a transitioning between them should work seamlessly. Furthermore, the NFDI-MatWerk architecture will contribute to the Working Group “Overall Architecture” of the NFDI section “Common Infrastructures”, see also 3.2.2. It is essential to acknowledge that some of our services, which may appear to be duplicates, possess unique specifications tailored to use cases within the research community. For example, the NFDI-MatWerk Data Repository and the RDM platform Coscine have distinct purposes within their domains, despite surface-level similarities.

Supporting the development of Base4NFDI services to the ramp-up stage is considered part of the sustainability of NFDI and will be a central building block in the long-term provisioning of core FAIR enabling services. NFDI-MatWerk is currently advancing its work on IAM4NFDI and has a direct personal connection to this project with the PI M. Politze (RWTH). As we move forward, PID4NFDI will be examined in depth and adapted. Additionally, we recognize the importance of

collaboration with TS4NFDI and KGI4NFDI. NFDI-MatWerk has further personal connections to various other Base4NFDI projects like Jupyter4NFDI with T. Hickel (BAM/MPI-SusMat), J. Janssen (MPI SusMat), B. Flemisch (Universität Stuttgart), [REDACTED] and I. Bierenbaum (KIT, NFDI4ING); or KGI4NFDI and TS4NFDI with [REDACTED] (KIT, NFDI4ING); and Helpdesk4NFDI with S. Slawik (DGM) (for more about the Base4NFDI integration see 3.2).

We implement actively a range of measures designed to enhance the adoption and utilization of our services, which leads to an expansion of NFDI-MatWerk within the MSE community and a scaling of our services: We are engaging new PPs and IUCs that utilize our tools and contribute to the development of best practices within and for the community as such as IUC02. To facilitate broader usage, we have established a roll-out group with the primary goal of lowering barriers to entry. By fostering an approachable and transparent environment, we aim to encourage community engagement (see 3.4).

The use of our services is tracked and measured to keep an overview about our expansion and scaling efforts and allows stakeholders easy access to key performance indicators. We aim to use already established solutions that are available under free licenses, such as Prometheus [143]. It enables us to gain valuable insights into service performance and usage patterns. Additionally, we build informative dashboards using Grafana [144], which provide visual representations of the data collected. An example of this can be seen with the Coscine dashboard hosted on GitLab [145]. The implementation of these dashboards is scheduled for this summer and will be displayed on the NFDI-MatWerk website.

4.5 Impact of changes of external conditions / constraints

Note: The impact of budget cuts by 30% and of the increase in personnel costs on the work programme has already been outlined Sec. 3.4.1

The accelerated development in AI technologies have strongly changed the needs of the MSE community as data-based research gained traction. Especially Large Language Models (LLM) quickly established themselves as tools in MSE. In several PPs of NFDI-MatWerk (e.g., PP14, PP20), the performance of these techniques for extracting semantic information from research documents and enriching KGs have been systematically explored. Furthermore, a feasibility study for workflow orchestration based on LLMs has been performed with the LangSim interface for the pyiron workflow engine.

The increased focus on data-driven research in MSE is also clearly noticeable by a strong interest in machine-learning approaches for computational and experimental data. The desire for sustainable materials development and life-cycle management of materials makes data-sharing between heterogenous partners more important. Several calls by funding agencies on German and European level have further promoted these trends. Consequently, it becomes more and

more common sense in the community that semantic standards are needed for Interoperability and Reusability. This improves the acceptance of technologies and services developed by NFDI-MatWerk, coming together with an increased demand of training, support, and tools, which we have matched with our dissemination strategy. The strong interest in the MSE Research Data Forum in 2025 is one of the proofs that NFDI-MatWerk addresses the interest of the community.

Since the start of NFDI-MatWerk, numerous national and international activities regarding the digital transformation with relevance to MSE have been launched. NFDI e.V. recently became a member of the RDA. Here, NFDI-MatWerk is an active member of the RDA working group (WG) "Harmonized terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in Materials Science and related domains". In 2021, recommendations on FAIR metrics for the EOSC were published, providing an analysis of activities relevant to the definition of FAIR Metrics in the EOSC context [146]. Since then, two international "FAIR Digital Object Conferences" have been organized to plan and develop the FDO implementations. NFDI-MatWerk is very active in the FAIR DO Forum [71] and is contributing to the working groups specifying and implementing FDOs. Furthermore, [REDACTED] (KIT) is a member of the Steering Committee and the Technical Advisory Committee. The ELN consortium [147] has been set up after submission of the NFDI-MatWerk proposal. NFDI-MatWerk in person of S. Brinkmann (FZJ) is deeply engaged in the activities of ELN consortium by supporting the process of defining the common specification for data and metadata interchange between different ELNs.

In addition, more digital natives working in the field leads to increasing acceptance for new digital solutions, observable in a growing demand. Further, the funding agencies (DFG, BMFTR) require much more detailed RDM strategie and DMPs for all individual projects. Hence, the driving force of several stakeholders to develop their own digital infrastructure is growing. Here, NFDI-MatWerk tries to align the activities and offers a DMP guide and through the Community Membership a service as a low-threshold support. The OneNFDI strategy supports consolidation of services between consortia, thus enabling the use of the NFDI basic services by NFDI-MatWerk (e.g. DMP4NFDI, IAM4NFDI), the contribution to these services with own expertise (IAM4NFDI by RWTH Aachen IT Center), shaping efficiency.

5 Work Programme

Each TA addresses individual aspects to foster the digital transformation of the MSE community. Additionally, the TAs are devoted to a set of overarching activities, that span the entire NFDI-MatWerk consortium and that are linked to the overall objectives. These are indicated within the TAs work programme by #hashtags.

#oneNFDI & #eosc	Develop an architecture and align the MSE digital ecosystem towards oneNFDI and EOSC [2 topics] → contributes to Objective 2
#empowerAI	Empower the MSE community to leverage the power of AI-tools by connecting existing services and integrating AI into MSE workflows. → Objective 1,3

#MSEsemantics	Support the MSE community in the development of a semantic representation for materials and materials data → Objectives 1,2,4
#knowledgegraph	Building and providing a central MSE knowledge graph aligned to NFDIcore → Objectives 2, 5
#dataQuality	Defining quality criteria and processes for curation of MSE data → new Objective 5
#roll-out	Ensure the reach out to the MSE community with activities that are scalable and address heterogeneity of the community → Objective 1
#solutions	Demonstrate our federated system: build solutions connecting architecture, workflows, data, and semantics for real world RDM-challenges → Objectives 1,2,3,4
#DigiTrans	Promoting the digital transformation of MSE with processes to foster self empowerment of the community and enable their contributions → Objective 1, 2, 6

Overview of Task Area Measures

Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-spokesperson(s)
TA Community Interaction (TA-CI)	CI-1: Concepts for Self-empowerment CI-2: Interactive communication platforms and public relations CI-3: Community counselling/consulting and engagement CI-4: Community Events – Stimulate and enable community interaction CI-5: Continuous exchange between MSE Institutions CI-6: Exchange & information formats on AI-application in MSE CI-7: Interaction with Base4NFDI and other relevant NFDI activities CI-8: Data Quality, Data Handling and Curation CI-9: Consortium related overarching activities	M. Zimmermann, R. Schwaiger
TA Workflows and Lab environment (TA-WLE)	WLE-1: Coordination and Services WLE-2: Deployment, Adoption, and Sustainability of Software Tools WLE-3: Node Store WLE-4: Development environment for computational workflows WLE-5: Application workflows in experiment and data analysis WLE-6: Quality of data and workflows WLE-7: Workflows for AI: Data curation, ML and LLMs	T. Hickel, R. Schwaiger, P. Felfer, J. Janssen, A. Krüger
TA (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI)	MDI-1: Data Registration services MDI-2: Central Services MDI-3: Support and Outreach	M. Politze, M. Müller, A. Streit, A. Hartmaier
TA Semantics and Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI)	SAI-1: Development of domain and application-level ontologies SAI-2: Semantic and data quality assessment SAI-3: Ontology integration in computational workflows SAI-4: Interoperable and community-driven MWO ontology ecosystem SAI-5: Semantic integration and enrichment of the MSE-KG SAI-6: Knowledge graph group support SAI-7: Leverage LLMs for data extraction and exploration SAI-8: MSE Semantics Dissemination and Education	S. Sandfeld, H. Sack, A. Krüger
TA Strategy Development (TA-SD)	SD-1: Organizational development SD-2: Service and solution management SD-3: Communication and outreach strategy SD-4: Project governance SD-5: Networking	C. Eberl

5.1 Task Area Community Interaction (TA-CI)

5.1.1 Status of TA-CI's Field in MSE

The heterogeneity of MSE requires particular efforts to reach out to the overall community by taking advantage of the different networks they are organized in. Hence, a close collaboration of different stakeholder associations has to be constantly stimulated and coordinated. With the DGM and the DVM two core associations are involved in TA-CI activities and are a guarantee for vivid interaction and exchange within the MSE community.

Figure 10: Logo of Task Area Community Interaction (TA-CI)

In the initial phase of NFDI-MatWerk, TA-CI activities focused on presenting and explaining the primary goals and visions of the consortium across as many MSE networks as possible. The building of awareness and even understanding (e.g. regarding data sovereignty) had to be addressed in very early events and pro-active contact to stakeholder groups at different institutions played a major role. In order to build up a sound basis for each stakeholder to empower themselves in dealing with the NFDI-MatWerk solutions that were being created in parallel, a comprehensive and continuously ongoing revision of the NFDI-MatWerk online presence happened (www.nfdi-matwerk.de). This was accompanied e.g. by summer and winter schools for PhDs and PostDocs offering a general introduction to digitalization as well as first tangible solutions, developed within the IUCs. The feedback helped developing teaching strategies as well as improve on teaching material to reach a community beyond the PPs [148]. Furthermore, a RDM guide was developed and published. The changing mindset of the community led to a growing number of researchers addressing TA-CI to find out how to participate in NFDI-MatWerk. Furthermore, the need for in-depth support and individual workshops for larger projects has grown and therefore changed our support. Hence, TA-CI's focus will increasingly be on mediation between the community stakeholders and the developers of the NFDI-MatWerk solutions to help overcome initial gaps of understanding. Moreover, offers to enhance self-empowerment for different knowledge levels and through dissemination channels will be an essential focus in future activities of TA-CI.

5.1.2 General Objectives of the TA-CI

The primary objective of the TA-CI is to encourage widespread acceptance and ensure active participation of the entire MSE community. This requires to cater to a variety of interdisciplinary research areas and diverse working cultures. A core mission will be to convince the MSE community that NFDI-MatWerk's solutions are dedicated to creating knowledge and not just to collect data in a tedious way. TA-CI shall be the first point of contact for community stakeholders not yet actively involved in NFDI-MatWerk activities. TA-CI will identify the respective stage of

development, acquirer the needs and communicate this to experts from the relevant TAs of NFDI-MatWerk. TA-CI shall help new stakeholders with an onboarding process, where they can identify the most suitable IUCs. If no fitting IUC can be found TA-CI shall help initiating discussions with experts and other PPs to determine if a new IUC is needed. Particular emphasis will be put on counseling new stakeholders on how to prepare and handle data in order to comply with the FAIR principles and data quality standards. TA-CI will be strongly committed to rollout activities, foster exchange with other NFDI consortia to support the oneNFDI vision. Furthermore, TA-CI support to weave digitalization into university education.

5.1.3 Measures and Work Packages

Measure CI-1: Concepts for self-empowerment (DGM, TUD)

Self-empowering researchers and technical staff to use NFDI-MatWerk tools is key to a sustainable adoption. Measure CI-1 focuses on developing modular, target-group-specific learning formats ranging from e-learning and webinars to in-person workshops. It includes tailored training concepts for lab technicians to strengthen their role in research workflows. Dedicated support for developing didactically sound teaching materials shall be provided, as well as a central platform offering structured, interactive learning experiences. TA CI coordinates content development and provides templates for other TAs. [#roll-out](#) [#DigiTrans](#) [#solutions](#)

KPIs: Number of educational media resources published in open and closed access, number of events held for educational purposes (DFG datasheet nfdi1000 numbers: 1005, 1006, 1008)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-1.1 Blended self-learning formats, webinars and teaching materials (DGM, TUD):

This work package develops modular self-learning formats tailored to the diverse prior knowledge of stakeholders. The initial focus lies in promoting self-empowerment of users in applying workflows developed within NFDI-MatWerk. Existing learning materials for individual tools will be systematically linked on the webpage. TA-CI will provide templates to support other TAs in identifying appropriate learning methods, developing tailored content for their stakeholder groups, and defining the necessary technical and didactic requirements. A dedicated e-learning platform will be launched and integrated into the NFDI-MatWerk website, offering hands-on demonstrations, exercises, and quizzes etc. It builds upon the self-learning infrastructure currently being developed within the DGM Academy (release end of 2025). Video content will be produced directly at the TA institutions using minimum technical equipment. If local production is not feasible, DGM will offer recording facilities and post-production processes. Complementing the digital formats, the second part of the blended learning strategy focuses on in-person offerings. These include introductory courses on FAIR RDM and workshops on selected topics.

WP CI-1.2 Training courses for technicians at scientific institutions & teaching material – exchange with training facilities, data stewards, success stories (TUD): In the realm of materials science, the role of lab technicians is pivotal. They are the backbone of research and development, responsible for conducting experiments and gathering the “raw” data. In the scope of NFDI-MatWerk the importance of teaching materials for lab technicians cannot be overstated. Digitalization refers to the integration of digital technologies into various processes, including the use of software for data collection and analysis, usage of electronic notebooks and automation of lab processes. Teaching materials that incorporate these digital tools are essential for equipping lab technicians with the skills needed to navigate this changing landscape. TA-CI will create hands-on training for lab technicians. Case studies from educational program will be adopted for NFDI-MatWerk. A video series with young professionals explaining the aspects of RDM in everyday life of lab technicians, providing best practice examples of collecting and handling data while emphasizing the importance of metadata and standardized semantics.

Measure CI-2: Interactive communication platforms and public relations (DGM)

NFDI-MatWerk’s services, outcomes, and community activities are made visible and accessible through a user-oriented web platform and coordinated communication formats. The website provides easy access to tools, materials, events, and project updates. LinkedIn, newsletters, and outreach materials support broad dissemination and targeted interaction with key stakeholders. TA-CI coordinates the development and implementation of all communication tools in close collaboration with TA-SD and other TAs, and in alignment with NFDI-wide strategies. [#roll-out](#)

KPIs: Total number of website visits (DFG datasheet nfdi1000 number 5110), number of communication tools recipients

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-2.1 Central web platform and knowledge hub (DGM): The NFDI-MatWerk website serves as a central access point for all services and project-related information and representation, offering a low-threshold interface that links users to the full range of NFDI-MatWerk and external resources. It includes regularly updated content on key dates, events, tools, workflows, RDM explanations, and success stories. Features to be developed include a search function, monitoring of service usage, teaching formats, a help desk form, and a user-friendly frontend interface for interaction with the MSE-KG. The goal is to make the knowledge graph easily accessible and searchable for simple and complex, context-based queries from various user groups, as well as linking different contents of the website. TA-CI will lead this activity in close cooperation with TA-SAI (see also SAI-6). DGM (experienced for website hosting) is responsible for hosting, maintaining, and editorial management, while all TAs contribute content.

WP CI-2.2 Communication tools for community information and engagement (DGM, TUD):

This work package ensures that NFDI-MatWerk's solutions, services, and community activities are clearly and consistently communicated to specific target groups to foster visibility, understanding, and engagement. TA-CI coordinates content creation in close collaboration with all TAs and in strategic alignment with TA-SD. Updates on developments and events are regularly shared via the project website, LinkedIn, newsletters, and visual outreach formats. The LinkedIn channel serves as a central social media platform for showcasing progress, amplifying community contributions, and engaging with researchers beyond the consortium. A quarterly NFDI-MatWerk newsletter compiles key updates and is supported by external outreach through the DGM newsletter, which has over 8,000 recipients in the German MSE community, as well as additional communication via the DVM network. To facilitate interaction at events and within the community, TA-CI creates and regularly updates outreach event materials, including flyers, slides, and short videos. These materials are actively used at community events such as described in CI-4. Additionally, TA-CI develops targeted content for closely affiliated NFDI-MatWerk community members, such as solution owners and institutional partners, to strengthen their participation and enable a focused dialogue. All communication activities are embedded in NFDI-wide strategies to ensure a coherent and coordinated public presence across the national research data infrastructure. TA-CI will create at least one survey in cooperation with TA-SD to collect feedback on the RDM status and needs from a larger number of the community.

Measure CI-3 Community counselling/consulting and engagement (DGM, IWS)

To support the effective use and broader uptake of NFDI-MatWerk services, a professional helpdesk system and a structured engagement process for new research consortia will be established. The helpdesk ticket system will be embedded into the project website and provide coordinated first- and second-level support, managed by TA-CI with input from other TAs. At the same time, consortia with thematically aligned research will be identified, introduced to relevant solutions, and guided through tailored onboarding and feedback steps—with at least two new groups engaged each year. [#roll-out](#) [#MSEsemantics](#) [#solutions](#)

KPIs: Number of user consultations (DFG datasheet nfdi1000 number: 1021)

Requested funding:

WP CI-3.1 Community counselling/consulting (DGM, IWS)

To empower the MatWerk community during [#roll-out](#), this work package will provide direct support to individuals with a variety of specific questions and practical challenges related to offered [#solutions](#), organizational matters, and general and strategic topics. A professional helpdesk system with ticket management system on open-source basis (e.g., Zammad) will be

implemented to ensure a structured and reliable process, providing organized and dependable assistance and responsibilities. It is aligned with the FAIR principles and is encouraged within the NFDI RDM Helpdesk network. It will be integrated into the NFDI-MatWerk website, where it will be hosted, updated and features managed. TA-MDI will support TA-CI during the implementation (see MDI-3.4). First Level Support, handled by TA-CI (one main and one backup), will respond to basic technical or organizational questions or forward them to Second Level Support, i.e., designated contacts in the technical TAs and TA-SD. If an issue remains unresolved, TA-CI will reassign the ticket. An FAQ will be developed on the basis of the submitted tickets. Additionally, the integration of a forum-like functionality to allow community answers will be explored together with TA-MDI. All activities will align with NFDI-wide efforts and evolve based on user feedback.

WP CI-3.2 Community engaging process (IWS, TUD): Through a continuous screening of the announcements for collaborative MSE research consortia approved by funding agencies (e.g. DFG, BMFTR, EU) will be contacted. Call specific requirements on RDM, open-access strategies and dissemination will be analysed and matched with the NFDI-MatWerk solution portfolio. Consultations with the the consortia will follow to prepare workshops dedicated to the specific needs of the consortia at hand and matched with existing IUCs. Therefore, the project can profit quickly from NFDI-MatWerk solutions and can become a PP. TA-CI will organize match making processes for specific stakeholder groups (data steward, PhD, technician, system administrator etc.) to enable experience, e.g. on implementation of an ELN. Individual counselling on the local implementation of NFDI-MatWerk solutions can be arranged. TA-CI will actively obtain feedback on usability of NFDI-MatWerk solutions.

Measure CI-4 Community Events – Stimulate and enable community interaction (DGM, DVM, IWS)

Community events are held to strengthen visibility, fostering exchange, and encouraging adoption. Presentations, posters, and booths are used to showcase the consortium's solutions and services, gather feedback, and engage MSE stakeholders. TA-CI coordinates event planning and implementation with support from all TAs. Outreach materials, such as flyers, slides, and short videos, are maintained and updated for consistent communication. The event schedule planned in advance to ensure strategic and coordinated participation. Participation in external events will be prioritized together with TA-SD and the Lenkungskreis. Participation of NFDI-MatWerk individuals from all TAs at non-NFDI-MatWerk events by means of lectures, posters etc. will be regularly queried, announced on the webpage and accordingly promoted through the LinkedIn channel.

KPIs: Number and participants of events held, number and participants of community-related activities (DFG datasheet nfdi1000 numbers: 1007, contribution to 2001)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-4.1 NFDI-MatWerk conferences for the community (DGM): NFDI-MatWerk will host its own annual community conference: a symposium at the MSE Congress (>1,000 participants, largest conference for MSE in Germany; on-site and online) in even years and the smaller MSE Research Data Forum (≤150 participants; onsite) in odd years. Both are organized by DGM and shaped by a consortium-wide program committee. Participation is open for the community. The consortium disseminates solutions and identifies needs and possible contributions.

WP CI-4.2 Community conferences and expert committees (DGM, DVM, TUD): Targeted specialist events—such as conferences and workshops on electron microscopy and other topics relevant to our PPs, will be attended to increase awareness and for dissemination. In parallel, all DGM/DVM expert committee meetings (e.g. DVM/DGM working group “Materialermüdung”) will be invited to actively involve all expert committees, gather their feedback on specific needs, and enable direct and in-depth exchange with scientists, industry professionals, and machine manufacturers.

WP CI-4.3 Workshop formats for universities and other research institutions (TUD, IWS): Targeted workshops at universities and research institutions provide an opportunity for NFDI-MatWerk to connect directly with potential user groups whose research aligns with the consortium’s focus areas. These events are designed to address specific needs with tailored presentations of IUCs, architectural components, and relevant services. Institutional requirements are collected in advance via a questionnaire. Further input and feedback are gathered during the workshop to inform future development. TA-CI coordinates the planning and implementation with support from all other TAs. Up to four workshops are planned per year, each lasting between 0.5 and 1 day.

Measure CI-5: Establish NFDI-MatWerk - concept “User journeys” and integration of data literacy in Matwerk study programs (FZJ, TUD)

This measure aims to define and map user journeys specifically for PhD students involved in scientific projects. By understanding and documenting these pathways, we can identify pain points, enhance data literacy, and improve overall RDM practices. [#roll-out](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-5.1 Define user journeys within NFDI-MatWerk-architecture (DGM, IWS, FZJ): The goal is to create detailed user journey maps that illustrate the experiences of PhD students in managing research data and developing data literacy throughout their scientific projects. A very particular attention will be paid to collaborative projects with complex relationships between

different institutions and disciplines. For this purpose, User Journeys will be organized where research goals, methods and processes will be identified together with the related (meta) data flux. TA-CI in cooperation with TA-SD will develop visual mapping tools to create user journey diagrams that highlight stages of the research process. Together with the project, pain points in RDM will be identified and mapped to NFDI-MatWerk solutions and IUCs. The projects will be provided by learning material as well as invitations to workshops dedicated to the particular needs. User feedback mechanism will be provided to continuously improve solutions. Practical examples will be published on the NFDI-MatWerk webpage to increase adoption or contributions.

WP CI-5.2 Data literacy lectures for MatWerk students (IWS, DGM, DVM): In close collaboration with Studenttag MatWerk and BV-MatWerk, the integration of single lecture sequences, practical trainings of RDM as well as development of new lectures will be the focus of this WP. The offers will reach from hand-outs, power point collections, videos (part of which will come from measure CI-1) to workshops for lecturers on the basics of RDM and the NFDI-Matwerk solutions. Besides developing and promoting the offers, TA-CI will stimulate exchange and discussions of how to integrate teaching portfolios on data literacy so that they will be in line with the accreditation requirements. Hence, further exchange with accreditation institutes will be taken up. The identification of potential synergies in the implementation of data literacy lectures between different NFDI consortia is also being aimed at and will be closely related to the activities in measure CI-7. As professional societies, DGM and DVM will support the adoption into MatWerk universities through their network.

Measure CI-6: Exchange & information formats on AI-application in MSE (TUD, DGM)

This work package aims to establish standardized exchange and information formats that facilitate the integration and application of AI methodologies in materials research and development. TA-CI will support the MSE community that actively contributes to the evolution of data standards and practices in AI applications. [#empowerAI](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-6.1 Promoting vivid exchange on AI-application in MSE (TUD)

The goal is to enhance collaboration among researchers, improve data interoperability, and accelerate innovation by creating a common framework for AI-driven materials science applications. The main tasks of TA-CI include a regular screening of research papers and events with AI context within MSE, identify experts and new talents to win them for online pitches (e.g. lunch talks). These pitches shall stimulate lively exchange of ideas and discussion on AI in MSE. In addition, short reports drawing attention to latest publications and brief summaries of the online pitches will be provided to the overall community via website and social media. This work package will be closely interlinked with TA-SD activities within WP SD-2.2 on foresight and future trends.

Measure CI-7: Interaction with Base4NFDI and other relevant NFDI activities (IWS, TUD)

Interactions within the NFDI network are crucial for enhancing knowledge sharing and leverage diverse expertise, contributing to the overarching goal of oneNFDI. Therefore, TA-CI will be responsible for the scouting of Base4NFDI activities, especially on training, education and community interaction. Furthermore, TA-CI will deepen the cooperation with working group “Physical Sciences in NFDI” and NFDI section “Training & Education”. [#oneNFDI](#)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-7.1 Interaction with NFDI-internal initiatives (IWS): In July 2025 NFDI-MatWerk started its first incubator project together with DMP4NFDI within Base4NFDI activities. With the guide on research data management plan [149], TA-CI created a basis for this cooperation. TA-CI will maintain regular contact with other NFDI consortia, in particular Base4NFDI. TA-CI will screen for events and workshops from other consortia, collect and providing a basic pool of advertising material (e.g. presentation slides, posters, flyers) and take part in initiatives from Base4NFDI regarding training and education. TA-CI will further contribute to collaborative activities within working group “Physical Sciences in NFDI”. This includes possible joint appearances at consortia conferences, organization of talk series with invited guests and promotion of each other's events. TA-CI will actively contribute to the events organized by NFDI section “Training & Education”. Experience from other consortia and projects (e.g. DALIA) will be adopted for NFDI-MatWerk.

Measure CI-8: Data Quality, Data Handling and Curation (BAM)

Data sets are considered high quality when their creation process is fully documented and therefore completely reproducibility. This requires, that all metadata is provided in a semantically structured format. TA-CI will collect examples of best practice for data quality, handling and curation. From these examples, generalized guidelinesbuilding on SAI-2.4 and TA-WLE-6 workflows will be developed with input from the IUCs and PPs or the greater community and made available via the NFDI-MatWerk website to promote consistent, high-quality data practices. [#dataQuality](#) [#MSEsemantics](#)

KPIs: Number of best practise examples

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP CI-8.1 Best practice examples (BAM, TUD): Best practice examples for data quality, data handling and data curation will be provided. This includes e.g. for experimentally collected data measurement accuracy, the use of calibrated measurement equipment, the specification of measurement uncertainty or error ranges, the completeness of metadata and the use of standardized formats, units and terminology. As this depends on the research question posed,

the specific criteria are developed in the IUCs. The results of SAI-2.4 on assessing the quality of datasets based on their semantic annotations and associated metadata will be incorporated here. The (software) solutions for the community provided on the NFDI-MatWerk website will be incorporated into best practices for data collection, data preparation, data processing and data analysis. The workflows to be developed in TA-WLE-6 will be considered for data curation. The recommendations of TA MDI-1.5 are observed in FAIRness assessment. [#dataQuality](#)

WP CI-8.2 – Minimum Data Quality Criteria (BAM, TUD): In this WP, general quality criteria and recommendations (including assessment of FAIRness of FDOs) from all IUCs are collected, unified and listed. They will be prepared, published and communicated in a comprehensible manner and, if necessary, adapted following feedback requests. The content will come from the technical TAs and the input from WPs SAI-2.4, WLE-6 and MDI-1.5 is taken into account. WP TA-SD-1.4 coordinates the implementation of quality controls and procedures within the consortium. Processes for the development of quality criteria and quality classes will be developed in TA-SD WP 1.4. [#dataQuality](#)

Measure CI-9: Consortium related overarching activities (TUD, FZJ)

We strengthen strategic coordination and visibility within NFDI-MatWerk by supporting the structured rollout of services and facilitating continuous communication between TAs and IUCs. TA-CI contributes to this by translating technical content, integrating experts, and organising key consortium meetings, all of which are closely aligned with TA-SD. [#DigiTrans](#) [#roll-out](#)

Requested funding:

WP CI-9.1 Roll-out: TA-CI is an active member of the Roll-out Group, which is responsible for the strategic framework of a structured implementation of NFDI-MatWerk solutions and services in the scientific community. The Roll-out Group develops content and measures to help researchers access, test and independently apply NFDI-MatWerk solutions. Here TA-CI plays a dual role: it contributes core components for the distribution, such as interfaces and workflows, and it supports other TAs in translating their solutions into user-oriented formats ready for communication via the website, training sessions or events. Feedback from the roll-out is actively fed back into development, ensuring that services are improved in response to actual user needs. The roll-out strategy is also closely aligned with the goals of TA-SD, particularly SD-2 and SD-3.

WP CI-9.2 Ongoing overarching coordination and organization: TA-CI plays a central role in user-oriented project coordination to ensure continuous information exchange and alignment across NFDI-MatWerk. This involves actively participating in regular meetings with other TAs and IUCs, which enables the early integration of new developments into the ongoing refinement of CI measures. A key focus is identifying and involving subject-specific experts from across the

consortium to contribute to Measures CI-1, CI-3 and CI-5 based on evolving requirements. TA-CI also coordinates its own regular meetings, including biweekly CI group meetings.. Strategic coordination is also supported by preparing and implementing the annual consortium coordination (AHoD) and strategy meeting in close collaboration with TA-SD.

5.1.4 Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives

The professional organizations **German Society for Materials Science** (DGM) and the German Society for Materials Research and Testing (DVM) are fostering both structural and personal connections within the MSE community at national and international levels. Institutional frameworks such as expert groups have extensive experience in sharing project outcomes within the community, making them a highly valuable asset in this TA. DGM will act as “door opener” for a vivid exchange with BV-Matwerk and Studentag-Matwerk, for potential future Matwerk study programs. DGM will contribute with their technical expertise in digital event and communication strategies. **Prof. M. Zimmermann** and **Prof. R. Schwaiger** are excellent and very well-known scientists and networkers within MSE while also being well familiar with different collaborative funding programs (priority program, research training group, collaborative research center and many more) as active PIs as well as members of various expert groups and research committees, hence have a rich repertoire of opportunities to act as ambassadors for NFDI-MatWerk.

5.1.5 Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases

The main focus of TA-CI activities will be on promoting the best practice examples from all active IUCs and on scaling up specific solutions for the use in a broader community. To **gather the information on the developed solutions within all IUCs**, members of TA-CI will regularly visit the working meetings and get feedback from PPs. This information will be used to create teaching materials within work packages CI-1.1 and CI-1.2. **TA-CI works for all IUCs as well as TAs**, examples of TA-CI contribution to IUCs are listed below.

IUC01: in close collaboration with the experts from technical TAs, TA-CI will lead the activities of IUC01. Based on the insights gained from the initial phase of NFDI-MatWerk, TA-CI will focus on enhancing the educational program for the MSE community.

IUC02, IUC08: TA-CI will be strongly involved in the work within both IUCs with a main focus on developing a general concept for roll-out process of proposed solutions. Therefore, members of TA-CI will ensure the alignment of the activities in IUCs with the measures CI-1 and CI-8. Additionally, TA-CI will be responsible for harmonizing the tasks of IUCs with the broader objectives of the roll-out group.

5.2 Task Area Workflows and Lab Environments (TA-WLE)

5.2.1 Status of TA-WLE's field in MSE

Figure 11: Logo of Task Area Workflows and Lab Environments (TA-WLE)

The FAIR principles [140] are a central mission of NFDI and have a strong impact on how scientific data need to be managed. It is less recognized that there is also a strong motion to establish FAIR principles for research software (RS) [150]. The FAIR4RS working group emphasizes the role of research software as digital objects to maximise research value. One way to achieve findability and accessibility is the implementation of open-source licence models. However, the definition of

RS includes “source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose.” [151].

The NFDI-MatWerk consortium has taken on this important task and invests substantial resources into FAIR workflows [152]. This is driven by the confidence that almost every materials scientist, working with experiments or simulation, nowadays uses workflows (or recipes) in a broader sense. However, many of them are individually designed and manually executed, e.g., with Excel sheets and shell or Python scripts. This results in a chain of transformation steps that are arbitrary, undocumented and not reproducible by others and often even the originator himself. To avoid the resulting errors and limited efficiency, the usage of workflow management systems (WfMS) is desired. While WfMSs have been used in biosciences for several years, their exploitation in materials science only recently became a topic of interest [153].

In NFDI-MatWerk, various measures have already been taken and implemented to make workflows FAIR and reproducible (cf. Sec. 4.1.1). This includes frameworks to ensure interoperability and version control of software tools, ELN solutions for the combination of experimental results with metadata, the investment into graphical user interfaces such as Chaldene [116] and pyironflow and the substantial investments into the WfMS pyiron [154]. All these developments are strongly aligned to the needs of the MSE community. This is necessary, because the hierarchical, multiscale character of materials requires a combination of heterogenous software tools, experimental processes, and characterization techniques. At the same time, the intrinsically interdisciplinary character of MSE motivated us to align our services to those of neighbouring disciplines, promoting the spirit of [#oneNFDI](#). To this end, the continued modularization of our workflow solutions and the semantic annotation of workflow nodes, [#MSEsemantics](#), are central to advancing interoperability. Building on recent activities, the TA-WLE is currently expanding its focus on interfaces to ML activities and LLM agents, [#empowerAI](#) as well as the quality of workflows and generated data, [#dataQuality](#).

5.2.2 General objectives of TA-WLE

The change of the TA's name from "Materials Workflows and Software Development" to "Workflows and Lab Environments" indicates the change of the TA's objectives. In the first funding period, the development of software components (e.g., pyiron, PASTA, Chaldene, ML tools) was necessary to provide solutions for the MSE community and its specific demands. It strongly enhanced our expertise in key topics related to experimental and simulation workflows. The second phase is devoted to the consolidation of the efforts on FAIR workflows and will ensure that integrated approaches such as Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs) in lab environments benefit from them. Accordingly, the major objectives of the TA-WLE are:

- (1) **Digitalization of computational, experimental and data-transformation workflows.** We provide material scientists with the toolbox to accelerate their research in lab environments. To this end, they should be represented and processed in virtualized processing platforms, i.e. digital notebooks. This ensures machine-readability and the applicability of AI technologies such as Large Language Models (LLMs). → related measures (below): WLE-4, WLE-5
- (2) Support the development and use of **Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs)** in lab environments, which will contribute to speeding up the discovery, development, and deployment of new materials by integrating automation, high-throughput experimentation, ML, and other data-driven approaches. → WLE-5
- (3) Establish **FAIR workflows** in the MSE community. We provide an exchange environment for workflows to make them findable and accessible. Technologies such as conda-forge and a strong link to ontologies render workflows interoperable. **Reusability** and **reproducibility** is addressed, which are major concerns in experimental MSE. → WLE-1, WLE-3
- (4) **Integrability of workflows** is central for the multidisciplinary and hierarchical complexities of MSE. Workflows must enable seamless integration of simulations from atomic to mesoscale and continuum levels. Systematically correlating experimental insights from diverse lab environments and diverse materials classes enhances understanding. → WLE-4, WLE-5
- (5) The workflows should support the generation of **high-quality research data in MSE**. They should enable the systematic handling of intrinsic uncertainties in modelling and experimental studies, incl. numerical precision as well as statistical, systematic, and instrumental errors. We work on techniques to automatically quantify such errors, curate and annotate large datasets from high-throughput experiments, and account for error propagation. → WLE-7
- (6) To promote user adoption and broad dissemination, we focus on developing **user-friendly solutions** within this TA. This includes creating intuitive graphical user interfaces, sharing best-practice examples, and offering a wide range of adaptable tools and methods. → WLE-2

5.2.3 Measures and Work Packages

Measure WLE-1: Coordination and Services (BAM, MPCDF)

This measure plays a key role in bridging efforts across TAs and PPs and supporting coordination, knowledge exchange, and service integration within TA-WLE. Another task is the strong alignment of workflows and lab environment activities with Base4NFDI and the OneNFDI principles. To this end, it provides a technical foundation that ensures all workflows and software tools are consistently developed and easy to use across the community. [#solutions](#) [#oneNFDI](#)

KPIs: Number of software solutions available via conda / PyPI packages

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP WLE-1.1 Coordination: Coordination of activities in this TA and with other TAs, with Base4NFDI services, with other initiatives related to workflows, and with PPs.

WP WLE-1.2 Version control: The TA will ensure that a distributed version control system (e.g., Git) for software solutions is available to make them traceable and reproducible.

WP WLE-1.3 Automated installation: An automated installation of tools together with their frameworks through conda-forge [34] and PyPI [155] will reduce the barrier for participants to set up their environments, ensuring that the diverse range of tools developed by NFDI-MatWerk is accessible with minimal configuration, enhancing their reproducibility.

WP WLE-1.4 Execution framework: The development of a minimalistic framework to set up and benchmark workflows is supported by Docker containers at local or centralized servers. Additionally, the integration of MyBinder allows users to run Jupyter notebooks directly from their browsers, i.e., it removes the need for complex local installations and enabling easier engagement with workflows. The services of Jupyter4NFDI will be used and supported.

WP WLE-1.5 Support: Continuous support of participants, e.g., in terms of IUCs, within the NFDI-MatWerk to make use of the following measures.

Measure WLE-2: Deployment, Adoption, and Sustainability of Software Tools (FZJ, FAU)

This measure ensures the effective deployment, adoption, and long-term sustainability of the solutions developed in TA-WLE. It combines the development of training, dissemination, and demonstrator projects to maximize impact across the MSE community. The formats in the WPs support broad accessibility, institutional integration, and long-term capacity building. Dissemination efforts — including workshops, publications, and joint projects — will promote best practices and community engagement. Demonstrators will apply the tools to real scientific problems, providing feedback for ongoing development and showcasing their research relevance. Together, these activities ensure the tools are well-integrated into daily workflows and supported by a growing, engaged user base. [#solutions](#) [#roll-out](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

KPIs: Number of provided educational materials (in terms of ECTS points); number of training events (workshops, tutorials, online courses), and participant numbers

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP WLE-2.1: Scalable and sustainable training programs: This WP focuses on designing and delivering flexible training formats to support broad skill development. We will significantly increase the number of online courses, integrating hands-on exercises and interactive modules tailored to varying expertise levels. Web-based documentation and self-paced learning materials will complement synchronous sessions, ensuring year-round accessibility. The content will be made reusable to support integration into academic curricula and institutional training efforts.

WP WLE-2.2: Dissemination and community engagement: Dissemination activities aim to promote tool adoption, raise visibility, and engage the broader MSE community. Together with TA-CI, this will include workshops and conference sessions, in addition to publishing use cases and contributing to joint publications (e.g., ML benchmarks). A coordinated outreach strategy will help build a strong user base and promote best practices in SW use and RDM, reinforcing the tools' position within daily research routines.

WP WLE-2.3: Scientific demonstrators and feedback integration: Demonstrator projects serve as applied test cases for the developed tools, linking SW development with scientific inquiry. These projects will highlight tool interoperability and practical relevance, while also producing valuable user feedback to inform future improvements. One planned demonstrator will explore microstructure reconstruction from serial sectioning data in metallography. Feedback loops will feed directly into development and training strategies.

Measure WLE-3 – Node Store (*MPCDF, MPI SusMat*)

This measure aims to further develop the FAIR-ness (focus on findability and accessibility) of *nodes*, which are understood as basic (or “atomic”) building blocks of workflows. Such nodes can, e.g., create an atomistic structure, start the computation with a software-tool, parse the output data of an experimental device, or can even be for a SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) of a manual experiment. The actual implementation of a node can be realized e.g. as a python function, as a pyiron or a KadiStudio workflow node, or as a concrete instruction taken, e.g. from the Python Workflow Definition [35] (cf. WLE-5). This WP will develop a node store which allows to manage nodes with all their relevant properties. The database will allow finding and selecting appropriate nodes, which are compatible with a specific workflow framework based on semantic annotations (cf. TA-SAI). Properties of a specific query include the input and output types of the node, the classification of the node, e.g. as a parser for an experimental device, together with metadata like author and license. The system will serve as a comprehensive hub for FAIR composing, deploying, publishing, and re-using components of complex workflows for the MSE community. [#roll-out](#) [#solutions](#)

KPI: Number of hosted and number of downloaded nodes

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP WLE-3.1: Design and deployment of relational database for the node store:

Development of the data model of the database underlying the node store. This includes the definition of relevant metadata for the nodes as well as relations between them, also to capture semantic annotations for nodes developed in Measure 4 and 5. This database will be deployed on MPCDF cloud resources, considering an authentication mechanism via IAM4NFDI.

WP WLE-3.2: Web frontend for accessing the node-store database: A web frontend for making the content visible and for browsing the node-store database will be developed using the Django framework. This will also enable rating the nodes, proposing changes to nodes (e.g., by adding new keywords) or suggesting new nodes by IAM4NFDI-authenticated users. Where appropriate, a link to a use case of the node in an already published workflow (e.g., PMD workflow store) or the NFDI-MatWerk website will be displayed.

WP WLE-3.3: API to the node store: The node store needs to expose a comprehensive API, which, e.g., allows software clients to make a copy of the data, or to perform specific queries, like listing all nodes which generate an output type that is currently required by a certain node in a pyiron workflow. The latter will be the initial focus and primary client for the new API.

WP WLE-3.4: Connection to other infrastructures: The node-store API will be constantly extended to enable queries by other WfMSs like KadiStudio or to capture information about node usage in published workflows of different sources like the PMD workflow store.

Measure WLE-4: Development environment for computation workflows (*MPI SusMat, BAM*)

The development and deployment of workflows in dedicated environments is needed in the MSE community due to the diversity of methodologies and tools required for describing heterogeneous materials, while their interoperability and reuse should be ensured. Using Jupyter notebook technology, this philosophy was already pushed forward as one of the success stories of NFDI-MatWerk. Challenges were identified regarding the complexity of Python programming, the usage of different workflow engines, high performance computing, and storage solutions, and were partially addressed already. In addition, there is an increasing demand to connect computational workflows and [#knowledgegraph](#) technology. [#MSEsemantics](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

KPIs: Number of feature requests from MSE community (through IUCs) implemented

Requested funding: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

WP WLE-4.1: Continuous support and maintenance of pyiron workflow framework: pyiron is the major IDE framework used in TA-WLE. Its development and maintenance will be continued, with focus on its modularity. Solutions for scheduling of computational jobs and storage will be

consolidated. The multi-physical and the hierarchical nature of materials will be considered by hierarchical software solutions. A focus will be on integrating tools for the continuum scale.

WP WLE-4.2: Concept development for (functional) programming of workflows: There will be continuous work on concepts for the workflow environment pyiron, meeting feature requests of the community. Specifically, we will consequently push the use of Python functions as building blocks (nodes) of workflows, being decisive for reproducibility and interoperability. We will collaborate on a format for exchanging nodes (Python Workflow Definition), see WLE-5.2.

WP WLE-4.3: Extend coupling of visual programming with workflows: The goal is to improve usability of workflow environments by an intuitive and practical GUI, which is fully connected with the Python programming in Jupyter notebooks. The work will be based on the successful experience with Chaldene (DFKI) and pyironflow (MPI-Susmat/BAM).

WP WLE-4.4: Coupling of workflows with ontologies and the MSE-KG: We continue to work on the interpretation of ontology files and the categorization of data. Further, semantic annotation of workflow nodes has become a major activity in the TA-WLE to improve the interoperability of workflows, to enable semantic workflow generation and to couple to LLM agents. It further supports the automatic integration of computed data into the MSE-KG. To this end, services such as AtomRDF and Semantikon will be consolidated, maintained and applied.

Measure WLE-5: Application Workflows in Experiment and Data Analysis (FZJ, FAU)

This measure focuses on creating standardized and interoperable workflows in experimental materials science to improve reproducibility, data integration, and automation aligned to computational materials science. As research becomes increasingly data-centric, harmonized FAIR workflows are essential for MAPs and automated labs. Measure 5 will continue to evaluate the wide range of workflow tools (e.g., pyiron, Python Workflow Definition, CWL, Galaxy, Airflow), will ensure that the requirements of manual experiments and data analysis are satisfied in the python workflow description (with WLE-4.2) and will work towards a common exchange format. We will build on a previously developed, markdown-enhanced SOP format that combines user-friendliness with automation readiness. SOPs will be continuously integrated into ELNs with full execution logs and will be linked to data lineage via the MSE-KG. Collaboration with initiatives like FAIRMat, NOMAD and MADICES ensures parser compatibility and contributes to shared workflow standards through the ELN Consortium. This will enable scalable, reproducible, and efficient workflows across the MSE community. [#solutions](#)

KPIs: Number of instruments/file types supported by workflow infrastructure; number of interoperable workflow formats supported (incl. parsers, number of SOPs in the node store)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

WP WLE-5.1: Machine-readable sample marking and experiment tracking system: This WP will establish a universal, machine-readable marking system for diverse materials (metals, polymers, ceramics, etc.) to track sample identity, data lineage and generation. The system will combine physical tags (e.g., NFC chips, QR codes) with digital tokens linked to instruments, SOPs, and users. For legacy instruments, it can include ELN-linked human input devices (HID) and other microcontrollers. These devices will be integrated into workflow environments, ELNs, and knowledge graphs (e.g., MSE-KG) to support automated data capture. The result will be visual specimen and data inheritance graphs, showing relationships between source materials, samples, and processed outputs. This infrastructure will enable high-fidelity provenance tracking for experimental workflows, especially important for MAPs.

WP WLE-5.2: Standardization and interoperability of workflows: This WP focuses on continuously evaluating workflow tools and formats used across the MSE community. We will assess their usability, extensibility, and integration potential, identifying overlaps and gaps. Based on this analysis and in collaboration with WLE-4.2, we will continue to develop the python workflow description. Rather than imposing a single toolset, the aim is to streamline existing ecosystems and promote convergence towards a single platform. Outcomes will support FAIR data principles and reduce redundancy in workflow development.

WP WLE-5.3: Structured and reusable SOPs for experimental workflows: We will further develop a structured, markdown-enhanced SOP format that supports both manual and automated processes. This includes evaluating verbosity levels, adapting formats to different institutional needs, and using large language models (LLMs) to help standardize existing procedures—always with human oversight. SOPs will be embedded in ELNs, containing both planned steps and execution logs with timestamps. We will contribute to the ELN Consortium's efforts to create a shared standard, enabling better integration with lab automation, parser infrastructure, and research metadata platforms like the MSE-KG.

Measure WLE-6 – Quality of data and workflows (*BAM, MPI SusMat*)

To achieve a quantitative prediction from simulation or machine-learned (ML) models, it is essential to not only model materials properties but also their uncertainty. The error propagation is based on the workflow, which enables the separation of the systematic and statistical uncertainties of the individual workflow steps, applying to both computational methods and experimental measurements by capturing their provenance. ML interatomic potentials are an example of how the uncertainty of ab initio training data impose uncertainties in properties like temperature-concentration phase diagrams. [#dataQuality](#) [#empowerAI](#)

KPIs: Number of workflows for data curation or quality control

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP WLE-6.1: Workflows for uncertainty quantification in materials science: Motivated by the multi-scale example of coupling the electronic scale with the interatomic scale, we aim to extend the previously developed models [118,156] for uncertainty propagation to develop a length-scale independent toolbox for uncertainty quantification and error propagation in the materials science domain. This enforces a joint handling of data points and error bars / confidence intervals in workflows.

WP WLE-6.2: Workflows for applying Bayesian optimization for parameter sampling: Materials acceleration platforms (MAPs) are often based on complex experiments and the prediction of materials properties with ML models suffers from sparse data. Bayesian optimization is well suited to efficiently guide the selection of experiments, by improving the sampling of complex parameter spaces and minimizing the resulting statistical error. We will provide a set of workflows for this kind of technologies including real-time validation of data.

WP WLE-6.3: Workflows to analyse causality and correlation: The multiphysics character and hierarchical structure of materials data makes the dependencies of data quality between different properties less apparent. We will therefore establish workflows to assess and curate the quality, causality and correlation of huge experimental data sets. This will involve an evaluation of data veracity, inconsistencies, incompleteness, and ambiguities.

Measure WLE-7 – Workflows for AI: Data curation, ML and LLMs (DFKI, FZJ, MPI SusMat)

AI technologies are becoming increasingly important in MSE, and not all exciting developments can be handled and foreseen in this proposal. In close collaboration with the activities in TA-SAI, this measure focuses on the workflow perspective on ML and LLMs. A variety of automatic workflows on data splitting (training/test/validation), model selection, model training/calibration and posterior model evaluation based on available datasets and metrics is foreseen. The potential of LLMs for the design of workflows will be evaluated. The activities will also be linked to already existing (IUC18) and expected future IUCs imposed by the PPs. [#empowerAI](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

KPIs: Number of use cases that benefit from the services provided in this measure

Requested funding:

WP WLE-7.1: ML Demonstrator platform, usability: Based on an iterative user-centred design methodology, a tool (web interface) that serves particularly experimentalists, but also more theoretically oriented staff will be developed. The tool allows for demonstrating the generation, training and application of ML models and will in particular be used in the context of IUC18.

WP WLE-7.2: Workflows for data generation and curation: The coupling of experimental and simulation workflows with ML models is essential to accelerate research in MSE. In close

collaboration with measure WP WLE-4 and IUC18, the newly developed workflows are directly coupled to ML models, using semantic annotations and built-in interfaces to the knowledge graph.

WP WLE-7.3: Development and application of LLM agents: This WP aims to develop and finetune LLM-based systems that allow for interactions in natural language including questions and instructions. Logical and semantic connections with and for workflows are used. Throughout the next funding period several IUCs on this topic are expected.

WP WLE-7.4: Finetuning of LLMs: The trend in LLM research is currently shifting from 1- or 2-stage approaches to a 3-stage process: generic model → domain-specific adaptation → problem-specific adaptation. Based on a continuous monitoring of the state-of-the-art, a generic tool set will be developed so that the materials science community can finetune their own specific LLMs.

WP WLE-7.5: Segmentation: The WP addresses the problem of semantic segmentation (SemSeg) in the context of microstructure analysis, since it is often unclear what material phases should be mapped to the concept “object”, and generic foundation models typically fail. A large variety of specialized software tools and ML approaches are used for SemSeg, and the creation of annotations on the training examples remains a highly relevant topic in practice. A particularly interesting approach is correlative microscopy, where information from one modality is used to annotate images from another, requiring cross-modality image registration. We will solve the SemSeg issue by (1) creating a repository and decision aid of existing SemSeg approaches and software solutions, and by (2) creating a MSE specific foundation model that can be integrated in any downstream application to solve the most generic form of cross-modality image registration.

5.2.4 Appropriateness of the Task Area’s Representatives

The **Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)** is a technical and scientific federal institute for materials with a focus on safety in technology and chemistry. To this end, it is strongly committed to the digitalization of materials, has strong activities in RDM, materials ontologies, and ML concepts. **Prof. Dr. Norbert Huber** is vice president of the BAM and responsible for the digital transformation of all departments. **Dr. Tilmann Hickel** is head of the division “Materials Informatics” at BAM and has a long-standing expertise in the workflow management of computational materials design. He used ab initio thermodynamics to optimize structural and functional properties of metallic alloys with a recent focus on the phase stability and phase transformation of defects in complex microstructures.

Prof. Dr. Ruth Schwaiger is the director of the Institute of Energy Materials and Devices (IMD) – Structure and Function of Materials (IMD-1) at **Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)** and Chair of Energy Engineering Materials at RWTH Aachen. Her research focus lies on the mechanical behavior of materials across length scales as well as in situ and operando methods in complex lab environments. Her expertise in integrating advanced experimental techniques with modeling

and simulation makes her a valuable contributor to NFDI MatWerk, especially in the development of interoperable workflows that bridge laboratory data acquisition and materials modeling.

The **Max Planck Institut für Nachhaltige Materialien (MPI SusMat)** conducts basic research on high-performance, sustainable materials. It develops and applies novel experimental and simulation methods to correlate the complex micro- and nanostructure of advanced materials and their properties under realistic environments. **Dr. Jan Janssen** is head of the group “Materials Informatics” in the department Computational Materials Science headed by Prof. Jörg Neugebauer. His expertise is the development of complex automatic workflows for the simulation of thermodynamic properties. A core activity in his group is the IDE pyiron, which was made available to the scientific community in 2018 through an open-source license (www.pyiron.org).

Prof. Dr. Antonio Krüger is CEO and scientific director of the **German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence GmbH (DFKI)** and head of the department “Cognitive Assistants” at DFKI. He is a full professor for Computer Science at Saarland University. Prof. Krueger is an internationally renowned expert on Man-Machine-Interaction and AI. His expertise in translating cutting-edge AI research into practical systems, is highly relevant to the integration of LLMs and semantic infrastructure in materials science. Prof. Krüger’s involvement ensures that NFDI-MatWerk remains at the forefront of applying AI to advance FAIR data practices in MSE.

Prof. Dr. Peter Felfer is professor at the Department of Materials Science at the **FAU Erlangen Nürnberg**. He integrates advanced microscopy with computational materials science, pioneering atom probe tomography (APT) instrumentation with ultra-low hydrogen backgrounds and developing open-source software toolchains for data analysis and FAIR data sharing including hardware development. His open source equipment enable atomic-scale hydrogen mapping and trap energy resolution, crucial for understanding hydrogen embrittlement. His work has significantly advanced computationally driven APT as a powerful tool for structural materials research through hardware/software integration.

5.2.5 Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases

The IUCs associated with TA-WLE serve three main purposes: (i) provide techniques and software solutions that are of general interest to the whole MSE community complementing the measures established by the TA, (ii) apply the software solutions and workflows developed to specific materials science problems and challenge the TA, (iii) demonstrate the impact of the developed services. In the following, the relevance of selected IUCs for TA-WLE is described:

IUC04: This IUC provides a general framework of model-driven thermodynamic databases that combine computation and experiment. Central for the project is the OpenBIS ELN, in which categories and object types are defined according to MSE application ontologies. The results of workflows for the computation of thermodynamic defect data are (via conceptual dictionaries) also uploaded to the ELN OpenBIS. The work is linked to WP WLE-4.4, WLE-5.2, and WLE-6.2.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC07: The FAIR data schema for microstructures developed in this IUC is decisive for the interoperability of software tools and workflows on the microscale, using finite element methods, phase field or crystal plasticity. It will be taken care of in WP WLE-4.1 and WLE-5.2.

IUC08: This IUC will provide best-practice examples for the use of ELNs (cf. WP WLE-5.2), with a focus on microstructures and mechanical properties. The correlation analysis techniques developed here will need to be integrated in corresponding workflows (cf. WP WLE-6.3).

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC09: Workflows are designed in coordination with FAIRmat such that the exchange of data, metadata, ontologies, and concepts for data curation (measure WLE-6) between two NFDI consortia is ensured. The analysis of electron microscopy data benefits from the combined perspectives of condensed-matter physics (FAIRmat) and materials engineering (MatWerk) and is connected to WP WLE-7.5.

IUC10: Multiscale simulations represent a challenge for workflow systems in materials science (see WLE-5). They require the connection of various distinct data types as well as computer codes of different communities. To this end, the node store can serve as an exchange platform (cf. WP WLE-3.4). The coverage of available tools is substantially improved if a connection to workflow systems established in other NFDI communities (here: NFDI4Ing) is possible.

IUC11: In this IUC, an ontological representation encompassing the workflows of both heat treatment courses and material transformation is designed to provide a common and unified description (cf. WP WLE-4.4 and WLE-5.1). The workflows need to be adaptable during use.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC14: The materials acceleration platform used at BAM in IUC14 is prototypical for a novel trend in the MSE community. The need of formalized workflows for handling the complex and coupled processes is apparent (cf. WP WLE-5.2). The IUC serves also as a benchmark for the performance of GUIs for workflows management (cf. WP WLE-4.3).

IUC15: This serves as an ideal IUC for the activities in WP WLE-5.3, as it standardizes the processing workflows to obtain tomographic and mechanical datasets from different resources aiming at long-term accessibility, reusability, and reproducibility of complex datasets.

IUC17: This IUC already served in the 1st funding period as a perfect chance to combine the execution of computational workflows on the atomistic scale with the development of a domain ontology for defects in crystals. Tools like AtomRDF have been developed for this purpose, and its integration with multiple workflow environments is planned. Further extensions address

additional length scales, thermodynamic concepts and experimental data. The activities will be continued in tight connection with WP WLE-4.4.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC18: Based on the rapid development of ML approaches, researchers are able to derive robust CPSP (Composition-Process-Structure-Property) relations and data-driven constitutive models from available simulation and experimental data with low efforts through standardized workflows. These activities are used to benchmark the developments for WP in WLE-7 and WLE 4.3.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC19: Round robin tests are frequently performed in collaborative projects to improve the consistency and reliability of results. The availability of well-defined SOPs, which make these tests reproducible, is decisive for this purpose. This IUC supports WP WLE-5.3 and WLE-6.1.

IUC20: This IUC extends IUC15 to the case for electron microscopy. Provenance workflows linking the samples, treatments and processing are required, as done in WP-WLE-5.3.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

5.3 Task Area (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI)

5.3.1 Status of this Task Area's Field in MSE

Figure 12: Logo of Task Area (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI)

Handling of metadata and data, i.e., (meta)data, is at the core of all RDM processes. NFDI-MatWerk has proposed a common architecture to interoperably align services, workflows and tools, and to address specific organizational and infrastructural needs of researchers and their home institutions (see Sec. 4.4). Due to the distributed nature of data handling and processing, a certain set of minimal interoperability and quality criteria is required. As described in Sec. 4.3, the FDO concept

forms this basis within NFDI-MatWerk. The architecture has been agreed upon in the consortium, but the vision for the entire NFDI still needs to be shaped: the Section Common Infrastructures has established the Working Group Overall Architecture to address this topic.

The FDO concept has been widely discussed and several competing implementation flavours based on its interpretations (e.g., W3C Standards [157], RDA Recommendations, or other community efforts like RO-Crate (Research Object Crate) [158]) have emerged over the past years. So far, only few interoperability layers have been implemented and have the required maturity. Nevertheless, the FDO concept is a core building block to achieve interoperability within the NFDI and EOSC and a key component to bridge to the European data spaces. On the other

hand, several FAIR assessment frameworks have been established, allowing researchers to validate and improve their adaptation of the FAIR principles within their own environment.

Even though the representation of single data sets is indispensable, the gain of knowledge comes from their connection within a knowledge graph. Development of semantics and ontologies are in the focus of TA-SAI, and it needs an infrastructural foundation by integration into services like ELNs and repositories. Consequently, we see a gradual uptake of semantics into metadata profiles that can be reused in the platforms and infrastructure components supporting the technical integration (e.g. AIMS, EVOKS, Terminology Service).

As we observe a standardization on the level of data representation, so do we on the level of the technical infrastructures. Foremost, so-called hyperscalers have built highly scalable infrastructures that allow to support a variety of different applications. Many of these technologies, e.g., Object Storages or Container-based virtualization, have become more accessible also within small private and community cloud setups.

5.3.2 General Objectives of the Task Area

The TA (Meta)Data Interoperability (TA-MDI) is responsible for the technical backbone of the consortium. This is required to form the basis for an interoperable ecosystem (previously called Digital Materials Environment, DME) of services, workflows, and tools that are developed or endorsed by NFDI-MatWerk and adopted by the researchers. A key assumption is that the vast amount of technical infrastructure components is distributed and governed by research groups or local universities' computing centres: TA-MDI must ensure that these local infrastructures are scalable and federated. Consequently, the harmonization within the NFDI-MatWerk Architecture represents a pivotal objective, as well as the connection to other NFDI consortia through the contribution to overarching topics like the Identity and Access Management, or the Overall Architecture within the Section Common Infrastructures and the Base4NFDI projects.

As a key component of interoperability, the FDO concept is used to connect the different parties within the ecosystem. TA-MDI is also concerned with interconnecting FDOs with the semantic and workflow infrastructures, making the FDO concept and KG more accessible to the researchers of the MSE community. The TA will therefore contribute to a few central services to create, register, harvest and search for FDOs, define semantic terminologies and metadata profiles, and manage individual knowledge graphs for the users.

Concurrently with the technical implementation and setup of services, TA-MDI also puts emphasis on the roll-out and the onboarding of research groups and local IT providers at universities to basic RDM principles and to the developed and endorsed tools, by offering guidelines, workshops, and best practices for their utilization.

5.3.3 Measures and Work Packages

Measure MDI-1 Data Registration services (*KIT, RWTH*)

This measure establishes the technical foundations for FAIR-compliant RDM in NFDI-MatWerk by providing essential services and tools for the registration, structuring, and semantic enrichment of (meta)data, and by exploring the use of AI to enhance them. It supports the creation, curation and FAIRness assessment of FDOs, and interfaces to (meta)data management services like ELNs or LIMS. Together, these activities ensure the usability, accessibility, and sustainability of research data across the MSE community.

KPIs: Number of datasets registered as FDO, number of FDOs matching the quality criteria, terms and metadata profiles created and used by applications in MSE scope.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP MDI-1.1 Data registration and ingestion interfaces: This WP aims to facilitate efficient data management for the MSE users. The focus will be on modelling FDOs and on low-level services and applications to support the registration of both decentralized and federated datasets. A special case is the creation of FDOs for workflow steps as required by the node store developed in WP WLE-3. To lower the usability barrier and promote the adoption of FDOs in the community, we will develop a user-friendly graphical interface for the FDO registration, which may also incorporate AI support (related to WP MDI-1.4) and connect with centrally provided services.

[#dataQuality](#) [#solutions](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

WP MDI-1.2 (Meta)data formats: To support the standardization of data formats, this WP will develop (meta)data schemas and application profiles along with semantic mappings harmonizing individual solutions. For this, TA-MDI will continue offering services such as EVOKS [159] to create, edit, curate, and publish SKOS vocabularies and thesauri, and AIMS [160], supporting users in autonomously structuring semantic metadata profiles describing their data. This WP will stay aligned with TA-SAI (see Sec. 5.4.3, WP SAI-1.1 and WP SAI-2.1) and with Base4NFDI, particularly with their cross-domain service TS4NFDI (Terminology Services 4 NFDI).

[#dataQuality](#) [#MSEsemantics](#) [#oneNFDI](#)

WP MDI-1.3 Connection to ELNs and Workflow Environments: Recording (meta)data is becoming an integral part of workflows for data curation in experiments and in simulations (see Sec. 5.2.3, WP WLE-5 and WP WLE-6). Since the introduction of ELNs and LIMSs, users are getting familiar with the practice of structuring (meta)data entries in their research processes. TA-MDI, in close collaboration with TA-WLE (see Sec. 5.2.3, WP WLE-5), aims to enhance workflows which are and will be established in the laboratories by encouraging the parallel use of FDOs. To facilitate this integration, RO-Crate [158] has been selected as the connecting format. This choice

aligns with the ELN format specification agreed upon within the ELN consortium, which is itself based on the RO-Crate standard and supported by a wide range of ELNs [161]. By leveraging RO-Crates, (meta)data captured in ELNs can be made interoperable with the broader FDO ecosystem without requiring significant changes to established practices. [#dataQuality](#) [#solutions](#)

WP MDI-1.4 AI solutions for (meta)data management: Since [#empowerAI](#) is becoming an important topic in MSE, TA-MDI aims to enable the conversion of (meta)data for AI workflows, connected to the semantic mapping planned in WP MDI-1.2. Additionally, this WP will explore the use of AI-methods to enhance and support (meta)data management, coordinating with the LLM-related activities of TA-WLE (see Sec. 5.2.3, WP WLE-7) and TA-SAI (see Sec. 5.4.3, WP SAI-7), and it will provide ways to assess the machine actionability of data, starting from existing checklists such as the one from Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) [162]. [#dataQuality](#)

WP MDI-1.5 FAIRness assessment: TA-MDI plans to formalize a FAIRness assessment specifically tailored for FDOs. Efforts will be made to stay aligned with existing FAIR data assessment tools, like Fuji [163], which will be evaluated and either expanded or complemented with dedicated FAIRness assessment for FDOs. As an extension, the assessment will also cover the quality criteria defined within NFDI-MatWerk without sacrificing generalizability. [#dataQuality](#)

Measure MDI-2 Central Services (RWTH, KIT)

This measure focuses on hosting and operating the central MSE-KG, as well as at integrating (meta)data management services with semantic artifacts and search interfaces to enable seamless data discovery, interoperability, and reuse across NFDI-MatWerk and beyond. The measure aims to be generalizable. To reach a broad user base as directly as possible, the results of the WPs will be integrated into central services, such as Coscine.

KPIs: registered users from MSE in central services (contribution to DFG datasheet nfdi1000 number 4002), amount of data and metadata stored, number of centrally created FDOs, number of performed search queries, number of triples stored in central knowledge graph services.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP MDI-2.1 Integration of ontologies into the services: The services provided by TA-MDI for the (meta)data management are based on schemas or profiles and support the integration of semantic artifacts, e.g., the ontologies developed by TA-SAI (see Sec. 5.5.3, WP SAI-1.1) or existing controlled vocabularies, glossaries, and taxonomies. Such schemas and profiles have been and will continue to be developed in the IUCs to fulfil their requirements, so that all the relevant datasets can be described by metadata structured in the same way. Successful examples of such a work are IUC02 and IUC04. At the same time, TA-MDI will stay in close

coordination with TA-SAI to support the continuous integration of [#MSEsemantics](#) from IUCs in the provided services. [#knowledgegraph](#)

WP MDI-2.2 (Meta)data services: TA-MDI will continue to contribute to central cloud services for the storage and the management of (meta)data, such as Coscine. The application of the FDO concept will be promoted to foster interoperability and reusability of research artifacts. Therefore, the development of interfaces connecting FDOs to the (meta)data storage and management services will enhance the user experience in creating, managing, and searching research datasets represented as FDOs. Additionally, to exploit the FDOs' full potential of machine-actionability, FDO operations will be modelled and developed to aim at full machine actionability of (meta)data. [#dataQuality](#) [#empowerAI](#)

WP MDI-2.3 Search: To enable efficient data search and discovery based on metadata, SPARQL interfaces will be implemented as a core component of this measure. In contrast to the central MSE-KG, the search interfaces should respect the users' individual access permissions. At the same time, a user-friendly interface exclusively dedicated to the search of FDOs will be developed, to be used in IUCs (see, e.g., IUC02 description, Sec. 4.1.3). Furthermore, a possible connection to the Eclipse Dataspace Components of Gaia-X [164] and to the International Data Spaces [67] will be explored. [#solutions](#) [#knowledgegraph](#) [#MSEsemantics](#)

WP MDI-2.4 Hosting of the central Knowledge Graph: TA-MDI will host and operate the central MSE-KG, defining the interfaces for the management of KG entries, as well as operating and monitoring the SPARQL interface needed to interact with the KG. Compared to individual semantic (meta)data storage (see WP MDI-2.2), the KG will be provided to serve open data from the MSE community as specified by TA-SAI in MWO (see Sec. 5.4.3, WP SAI-5.1 and WP SAI-6.2) and collected by the consortium. The central KG will significantly ease entity discovery and semantic interpretation; concurrently, FDOs provide a harmonized, machine-actionable and persistent representation of various research artifacts that is interpretable without client knowledge of specific ontologies, shapes, or terms. Consequently, FDOs matching the quality criteria of NFDI-MatWerk will be harvested into the MSE-KG to leverage synergistic effects and profit of the unique advantages of both technologies. The tasks will be carried out in close collaboration with TA-SAI (see Sec. 5.4.3, WP SAI-5.3) and with HMC. [#knowledgegraph](#)

Measure MDI-3 Support and Outreach (*RUB, KIT, RWTH*)

This measure ensures the effective dissemination, monitoring, and continuous development of TA-MDI services in close collaboration with other TAs, PPs, and IUCs. It encompasses not only internal coordination and external communication, but also requirement analysis and user feedback processes, user support and training, documentation and tutorials, as well as contribution to the service architecture and reference applications.

KPIs: Number of educational events contributed to.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP MDI-3.1 Coordination: The coordination within TA-MDI and the communication within the consortium, to the IUCs, as well as to Base4NFDI and the NFDI Sections Common Infrastructures and (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance is covered in this work package. [#oneNFDI](#)

WP MDI-3.2 Requirement Analysis and Feedback: For the community-based improvement of TA-MDI services, it will be necessary to perform a requirement analysis of the IUCs and regular feedback rounds, as it was done, e.g., in IUC02. To ensure that these interactions will be productive, a bridge between developers and scientists will be essential. This so-called “hinge function”, will effectively translate scientific needs into concrete software requirements, acting as a translator and connector between the MSE community and the TA, ensuring that both perspectives are aligned. [#solutions](#) [#roll-out](#)

WP MDI-3.3 Knowledge Base and Dissemination: TA-MDI complements the work of TA-CI on the content of the website, listing and maintaining the description of the provided (meta)data services, including documentation, tutorials, and videos. Future contributions will focus on showing the MSE scientists how to best use the offered tools in their scientific context. [#roll-out](#)

WP MDI-3.4 Support: To maximize the usability and impact of the developed solutions across the MSE community, TA-MDI will provide the users with support in various forms: by assisting TA-CI during the implementation of the helpdesk (see Sec. 5.1.3, WP CI-3), by contributing to the roll-out of the solutions (see Sec. 5.1.3, WP CI-9), or by participating as instructors at individual workshops. Coordinated by TA-CI, TA-MDI will offer support and training material on the developed (meta)data management services (see Sec. 5.1.3, WP CI-1), as well as data stewards who will assist users and refer them to appropriate resources, based on their individual requirements. [#roll-out](#)

WP MDI-3.5 Harmonization of Services: For the long-term success of NFDI-MatWerk, a solid technological foundation and an extensible architecture are essential. For this reason, technical and infrastructural components were organized into a structured portfolio of software, services, and tools (see Sec. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). As the technological ecosystem is evolving, this architecture demands continuous expansions, adaptations, and maintenance. To coordinate these efforts and to ensure the integration of the Base4NFDI components, a cross-TA architecture group has been established (see Sec. 3.4). TA-MDI will actively participate in the architecture group, regularly providing insights from the infrastructure point of view. [#oneNFDI](#)

WP MDI-3.6 Reference Applications: TA-MDI, coordinated by TA-CI, will focus on a gradual outreach, onboarding, and [#roll-out](#) strategy to engage an increasing number of PPs and IUCs (see WP CI-9). This approach will include the targeted integration and prototyping of interfaces and applications in different IUCs. TA-MDI will work closely with domain experts and end-users in a process allowing for iterative refinements, to ensure that the technological [#solutions](#) will be developed and customized in alignment with the specific requirements.

WP MDI-3.7 Monitoring and Data Usage Analytics: The monitoring of registered data and service usage will be essential for maintaining transparency, ensuring sustainability, and guiding the strategic development of the NFDI-MatWerk infrastructure. Understanding the usage statistics of tools will provide valuable insights into user needs, adoption patterns, and potential areas for improvement. For this reason, TA-MDI will regularly monitor the usage of the offered (meta)data management services, as well as the amount of (meta)data processed or registered. This will include collecting aggregated data on service access.

5.3.4 Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives

The **ICAMS** (Interdisciplinary Centre for Advanced Materials Simulation) at Ruhr-Universität Bochum, develops and applies multiscale simulation tools for advanced materials. It is on the forefront of a paradigm change to data-driven multiscale materials modelling, which is based on materials data and trained ML models rather than by quasi-empirical rules. Co-Applicant **Prof. Dr. A. Hartmaier** is professor for mechanics of materials and director of the department Micromechanical and Macroscopic Modeling. His research focuses on micromechanical and scale-bridging modeling of deformation, fracture, and fatigue, as well as ML-based methods for mechanical systems. In NFDI-MatWerk's previous phase, he contributed to IUC 07 on data formats and workflows for spatiotemporal microstructure evolution.

The **SCC** (Scientific Computing Center) [165] is the computing and data centre of KIT. With GridKa [166], SCC is responsible for the storage and analysis of about 15% of the data generated at the LHC [167] at CERN. SCC also operates HoreKa [168], a 27 PetaFlop/s supercomputer, part of NHR. Co-Applicant **Prof. Dr. A. Streit** is SCC director and professor for "Distributed and Parallel High-Performance Systems". His expertise and research focus lies in data management as well as distributed & federated computing. In NFDI, he is member of the steering board of NFDI-MatWerk and NFDI4Ing as well as member of the TEC (Technical Evaluation Committee) in Base4NFDI [169]. Through continuous contributions in RDA [170], EUDAT-CDI [171], AARC2 [172], NFFA Europe, and several EOSC-projects and NFDI consortia, SCC has been at the core of data infrastructure services and policy developments in Germany and in Europe.

Co-Applicant **Prof. M. S. Müller** is head of the Chair for High Performance Computing, director of the **IT Center of RWTH Aachen University**, on the Management Board of NHR4CES, the Board of Directors of JARA-CSD (Jülich Aachen Research Alliance Center for Simulation and

Data Science) [173] and of NHR. His research interests include programming methodologies, software development tools and computational science on HPC. Co-Applicant **Dr. M.Politze** is head of the department Research Process and Data Management at the IT Center of RWTH. His research focuses on Semantic Web, Linked Data, and architectures for distributed and service-oriented systems. He is Co-Spokesperson of the IAM4NFDI basic service and Speaker for the WGs IAM and OA of the Section Common Infrastructures. Within his department, he is responsible for local RDM support at RWTH and national RDM services Coscine and DataStorage.nrw.

5.3.5 Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases

TA-MDI will contribute to the IUCs by providing the (meta)data management services to support the implementation of the FAIR principles. The scientific use cases introduced by the participating PPs will serve as the basis for applying and tailoring these services to meet specific research needs. These activities will be carried out in close coordination with TA-SAI to ensure that the semantic developments remain aligned with the underlying technical infrastructure.

IUC02: From the RDM perspective, this IUC provides a concept to shape MSE datasets into exemplary reference datasets (which already include research datasets) as FDOs. To make it possible in a user-friendly way, the development of a graphical interface for the FDO registration is envisioned. The data schemas provided by the PPs are employed to develop the JSON metadata schema and the semantic representation. The concepts of data quality, along with data structuring, interoperability, findability, and reusability, are applied. This makes IUC02 an important use case to implement the FAIR principles and to provide a framework for generating and distributing reference datasets. Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC04: IUC04 is connected to TA-MDI as it uses the S3 storage in Coscine as storage for openBIS. It is accessed directly through the Amazon Toolkit.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC07: In this IUC, data structures and workflows to handle the spatiotemporal evolution of microstructures during thermomechanical materials processing will be formulated and implemented in form of a toolbox for the community. The aim of this IUC is to render such time-dependent microstructural data into FDO by applying a semantic description of microstructural features defined in a widely accepted data schema.

IUC20: This IUC provides an ontology for the description of physical samples, tested in the context of Electron Microscopy, enabling reproducibility and semantic interoperability in experimental workflows. The knowledge representation provided by the ontology should remain closely aligned with users, keeping a balance between their practical needs and a FAIR-compliant structure. This is intended to be achieved with continuous feedback and iterative refinement. From

the infrastructure perspective, this IUC provides an exemplary case study of a vocabulary service to store, manage, and access-controlled vocabularies.

5.4 Task Area Semantics and Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI)

5.4.1 Status of this Task Area's Field in MSE

Figure 13: Logo of Task Area Semantics and Artificial Intelligence (TA-SAI)

The importance of semantic technologies in MSE has become widely acknowledged across national and international communities. This shift is driven by the need to ensure interoperability and FAIR compliance across heterogeneous data sources. Ontologies are becoming essential infrastructure for machine-actionable (meta)data in the MSE community.

Several ontology initiatives have emerged in the MSE landscape, with a growing interest in developing interoperable and extensible models. Among these, the PMD Core Ontology (PMDco) [174] plays a pivotal role as a mid-level ontology tailored to the MSE domain. Integrated with the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) [175], PMDco facilitates cross-domain interoperability. Supported by NFDI-MatWerk and PMD, an increasing number of research groups in Germany have developed domain and application-level semantics. At the European level, the EMMC has continued to advance the Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology (EMMO) [176], which is now adopted by multiple communities.

Despite these advances, the adoption of ontologies in MSE remains challenging. The field is inherently interdisciplinary, and development is further complicated by the need to represent multiscale phenomena and evolving materials processes. As a result, semantic artefacts must balance formal precision with the flexibility required by domain scientists.

In summary, while a variety of ontologies now exist, a unified, interoperable semantic infrastructure for MSE is still evolving. NFDI-MatWerk continues to play a key role by filling semantic gaps, aligning existing artefacts, and coordinating with national and international initiatives, while also leveraging AI methods such as large language models to support metadata generation, semantic annotation and ontology engineering.

5.4.2 General Objectives of the Task Area

TA-SAI aims to build an open, extensible semantic foundation for describing materials, processes, simulations, and experiments across MSE subdomains. Addressing the inherent complexity of materials data, which spans multiple length and time scales, is key to enabling data reuse, integration, and automation across scientific workflows. Building on the achievements of the first

funding phase, the TA now focuses on the further developing, consolidating, and deploying of semantic artefacts that reflect the full range of MSE research. The main objectives are:

- I. To **develop domain and application ontologies in MSE** that contribute to the extension and alignment of a modular, community-driven ontology architecture. This objective supports bottom-up schema and terminology development in collaboration with the IUCs. The resulting semantic artefacts are grounded in research workflows and are designed to flexibly incorporate scale-bridging concepts across diverse domains.
- II. To establish a **central semantic infrastructure**, semantics the MatWerk Ontology (MWO) [57] and the MSE Knowledge Graph (MSE-KG) [133]. Together, they provide harmonized, mid-level semantics and act as a unifying layer for the diverse ontologies developed across NFDI-MatWerk. The MSE-KG aims to improve web-based access, findability, and integration of heterogeneous materials data.

To achieve these objectives, TA-SAI focuses on the following strategic activities:

- Active collaboration with other NFDI consortia and contributions to the broader NFDI ecosystem, particularly through alignment with NFDIcore ontology development and integration of NFDI-MatWerk's semantic infrastructure [177].
- Enabling semantic interoperability across national and international initiatives, including MaterialDigital, EMMC, and global efforts coordinated through the RDA and EOSC.
- Exploration of AI-driven methods, particularly large language models, to support knowledge extraction, metadata handling, and ontology development. The goal is to reduce the effort for domain experts and improve accessibility of semantic technologies.
- Fostering a cultural shift toward the use of semantic standards in the MSE community by demonstrating clear benefits to domain scientists and rolling out of practical solutions.

The schematic in Figure 14 illustrates how semantic technologies, developed within TA-SAI, are integrated into scientific workflows and data infrastructures to produce FAIR-compliant, interoperable (meta)data, ultimately enabling linked data discovery through the MSE-KG.

Figure 14: Schematic overview of the semantic infrastructure in NFDI-MatWerk.

By combining technical development with broad community engagement, TA-SAI serves as an enabler of FAIR data practices within NFDI-MatWerk. Its work is central to ensuring long-term interoperability, sustainability, and impact across the materials science data ecosystem.

5.4.3 Measures and Work Packages

Measure SAI-1 Development of domain and application ontologies in MSE (FZJ, UFR)

This measure focuses on developing and extending ontologies for materials description, with an emphasis on microstructure and scale-bridging representations. It supports use-case-driven ontology development, including the alignment with external initiatives, and demonstrators to showcase practical integration of heterogeneous data. [#MSEsemantics](#) [#solutions](#)

KPIs: number of semantic resources developed, number of semantic resources integrated into data pipelines

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-1.1 Ontology design for materials description: The focus is the development and refinement of ontological components for describing materials, description of microstructure and the representation across length and time scales. Building on the Ontology for Crystallographic Defects (OCDO) [124], the aim is to provide a unified, semantic framework for representing microstructural features observed in both experiments and simulations. This WP also includes support for the development of additional ontology modules from IUCs, ensuring that evolving community needs are addressed. To ensure alignment between semantic artefacts and metadata infrastructure, these activities will be closely coordinated with the developments in TA-MDI, in particular 5.3.3 WP MDI-1.2 and WP MDI-2.1.

WP SAI-1.2 Semantic alignment and interoperability of MSE ontologies: To ensure compatibility beyond NFDI-MatWerk, MSE ontologies will be aligned and harmonized with broader initiatives such as EMMC, MaterialDigital, and upper-level frameworks like the Basic Formal Ontology [175]. This semantic alignment will facilitate cross-domain data exchange and integration, improving interoperability with external platforms and infrastructures.

WP SAI-1.3 Demonstrators for ontology-based data integration: A set of demonstrators will showcase how the developed ontologies enable the integration of heterogeneous data. Selected based on IUC needs, the demonstrators will focus on terminologies linking processes, microstructure, and properties. These use cases will highlight how ontological annotation improves data discoverability and enables advanced semantic querying, while serving as testbeds to assess the completeness and value of the models.

WP SAI-1.4 Support for community integration of semantic resources: In close coordination with TA-CI (see 5.1.3, WP CI-5 and CI-9), this WP supports the roll-out of domain and application-

level ontologies, along with associated demonstrators. It includes the application of semantic mappings in metadata records and related artefacts, such as metadata descriptions in ELNs. The focus is on enabling researchers within to integrate ontologies into their RDM workflows, through guidance and hands-on materials tailored to MSE. [#roll-out](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

Measure SAI-2 Semantic and data quality assessment (FZJ, UFR)

Reliable semantic artefacts are essential for data interoperability and quality in the MSE domain. This measure focuses on establishing a curated ontology collection of openly developed semantic resources across use cases and apply structured evaluation methods to assess coverage and FAIR compliance. It also links semantic annotations to data quality metrics, supporting the consistent and trustworthy use of MSE data. The main aim is to develop and curate a semantic map of MSE information to support interoperability and help users find suitable ontologies and schemas to describe their research data. [#MSEsemantics](#) [#dataQuality](#)

KPIs: number of semantic resources curated and evaluated.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-2.1 Collection and curation of MSE ontologies: A collection of materials science ontologies will be established and maintained, serving as a shared semantic resource for the NFDI-MatWerk community. The collection will be hosted on a stable platform, such as the TIB Terminology Service [178], or on services provided by TA-MDI (see 5.3.3, WP MDI-1.2). This collection should include persistent identifiers, rich metadata and specific metrics defined in WP SAI-2.3. Curation workflows will follow recommendations from TS4NFDI, ensuring versioning, quality control, and traceability of updates.

WP SAI-2.2 Harmonization and alignment of MSE semantic artefacts: This WP focuses on aligning ontologies and other semantic artefacts used in different application domains and IUCs, as well as the top-level alignment with BFO [175], following the guidelines developed in WP SAI-4.4. The aim is to develop an open semantic framework, ensuring consistent modelling of materials entities, processes, and properties.

WP SAI-2.3 Ontology evaluation from domain and FAIR perspective: Ontologies will be evaluated using structured criteria to assess both their domain relevance and compliance with FAIR principles. The evaluation will be based on the Semantic Artefact Assessment Methodology developed in the EOSC context [179]. Tools such as FOOPS! [180] and O'FAIRe [181] will be used to support this process, as well as the ontology quality metrics defined in WP SAI-4.3, and the recommendations of the RDA Working Group on "Harmonised Terminologies and Schemas for FAIR Data in Materials Science" [64]. The WP will also include an assessment of how comprehensively an ontology represents its target domain. [#eosc](#)

WP SAI-2.4 Ontology-based data quality assessment: This WP assess dataset quality through semantic annotations and associated metadata. By leveraging ontologies, key aspects can be evaluated such as completeness, coverage, and consistency across datasets and repositories. It supports identifying issues such as inconsistent terminology use, missing values in annotated properties, or schema mismatches. These evaluations aim to improve the usability of MSE research data. [#dataQuality](#)

Measure SAI-3 Ontology integration in computational workflows (FZJ)

This measure focuses on embedding semantic technologies into computational materials science by developing ontologies and tools that annotate, and link simulation data and workflows. It enables consistent representation of modelling methods across scales, integration with workflow engines, and the construction of materials simulation knowledge graphs.

KPIs: Number of triples in the knowledge graph, number of downloads of developed tools (DFG datasheet nfdi1000 numbers: 5).

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-3.1 Semantic description of computational methods: Ontological models will be developed to describe materials simulations across atomistic, mesoscopic, and continuum scales, capturing both the physical models and their computational implementations. Building on the Computational Materials Sample Ontology (CMSO) [125] and Atomistic Simulation Methods Ontology (ASMO) [126], the scope will be extended to represent multiscale workflows. The descriptions will also cover AI/ML workflows used for surrogate modelling, property prediction, or microstructure analysis. [#MSEsemantics](#)

WP SAI-3.2 Integration with simulation workflows: In collaboration with TA-WLE, ontologies will be coupled with simulation data pipelines to enable semantic annotation of input parameters, processing steps, and outputs. The approach used in the *atomRDF* python library [17] originally developed for annotating crystal structures and atomistic workflows, will be extended to cover other modelling domains. This integration supports interoperability between simulation tools and simplifies tracking of provenance, enhancing reproducibility and cross-software compatibility in multiscale modelling. [#solutions](#)

WP SAI-3.3 Knowledge graph for materials simulations: A knowledge graph infrastructure will be established to represent and interlink semantically annotated simulation data. Using RDF as the underlying framework, simulation outputs and metadata will be integrated across methods and projects. It will expose a public SPARQL endpoint to support advanced querying and provide an API layer to facilitate programmatic access and integration with external tools and platforms. [#knowledgegraph](#)

WP SAI-3.4 Interoperability with external materials databases: Semantic interfaces to established materials databases will be developed, such as the NOMAD repository [45], Materials Project [182], AFLOW [183] or the Alexandria database [184]. Ontology mappings and data pipelines will be developed to harmonize schema-level representations and enable automated data exchange. The goal is to allow users to access external databases and integrate third-party data directly into their workflows. [#knowledgegraph](#)

WP SAI-3.5 Generalized software solutions for handling RDF data: In cooperation with TA-WLE, the aim is to develop reusable software for handling RDF data. A key focus is on enabling the programmatic composition of SPARQL queries, building on the development of tools4RDF from the first funding phase [185]. The goal is to lower the barrier for MSE users to adopt semantic technologies in their workflows. [#solutions](#)

Measure SAI-4 Interoperable and community-driven MWO ontology ecosystem (FIZ)

This measure aims to build a consistent, interoperable ecosystem of BFO-aligned domain ontology that supports semantic integration and cross-domain data interoperability within NFDI-MatWerk. Community-driven practices, including shared guidelines, collaborative curation, and ongoing support, will empower application ontology developers across use cases to contribute to and benefit from a unified semantic framework. [#MSEsemantics](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

KPIs: Number of contributed educational media resources.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-4.1 Enrichment and cross-domain integration of MWO: The activity includes developing ontology design patterns, shortcuts, and simplifications in the domain-level MatWerk Ontology (MWO) [186] to improve user-friendliness and streamline the creation of application ontologies. It covers the addition of community-driven concepts, such as those needed for integrating application ontologies and meeting knowledge graph requirements. Further goals include continuous harmonizing MWO with related top- and mid-level ontologies like PMDco and NFDIcore and ensuring interoperability with other NFDI ontologies.

WP SAI-4.2 Enhance interoperability and BFO alignment of application ontologies: To ensure usability and interoperability of ontologies across different (sub-)domains, this WP aims to support ontology developers to integrate their application ontologies with BFO [175], NFDIcore [177], PMDco [174,187], and MWO [186]. The activity will be conducted in close collaboration with experts involved in ontology development across different PPs (see WP SAI-2.2).

WP SAI-4.3 Evaluation and quality assurance of BFO-based ontologies: Ontology evaluation for MWO and BFO-aligned application ontologies (see WP SAI-2.3) includes defining clear evaluation criteria based on established quality metrics such as completeness, consistency,

clarity, and reusability [188]. A combination of expert reviews and automated tools (e.g., OntoQA) is used to assess logical soundness and modelling accuracy [189]. Validation is carried out using measuring reasoning efficiency and responses to competency questions and SPARQL queries. Continuous integration pipelines are implemented to automate testing, reasoning checks, query execution, and change tracking.

WP SAI-4.4 Community-driven BFO-aligned ontology development guideline: This WP focuses on developing comprehensive guidelines for developing BFO-based ontologies. It will provide best practices for creating application ontologies, standardizing the documentation and versioning of application ontologies using the Ontology Development Kit [109], and conducting ontology evaluation and reasoning. The WP will actively support PPs and IUCs in developing compliant ontologies by offering training materials disseminated in WP SAI-8.

Measure SAI-5 Semantic integration and enrichment of the MSE-KG (FIZ)

This measure focuses on the continued development and enrichment of the Materials Science and Engineering Knowledge Graph (MSE-KG) as a central semantic infrastructure within NFDI-MatWerk [190]. [#knowledgegraph](#)

KPIs: Number of triples in the knowledge graph.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-5.1 Community-driven MSE-KG population and enrichment: The MSE-KG will be further populated with rich metadata and structured information from the community, including consortium structures, tools, software, workflows, publications, datasets, services, KPIs, and MSE-specific content such as materials, devices, properties, and processes. In close collaboration with IUCs and PPs, the Linked Open Data (LOD) working group (WP SAI-8.4) will develop a digital pipeline for streamlined metadata curation and MSE-KG integration [191]. A sustainable interface for KG management will be developed with TA-MDI to support automated and efficient population workflows (see 5.3.3, WP MDI-2.4). Finally, IUC inputs will be utilized to demonstrate the added value of KGs for the MSE domain.

WP SAI-5.2 Collaborative integration of PMD data into the MSE-KG: To foster long-term accessibility and reuse of data produced by the PMD initiative, This WP collaborates with PMD consortia to streamline metadata collection and integrate it into the MSE-KG. The considered data will be collected from PMD-KG [192], PMD data portal [193] as well as data repositories of the individuals funded projects.

WP SAI-5.3 Integrating MSE repositories, FDOs, and authority resources in KG: This WP aims to enrich the MSE-KG by integrating MSE-related data repositories and platforms that provide structured materials metadata, like NOMAD [45] and MatPortal [194]. It also focuses on

integrating FDOs into the MSE-KG in close collaboration with TA-MDI (see 5.3.3, WP MDI-2.4) and HMC. Furthermore, authority resources such as Wikidata and ORCID will be linked to the MSE-KG to strengthen metadata quality in the MSE domain. The most demanding tasks of this WP will be the MWO alignment of metadata, developing robust RDF conversion pipelines, and preparation of exemplary SPARQL queries to allow users to find and reuse the mentioned resources through the MSE-KG interfaces.

WP SAI-5.4 Assessment and alignment of inter- and cross-domain KGs: This WP evaluates existing MSE-related and cross-domain KGs (e.g. MatKG [195], NIST's materials data infrastructures [196], MaterialsMine [197], Helmholtz KG [198], ORKG [199]) to assess their compatibility with the MSE-KG. The objective is to assess the feasibility of linking these KGs through analysing ontology alignment, shared entities, RDF compliance, and technical challenges. This WP also supports linking the MSE-KG with KGI4NFDI (a Base4NFDI project) [200] to foster interoperability within the NFDI ecosystem.

WP SAI-5.5 Scholarly data extraction for MSE-KG: This WP focuses on extracting basic metadata from scientific literature (like authors, affiliations, materials studied, experimental methods, and reported properties) to populate the MSE-KG [201]. More complex, LLM-supported KG population approaches will be explored in WP SAI-7.

Measure SAI-6 Knowledge graph group support (FIZ)

This measure highlights the supporting roles and tasks of TA-SAI within the KG group, focusing on enabling seamless access, interaction, and integration of the MSE-KG. These efforts aim to significantly enhance the visibility, and sustainability of the MSE-KG, thereby extending its potential as an interoperable resource for the MSE research community. [#knowledgegraph](#)

KPIs: Number of performed search queries to the knowledge graph.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-6.1 MSE-KG frontend development and semantic interaction support: This WP focuses on the implementation of an interactive and user-friendly web interface for the MSE-KG. TA-CI will lead the development of the frontend interface, and TA-SAI will support this effort through three key aspects of visualization, query and exploration, and interaction support.

WP SAI-6.2 MSE-KG infrastructure operation and hosting support: This WP focuses on the operation and hosting infrastructure of the MSE-KG. TA-MDI will lead the technical operation and ensure reliable hosting of the MSE-KG (see 5.3.3, WP MDI-2.4), and TA-SAI will define the functional requirements of the interfaces for managing the MSE-KG entries, as well as design of a metadata delivery pipeline and a data registry service. TA-SAI will also specify the needs for SPARQL endpoint operation and seamless integration of the MSE-KG with external tools and

platforms. TA-MDI and TA-SAI will also work collaboratively on integrating FDOs into the MSE-KG (see WP SAI-5.3 and WP MDI-1.3).

WP SAI-6.3 Semantic descriptions for ELN and MSE-KG synchronization: As part of TA-WLE's effort to connect entries in ELNs to the MSE-KG (WLE-5), TA-SAI will contribute by developing semantic representations of ELN elements and their relevant metadata within MWO. This includes establishing a mapping pipeline between ELN data fields and MWO concepts, generating RDF triples, integrating them into the MSE-KG, and enabling data discovery and aggregation through SPARQL queries.

Measure SAI-7 Leverage LLMs for data extraction and exploration (FZJ, DFKI, FIZ, UFR)

This measure tackles the challenge of integrating unstructured scientific information by combining large language models (LLMs) with domain ontologies. It aims to improve semantic descriptions, and enable intuitive, ontology-driven access to data. [#empowerAI](#)

KPIs: Number of datasets enriched or linked via LLM-supported pipelines, number of semantic resources generated or improved with LLM-based tools.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-7.1 Information extraction from literature for data integration (FZJ, UFR): Information will be extracted from scientific literature to enhance the description of materials data relevant to selected systems covered within the IUCs. By supplementing existing datasets with literature-derived content, this work aims to improve semantic coverage and create stronger links between distributed data sources. The result will be more interconnected and contextualised materials knowledge, supporting both reuse and discovery.

WP SAI-7.2 Semantic enrichment of datasets (FZJ, UFR): Existing datasets will be semantically enriched by mapping metadata and content to established MSE ontologies. Where needed, domain-specific terminology will be extended to cover emerging concepts. Resulting descriptions will be instantiated as RDF, supporting integration into knowledge graphs and enabling ontology-based queries and reasoning.

WP SAI-7.3 Support activities for improving metadata records (FZJ, UFR): This work package focuses on applying LLMs to improve and generate metadata records for publications and datasets. From a predefined set of metadata keys, LLMs will assist in identifying appropriate ontology terms and completing metadata fields. Outputs will contribute directly to the construction and population of materials knowledge graphs.

WP SAI-7.4 Knowledge extraction infrastructure (DFKI, FZJ, UFR): For the purpose of empowering the MSE community, in this WPs, LLM-based tools will be developed, including

pipelines for data ingestion, ontology, metadata mapping and RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation). This WP is closely connected to 5.2.3 TA-WLE WP 7.

WP SAI-7.5 Demonstrator for data exploration (DFKI, FZJ, UFR): A demonstrator will be developed to showcase advanced querying and exploration capabilities across semantically linked datasets. Users will be able to pose natural language queries to explore chemical and configurational spaces or retrieve specific material properties. The demonstrator will illustrate how LLMs and ontologies can support intuitive access to distributed materials data. It will be developed based on the user-centred design methodology for the demonstrator to be useable for everyone.

WP SAI-7.6 LLM for BFO-compliant ontology development (FIZ): Extraction of domain-relevant concepts, relations, and entities from curated textual resources is followed by applying LLMs to support a machine-assisted process for developing application ontologies. The extracted knowledge is formalized into structured ontologies using established design patterns and aligned with MWO to ensure semantic consistency and interoperability.

Measure SAI-8: MSE Semantics Dissemination and Education (FZJ, FIZ)

This measure promotes the adoption, and reuse of ontologies and knowledge graphs across the MSE community. It supports users through training, outreach, helpdesk services, and structured collaboration, both within NFDI and internationally. Activities are closely coordinated with TA-CI to ensure alignment with training formats and community-facing efforts.

KPIs: Number of contributed educational media resources, number of events and participants.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SAI-8.1 Training materials for ontology use in MSE: Comprehensive training materials will be developed to support the understanding and practical application of MSE ontologies. These resources will include hands-on examples and interactive notebooks that show how ontologies can be integrated into research workflows. Designed to meet the needs of users at different experience levels, from beginners to advanced, the materials will be openly accessible and specifically tailored to the MSE community.

WP SAI-8.2 Helpdesk and website support: Coordinated by TA-CI, a structured support service (helpdesk) will be established to assist users with questions related to ontologies and metadata, guiding them to relevant documentation and solutions. In parallel, content will be developed and maintained for the metadata and semantics section of the NFDI-MatWerk website, including relevant tools and ontology collections. This WP also includes support for communication activities (see 5.1.3, WP CI-2).

WP SAI-8.3 Dissemination and participation in community events: To maximize outreach, content about semantics will be integrated into NFDI-MatWerk workshops and training activities led by TA-CI. The team will also participate in events organized by other consortia, the NFDI, as well as domain-specific conferences. Key efforts include co-organizing international events focused on semantic technologies in MSE.

WP SAI-8.4 Best practice guidelines for ontology development: Contributions will be made to the development of best practice guidelines that focus on ontology use, development, and maintenance in MSE. Additionally, the Linked Open Data Working Group (LOD-WG) [202] aims to provide educational resources and dissemination services to aid PPs overcome obstacles in implementing LOD. The group supports the development of pipelines for metadata curation and integration into MSE-KG.

WP SAI-8.5 Inter-consortia, national and international collaboration: The development of semantic infrastructure in NFDI-MatWerk takes place within a broader ecosystem of related efforts across different communities. To ensure interoperability and reuse, this WP supports coordination with parallel developments. Collaboration with national efforts such as the NFDI and PMD, as well as international efforts, the RDA and EMMC, ensures NFDI-MatWerk remains technically compatible and visible to the evolving data landscape.

5.4.4 Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives

Prof. Dr. Stefan Sandfeld is the director of the IAS (Institute for Advanced Simulation) – Materials Data Science and Informatics (IAS-9) at Forschungszentrum Jülich and Chair of Materials Data Science at RWTH Aachen University. He leads national and international efforts to integrate semantic technologies, scientific ML, and AI into materials research. He has served since 2019 as Chairman of the Expert Committee “Materials Modelling, Simulation and Data” of the German Materials Society (DGM) and serves as speaker of strategic initiatives such as the Helmholtz project SOL-AI [203], focusing on a foundation model to accelerate photovoltaic materials research. He also serves as co-lead of the Rhine-Ruhr Center for Scientific Data Literacy (DKZ.2R). Since 2022, he serves as FZJ representative in the council of the CECAM (Centre Européen de Calcul Atomique et Moléculaire) [204], further reflecting his integration in the European computational materials community.

Prof. Dr. Harald Sack is Vice-President of Information Service Engineering at FIZ Karlsruhe and professor of Information Services Engineering at FIZ Karlsruhe and the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology's Institute of AIFB (Applied Informatics and Formal Description Methods) [205]. FIZ strengthens the connection between NFDI and EOSC projects by linking data and services from both ecosystems. Prof. Sack is a charter member and general secretary of the German IPv6 Council, and a member of the SWSA (Semantic Web Science Association) [206] and has served as program committee member of more than 120 international conferences and workshops in

Semantic Web, Knowledge Representation and Knowledge Mining. He has conducted very successful MOOCs with the Open HPI (Hasso Plattner Institute for IT Systems Engineering) Teaching platform (e.g. 2023 Knowledge Graphs - Foundations and Applications) [207].

Prof. Dr. Antonio Krüger is CEO and scientific director of the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence GmbH (DFKI) and head of the department “Cognitive Assistants” at DFKI. He is a full professor for Computer Science at Saarland University. Prof. Krueger is an internationally renowned expert on Man-Machine-Interaction and AI. His expertise in translating cutting-edge AI research into practical systems, is highly relevant to the integration of LLMs and semantic infrastructure in materials science.

5.4.5 Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases

The IUCs serve two main purposes: (i) provide domain-specific scenarios that guide the ontology development, and (ii) apply semantic technologies within research workflows to enhance data interoperability and support the implementation of the FAIR principles. This interaction ensures that developments within TA-SAI remains aligned with the practical needs of the MSE community. The following highlights the relevance of selected IUCs for TA-SAI:

IUC12: This IUC demonstrates how semantic alignment between domain-specific and upper-level ontologies enables interoperability between heterogeneous data sources. The IUC addresses key challenges in semantics: managing alignment across evolving ontologies and reuse of ontologies in metadata schemas. Here, interaction with FAIRmat and PMD is planned.

IUC13: The use case develops a co-creation environment for semantic assets based on OpenSemanticLab [142]. This will enable users to create MWO-compliant objects with a few code lines, GUI or a chatbot and store them in the KG. The user interface provides low-threshold access through interactive visualizations, filterable tables and detailed views on linked data.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC17: This use case supports TA-SAI, providing use-case-driven input for the development and validation of ontologies describing crystalline defects across scales and methods. It contributes to the Open Crystallographic Defect Ontologies [124] and the alignment with broader semantic frameworks. PPs provide domain expertise and research data to test and refine ontology instantiation and KG development within scientific workflows.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC18: This IUC contributes data-driven workflows for semantic representation of Composition-Process-Structure-Property (CPSP) relationships. It demonstrates how ontologies and metadata can be integrated in inverse design pipelines and ML workflows. The resulting infrastructure supports automation and interoperability in data-centric materials science.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

IUC20: This IUC provides an ontology for the description of physical samples, tested in the context of Electron Microscopy. Alignment with existing standards (PRIMA ontology [208], EM Glossary [138]) is planned. The ontology links sample descriptions to processing and measurement data, supporting provenance tracking, and facilitating the reuse of procedures across facilities. It enables the integration of structured metadata with analysis pipelines, ensuring that the data is ready for AI-based methods.

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

5.5 Task Area Strategy Development (TA-SD)

Figure 15: Logo of Task Area Strategy Development (TA-SD)

5.5.1 Status of this Task Area's Field in MSE

The digital transformation in science is ongoing and its opportunities become gradually visible and accessible to scientists: a fundamental readiness to commit to novel unified ways for its advancements can be witnessed in the MSE community which is also confirmed by the feedback and support demonstrated in our surveys in 2020 and 2024 [209]. Still, challenges of the digital transformation and the need for RDM solutions can be

observed: Before NFDI-MatWerk started, researchers often reacted pragmatically by developing their own hands-on solutions for challenges that sometimes result in an advantage within the competitive field of science. This caused decentralised and inconsistent solutions towards RDM within parts of our community. Obviously, this is far from what is necessary to fulfil FAIR principles. The transformation towards a FAIR data future needs the openness also from the users (e.g. the researchers) for continuously proceeding developments including adapting MSE research data handling, selecting, testing and implementing newly developed solutions and commitment to participate in the ongoing movement for FAIR MSE RDM pushed forward by NFDI-MatWerk. The NFDI-MatWerk consortium nurtures this development as it will only be successful when a strong community commitment is available. It also means that the implementation of the NFDI in the materials community is a pressing matter, since community support can be lost when central platforms and projects are stalled.

5.5.2 General Objectives of the Task Area

The NFDI initiative paves the way for a vastly more comprehensive shift in science than the mere establishment of an infrastructure. Tomorrow's scientific methods will diverge in many ways from today's reality, e.g. by the new possibilities and demands with and by AI. This paradigm shift brought by the digital transformation in science will need to go much deeper than just data

harmonization or common metadata schemas. For NFDI-MatWerk, the NFDI movements is more than a technocratic initiative for data handling. It is an enormous change in the possibilities of research processes and knowledge generation. Thus, NFDI-MatWerk needs a dedicated strategy for user-centric and -driven developments, community engagement incentivization and more.

As in any well-managed organization, such an elaborated strategy should address the overall challenges from different viewpoints and ensure a harmonized target implementation. In the first funding period, the focus of the TA was mainly on organizational development, ensuring goal-oriented collaboration and co-creation between TAs and PPs, information exchange and overall governance. In the second funding period, the focus will broaden and will implement a portfolio management for a consistent user-oriented decision and development process for infrastructure solutions and a stronger interaction with the TA-CI to foster outside communication along the NFDI-MatWerk strategy and for roll-out processes. The general objectives are:

- Evolution of transparent processes and governance for community-driven decision-making.
- Ensure relevance by closely involving the scientific community into the infrastructure's development process.
- Develop and integrate portfolio management processes to integrate user needs and foresight results into development decisions.
- Further develop processes to monitor the readiness of solutions for roll-out
- Further develop monitoring and feedback procedures for the community.
- Align a consistent communication strategy with the general NFDI-MatWerk strategy
- Further develop and transfer today's mechanisms for incentives and good scientific practice into the digital realm for a successful change process.
- Connect to other RDM efforts, nationally and internationally.

Monitoring the forementioned challenges greatly improves the chance for a successful infrastructure implementation, independently of its technological advancement: If the MSE community's needs are considered and met, then general acceptance will be high and the overall goal of the NFDI will be achieved. However, this requires an environment, in which the community is ready for such a close interaction and contributes the necessary time investments.

5.5.3 Measures and Work Packages

Measure SD-1: Organizational Development (*IWM, UFR*)

This measure ensures the continuous development and adaptation of organisational structures, roles and responsibilities according to the changing needs of the community and the project team.

[#DigiTrans](#) [#dataQuality](#) [#roll-out](#) [#solutions](#)

KPIs: Number of applications for FlexFunds, ratio of number of datasets fulfilling the quality criteria to number of datasets provided by the consortium, number of actors/communities/institutions newly integrated since the proposal was submitted

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SD-1.1 Concepts for an organization that translates needs into infrastructure: TA-SD continuously monitors and refines the project's organisational structure to ensure it adequately reflects the community's evolving needs. This includes analysing collaboration layers (e.g. TAs, IUCs, cross-functional teams like the architecture group) and implementing supporting mechanisms such as the creation of new working groups (e.g. roll-out group), enhancing communication structures, and refining roles.

WP SD-1.2 Processes for community participation in strategy and product portfolio development: TA-SD designs and implements structured processes to facilitate the continuous involvement of the MSE community in the strategic and developmental directions of the consortium. These include formats like strategy meetings and AHoDs. In particular, processes for onboarding and collaboration of pilot projects (PPs) within the IUC teams are created to ensure community-driven development.

WP SD-1.3 Concepts for incentivizing community contributions: To foster acceptance and participation, TA-SD develops incentive models that promote contributions from the MSE community to the shared infrastructure. This includes supporting the publication of ELNs, semantics, datasets and software via repositories, as well as examples of digitalised scientific workflows. TA-SD also develops approaches to empower various stakeholders, especially from academia. Additionally, the Flex Fund concept is designed to encourage pilot projects to contribute within the IUC framework.

WP SD-1.4 Coordinating processes for FAIR and user-friendly data, workflows and software: To ensure that outputs meet the FAIR principles, TA-SD coordinates the implementation of quality checks and procedures with the technical TAs (see 5.4.3 WP SAI-2.4, 5.2.3 WP WLE-6, 5.3.3 WP MDI-1.5). In collaboration with the roll-out group, mechanisms are developed to assess and guarantee that published datasets and software adhere to FAIR standards, thus promoting their reusability and sustainability within and beyond the project. TA-CI will be responsible for dissemination of developed quality criteria (see 5.1.3 WP CI-8.2).

WP SD-1.5 Coordinating processes for decisions on user interfaces: TA-SD coordinates decision-making processes for core user interfaces within the consortium, focusing on strategic services such as the MSE KG and the consortium's central website. Coordination includes stakeholder consultation, technical feasibility checks, and alignment with overall usability goals.

Measure SD-2: Solution and service management (UFR)

This measure ensures the operationalisation of concepts from SD-1 in the form of concrete services and solutions, including their maintenance, further development and adoption by the community. [#DigiTrans](#) [#roll-out](#) [#solutions](#)

KPIs: Number of solutions in development stage, prototype stage and operation stage; number of NFDI-MatWerk community members

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SD-2.1 Community needs, user journeys and translation into requirements: TA-SD develops and implements formats such as user journeys and data journeys, supporting self-empowerment of users and enabling tailored collaboration between pilot projects and development teams. These tools are used in workshops that are co-facilitated with trained NFDI-MatWerk experts (train-the-trainer model) to ensure long-term sustainability and integration into community practices.

WP SD-2.2 Solutions and Portfolio Management: The modular strategy for services and solutions development in NFDI-MatWerk yields a high number of solutions, making a transparent portfolio management indispensable. Processes for translating community needs into products, for bridging between developers and users and for evaluating current TRLs are set up, supported by an information system for portfolio overview. Together with the [#roll-out](#) group and TA-CI, the dissemination status of the respective solutions is assessed and further supported, e.g. with help files, videos, blended learning, workshops and hackathons. A process for decision-making for newly developed products or adaptation of products is installed together with the product owners of the development teams. Foresight processes support the consideration of future trends and developments within MSE and regarding new technologies and their impact.

WP SD-2.3 Roll-out group activities: The newly developed community membership (see 3.1) is an important new framework of NFDI-MatWerk to embed itself closer in the community. TA-SD sets up the digital platform [210] and leads the processes for membership management within the [#roll-out](#) group. Additionally, TA-SD contributes to the [#roll-out](#) group, especially regarding SD-2.2 and SD-3.

Measure SD-3: Communication and outreach strategy (IWM, UFR)

This measure ensures the alignment between the consortium's internal strategy and its external communication. TA-SD works closely with TA-CI to foster a coherent communication structure and representation. [#roll-out](#) [#oneNFDI](#)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

KPIs: Number of scholarly works published

WP SD-3.1 Communication strategy development: A communication strategy and concept including all outside communication channels (Website, LinkedIn, events, conferences, other NFDI consortia events etc) and stakeholder groups will be established by TA-SD, with a strong focus on the alignment with the overall NFDI-MatWerk strategy. TA-SD and TA-CI will operationalize this concept in close exchange to ensure a uniform communication and to support the [#roll-out](#) processes.

WP SD-3.2 Strategic outreach coordination: One important stakeholder group comprises of other initiatives active in similar fields, e.g. the BMFTR (German: Federal Ministry for Research, Technology and Space) initiative MaterialDigital for industry-related projects [211], RDA [59] for global efforts towards FAIR RDM and other NFDI consortia (e.g. FAIRmat, NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Chem, DAPHNE, NFDI4Energy). TA-SD sets up a strategy to ensure continuous alignment and exchange with these stakeholders.

WP SD-3.3 Public Affairs Strategy: This WP aims to establish a dedicated Public Affairs strategy (e.g., press releases) in line with the overall communication strategy (WP SD-3.1). TA-CI will support TA-SD with the implementation and realization of Public Affairs activities.

Measure SD-4: Overall project management and administration (*IWM, UFR*)

Due to the variety of project partners and entities within the consortium, NFDI-MatWerk needs a strong project management on the operational level. TA-SD will ensure overall communication and alignment between TAs and other entities (e.g., Lenkungskreis, Steuerungsgruppe) beyond internal TA management. The aim of this measure is to operationalize the concepts developed in the other measures of TA-SD. [#DigiTrans](#)

Requested funding:

WP SD-4.1 General consortium coordination: The general consortium coordination aims to implement a single point of information, bundling and disseminating information within the consortium as well as documenting for internal purposes. This includes meeting and events scheduling, preparation, facilitation and follow-up as well as general project administration.

WP SD-4.2 Agile Management in IUC teams: NFDI-MatWerk's IUCs are the main vehicle to bridge between the MSE community and the TA's activities. To ensure user-oriented development, TA-SD will steadily manage the progress of the different interdisciplinary teams working on IUCs and support them throughout the development process. To this end, TA-SD will implement agile principles in IUC teams, foster agile tools and perspectives and strengthen agile roles in IUC teams. This WP also aims to implement new (agile) processes in IUC teams and beyond to support the organizational changes necessary to further strengthen community participation in strategy and product portfolio development (SD-1.2).

WP SD-4.3 Ensuring compliance with Funding Agency and NFDI Association: NFDI-MatWerk's development process is guided by regulations of the funding agency as well as the larger NFDI context. This affects, e.g. oversight by DFG, operational guidance by the NFDI directorate, cross-cutting topics in NFDI sections and Base4NFDI as well as the overall organizational embedding of NFDI-MatWerk with its member institutions in the NFDI association. This WP manages, e.g., the interface to the "Konsortium gemäß Satzung", the formal admission of new participation in line with DFG requirements and resulting necessary amendments to the cooperation contract.

WP SD-4.4 Finance management: This WP encompasses the financial administration in cooperation with the applicant institution's finance department to ensure timely allocation and monitoring of financial resources. Management of Flex Funds in this funding phase will require further staff capacities in TA-SD in addition to general finance management. This includes the constant adaptation of the financial forecast for budget planning, along with the documentation required by the funding agency to ensure correct use of funds. The Steuerungsgruppe will be responsible for overall financial oversight.

WP SD-4.5 Qualitative and Quantitative Reporting: Successful project management relies on easy-to-use processes for the different reporting frameworks required. This WP assumes responsibility for coordinating qualitative reporting for the interim report and symposium (funding requirement) as well as quantitative reporting for the indicators set up by the consortium itself as well as by the funding agency and policymakers (e.g., ministry). This WP also aims to implement insightful, efficient reporting mechanisms in Lenkungskreis meeting and other consortium events.

Measure SD-5: Stakeholder Management and Networking (IWM / UFR)

NFDI-MatWerk's activities are always embedded in the legal, political and social context of the German science landscape. Therefore, TA-SD will ensure steady, precise and professional communication channels towards our stakeholders and network. [#oneNFDI](#) [#eosc](#) [#DigiTrans](#)

KPIs: Number of participations in working groups or sections of the NFDI Association, Number of cooperations (DFG Datasheet numbers 1011-1016)

Requested funding: [REDACTED]

WP SD-5-1 Managing "#OneNFDI" contributions: TA-SD will manage the contribution of NFDI-MatWerk's TAs to the NFDI sections, task forces and groups and strengthen the idea of "#oneNFDI" [10]. TA-SD itself will also contribute to different NFDI entities (e.g. Section Industry Engagement [212], Section ELSA [99], Konsortialversammlung, Managementkreis, Finanzkreis, Task Force Evaluation and Reporting [213], Task Force User Research, CC-BY-US group [98]).

WP SD-5.2 Operative links to related initiatives: NFDI-MatWerk strives for synergies with related RDM initiatives (see SD-3.2), e.g. in the German MSE community and thematically "close"

NFDI consortia, e.g. within the engineering or physical sciences (see 3.2.1). In this regard, relations with the initiative MaterialDigital [211] are especially of strategic importance to NFDI-MatWerk. To ensure complementarity and synergies on the organizational level in line with the strategy developed in WP SD-3.2, TA-SD will devote itself to keep in close and regular connection with the Plattform MaterialDigital Executive Office [214] both on the strategic (SD-3.2) as well as the organizational and administrative level (this WP).

WP SD-5.3 Stakeholder management: This WP aims for systematic identification, analysis and prioritization of a stakeholder communication strategy for continuous involvement and acceptance of the relevant stakeholders. Therefore, we assume a variety of differing stakeholders that we all need to address, like fellow scientists with and without IT knowledge, other scientific disciplines and their respective NFDI consortia and RDM organisation as well as the political arena. Developing precise and appropriately tailored communication methods will be a core activity of this TA in close collaboration with TA-CI for its subsequent implementation.

WP SD 5.4 Fostering international relations: This WP aims to strengthen and support NFDI-MatWerk's activities on the international level. One key activity of TA-SD will be the preparation of our International Advisory Board meetings (see 3.4). Furthermore, this WP aims to align activities of the different TAs, including TA-SD, in international initiatives (e.g. activities regarding EOSC National Node, RDA Plenary).

5.5.4 Appropriateness of the Task Area's Representatives

The **Fraunhofer IWM** aims at enabling Germany for pioneering the digital representation of materials and is thus leading ongoing efforts since several years, always in close contact with many supporting partners and stakeholders. The IWM has an exceptionally broad strategic viewpoint at its disposal and can rely on its long-term experience. With the "Innovation Platform MaterialDigital" (since 2019) and the "Landesprojekt MaterialDigital" (since 2017) the Fraunhofer IWM was already set in motion to create digital environments for exchanging materials data, information, and knowledge. Since becoming deputy head of Fraunhofer IWM in 2014, **Prof. C. Eberl** has prioritized the digital transformation of MSE and actively advanced this agenda with colleagues and partners from academia and industry, gradually but sustainably shaping a cultural change within a traditional scientific discipline. His long-standing engagement makes him a natural choice to lead the consortium's strategic efforts.

5.5.5 Connection to Infrastructure Use Cases

TA-SD supports every IUC with agile management expertise (see WP SD-4.2). The role of TA-SD in each IUC is to ensure user-oriented development, alignment with other NFDI-MatWerk entities and documentation and presentation of results. Hence, TA-SD is connected to every IUC.

6 Additional Aspects

6.1 Equity and diversity

Women remain underrepresented in MSE, as in all STEM fields: 26% among young DGM members, but only 14% among established professionals. NFDI-MatWerk shows comparatively higher participation, with two female co-spokespersons (18%) and ~35% female team members, while DFG MSE review boards include 4 women out of 24 members (17%) [215,216]. The project team shows strong international diversity and interdisciplinary collaboration, reflecting NFDI-MatWerk's commitment to inclusivity. PhD students are a key group, to address the shortage of young researchers and train them in good scientific practice using emerging data infrastructures. NFDI-MatWerk engages the MSE community in meetings, workshops, conferences, and seasonal schools, consistently achieving female participation above the discipline average (25–52%) and showing a steady increase, from 26% at the first AHoD event to 33% in 2025. We are convinced that our recognized and widely visible role model PIs (e.g. Ruth Schwaiger, Martina Zimmermann, Birgit Skrotzki, Nina Merkert, Manja Krüger, Heike Leitte, Sandra Korte-Kerzel, Rebecca Janisch, Katrin Stump, Claudia Fleck, Wenwen Song, Irina Sens) have a significant impact on attracting young female scientists to actively participate in NFDI-Matwerk. Moreover, with its discipline-specific female network Women@DGM our consortium can rely on a well-established platform within the DGM community.

6.2 Further comments

Reflexions and comments: The underlying concept of domain-specific consortia is absolutely necessary to meet the different needs of the scientific communities. In the next phase, a more intensive interaction and collaboration with other NFDI consortia is important to create an interoperable infrastructure connecting all disciplines. This can be tackled when a majority of the respective scientific community has successfully established a FAIR research environment. In terms of collaborations, the legal framework of the NFDI Verein is extremely helpful since it allows non-profit collaborations without barriers. While it is still early, making Base4NFDI a benefit for all consortia will be a crucial element. Here, the missing service providers are a bottleneck in terms of large-scale implementation of basic services. The annual financial funding is difficult to handle, especially when funds need to be provided flexibly.

Enhancing NFDI-MatWerk: There is still a long way to go in terms of the Digital Transformation in MSE since all machines and simulation tools need to be connected: we need more: (1) scaling up the infrastructure integration by the community, (2) train the trainers on ontology and workflow development, (3) actionable concepts for FAIR MSE environments based on a scalable and generalizable infrastructure architecture.

With increasing technology-readiness levels (TRLs) of the singular infrastructure elements / solutions, their integration into a MSE infrastructure continuum requires a closer interaction between TAs and therefore a continued organizational development of NFDI-MatWerk. The strongly user-driven infrastructure development by agile, interdisciplinary teams by along the scientific workflows, together with Product Owners from the scientific community has turned out to be a real success. To improve agility in the second funding phase, a substantial share will be made available in the form of flex-funds, related to work packages in IUCs and community needs.

In a competitive scientific environment, the transformation process can only be sustained if incentives support the participation in this community effort. Here, new methods need to be learned and trained (e.g. semantic technologies) and scientific workflows adapted to the digital infrastructure. The effort to get this started and maintained is a fundamental challenge and not a MSE specific issue. It requires a cultural change for each community as well as more resources at all scientific institutions to enable continuous integration of digital infrastructure while organizing the establishment of a shared infrastructure between all stakeholders. This calls for an overarching organizational structure which cannot be solved by individual institutions or consortia.

Disclosure: NFDI-MatWerk has used AI tools (DeepL, ChatGPT) for grammar, style, spelling, summarizing, and translation that do not affect the scientific content. The authors retain full responsibility for the content.

Appendix

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